

2. Graphite/Epoxy: Hercules IM7/8551-7

A new graphite/epoxy material was investigated to determine its elastic and strength properties as follows: $E_{11}=23.5 \times 10^6$ psi, $E_{22}=1.21 \times 10^6$ psi, $G_{12}=0.300 \times 10^6$ psi, $\nu_{12}=0.339$, $X=350.6$ ksi, $X'=150.1$ ksi, $Y=10.6$ ksi, $Y'=25.5$ ksi, $S=S'=26.6$ ksi. The corresponding principal strength parameters are: $F_1=-3.810 \times 10^{-3}(\text{ksi})^{-1}$, $F_2=5.512 \times 10^{-2}(\text{ksi})^{-1}$, $F_{11}=1.900 \times 10^{-5}(\text{ksi})^{-2}$, $F_{22}=3.700 \times 10^{-3}(\text{ksi})^{-2}$, $F_{66}=1.413 \times 10^{-3}(\text{ksi})^{-2}$. Least square analysis was used but no constraint conditions were applied, the results of these calculations are: $F_{12}=3.999 \times 10^{-5}(\text{ksi})^{-2}$, $F_{112}=-4.073 \times 10^{-7}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$, $F_{122}=5.332 \times 10^{-6}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$, $F_{166}=1.619 \times 10^{-6}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$, $F_{266}=1.469 \times 10^{-5}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$. It can be seen in Fig.8 that the cubic curve (3) is closed but that the straight line (4) does pass through the failure region. This of course leads to an open failure surface and indeed such is the case in Fig.9 for a range of σ_6 loading. However, if the constraint condition (13) is imposed to evaluate F_{166} and F_{266} , one can obtain $F_{166}^* = 3.032 \times 10^{-6}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$, $F_{266}^* = 6.219 \times 10^{-5}(\text{ksi})^{-3}$. Thus one does derive a closed failure surface. This is evident in Fig.10.

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical method has been presented utilizing constraint conditions that permits one to construct a closed cubic polynomial failure surface. The procedure is based on three stages of testing and analysis:

- (1) Calculate the principal strength parameters ($F_1, F_2, F_{11}, F_{22}, F_{66}$) based on standard tension, compression and shear tests.
- (2) Conduct biaxial load tests ($\sigma_6=0$) at a minimum of three different stress levels and evaluate the interaction parameters (F_{12}, F_{112}, F_{122}) in the cubic failure equation (3) in $\sigma_1 - \sigma_2$ plane using the method of least squares. If this failure curve is open, invoke closure condition described in this paper.
- (3) Conduct combined loading tests involving shear stress preferably at two different stress levels and invoke the closure condition (13) to evaluate F_{166} and F_{266} using the method of least squares.

This paper presents closed failure surfaces for two different graphite/epoxy materials using the methodology described. The analyst and designer now have available for the first time a closed form of the cubic polynomial failure criterion.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial aid of the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (Grant No. A-2783) who have provided a valuable supplement to the support received from the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (under Grant No. NSG-7409) for the development of the static strength model.

REFERENCES

1. Tennyson, R.C., Nanyaro, A.P., Wharram, G.E., "Application of the Cubic Polynomial Strength Criterion to the Failure Analysis of Composite Materials", J. Composite Materials Supplement, Vol. 14, 1980, pp. 28-41.
2. Tennyson, R.C., Elliott, W.G., "Failure Analysis of Composite Laminates Including Biaxial Compression", NASA CR 172192, Aug. 1983.
3. Tsai, S.W., Wu, E.M., "A General Theory of Strength for Anisotropic Materials", J. Composite Materials, Vol.5, 1971.
4. Tennyson, R.C., MacDonald, D., Nanyaro, A.P., "Evaluation of the Tensor Polynomial Failure Criterion for Composite Materials", J. Composite Materials, Vol.12, 1978, pp. 63-75.
5. Nanyaro, A.P., "Evaluation of the Tensor Polynomial Failure Criterion for Composite Materials", M.A Sc. Thesis, University of Toronto, 1978.
6. Wu, E.M., "Optimal Experimental Measurements of Anisotropic Failure Tensors", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 6, 1972.
7. Tennyson, R.C., "Application of the Cubic Strength Criterion to the Failure Analysis of Composite Structures, NASA CR 165712, May, 1981.
8. Tennyson, R.C., "Experimental Evaluation of the Tensor Polynomial Failure Criterion for Designing Composite Structures", NASA CR 155219, Oct. 1977.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10 Closed failure surface for graphite/epoxy

3-D BOUNDARY ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF MICROMECHANICS PROBLEMS IN METAL GRAIN REINFORCED RESINS

Zhang Heng
(Luoyang Institute of Technology)
Wang Zhenming
(Institute of Mechanics, Academia Sinica, Beijing, China)

*This research program was financially supported by the Scientific Committee of Henan Province

1. INTRODUCTION

The dies used for blow molding, injection molding, compression molding and transfer molding of plastics are now made of Al or Fe grain reinforced epoxy resin or phenolic resin in stead of steel or aluminium alloys, which makes the die making peoriod shorter and greatly reduces the cost and the weight of the dies ¹. The modulus of grain reinforced composites is much lower than metal materials at the die working temperature, which may lead to larger deformations when the dies are subjected to their working loads. This would influence the quality of plastic products directly. It is important for the applications of grain reinforced composites to the die making area that the modulus of the new material with different volumn ratios should be predicted accurately at different temperature.

many micromechanics models, such as the parallel phases, the series, the disperse, the Hirsch's, the Counto's and the Hashin's models, have been proposed for the modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites ². But there exist larger deviations between their computing results and experiment results because the random distribution of the grains in the 3-D domain of the matrix was not considered in all these models. A boundary element technique combining the theory of statistics is presented in this paper for the modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites at higher temperature. The modulus of epoxy reinforced with sphere shaped Al grain at the working temperature of injection molding was tested. Good coincidence was found between the experiment result and the computed result by the boundary element method.

2. BOUNDARY ELEMENT METHOD WITH SUBREGIONS AND CONDENSATION TECHNIQUE

The boundary integral equation of boundary value problems of elastostatics with no body force may be written as follows ³

$$[C_1] \{U_1\} - \int_{\Gamma} [P^*] \{U\} d\Gamma = \int_{\Gamma} [U^*] \{P\} d\Gamma \quad (1)$$

where $\{U\}$ and $\{P\}$ are the boundary displacements and tractions respectively $[U^*]$ and $[P^*]$ are the displacements and tractions corresponding to the Kelvin's fundamental solution. Finite elements were plotted on the boundary of the domain and then Eq. (1) is discretized. Taking each node on the boundary as the source point in the fundamental solution, one obtains the system of equations

$$[H] \{U\} = [G] \{P\} \quad (2)$$

where $\{U\}$ and $\{P\}$ are the node displacements and tractions respectively, $[H]$ and $[G]$ are corresponding coefficient matrices.

Let a 3-D domain Ω consists of a continuous phase (the elastic matrix) and M elastic

inclusions with different phase (the grain), see Fig.1. The domain Ω was divided into $M+1$ subregions: the number for the matrix is zero, and the numbers for the other subregions are $1, 2, \dots, M$ respectively. All the boundaries including the common boundaries between these subregions were discretized and then, a system of equation like Eq.(2) may be written for each subregion. They are listed as following

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [H_0^0 \ H_0^0 \ H_1^0 \ H_2^0 \ \dots \ H_n^0] [U_0^0 \ U_0^0 \ U_1^1 \ U_2^2 \ \dots \ U_n^n]^T = \\
 & [G_0^0 \ G_0^0 \ G_1^0 \ G_2^0 \ \dots \ G_n^0] [P_0^0 \ P_0^0 \ P_1^1 \ P_2^2 \ \dots \ P_n^n]^T \\
 & [H_0^1] \{U_1^0\} = [G_0^1] \{P_1^0\} \\
 & [H_0^2] \{U_2^0\} = [G_0^2] \{P_2^0\} \\
 & \vdots \\
 & [H_0^n] \{U_n^0\} = [G_0^n] \{P_n^0\}
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where H_k^1 and G_k^1 ($k, l=0 \sim M$) represent the submatrices in the coefficient matrices $[H]$ and $[G]$ of the k th subregion corresponding to the boundary adjacent to the l th subregion, \bar{H}^0 and \bar{G}^0 represent the submatrix in the coefficient matrices $[H]$ and $[G]$ of the 0 th subregion corresponding to the known node displacements and node tractions, and H_0^0 and G_0^0 corresponding to the unknown, U_k^1 and P_k^1 ($k, l=0 \sim M$) represent the unknown node displacements and node tractions on the boundary of the k th subregion adjacent to the l th subregion.

On the common boundaries of all the subregions, exist the following conditions

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_k^1 &= U_1^k \quad (k, l=0 \sim M) \\
 P_k^1 &= P_1^k \quad (k, l=0 \sim M)
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Substituting Eq. (4) into Eq.(3) results in the general system of equations

$$\left[\begin{array}{cc|cccccc}
 G_0^0 & H_0^0 & H_1^0 & -G_1^0 & H_2^0 & -G_2^0 & \dots & H_M^0 & -G_M^0 \\
 \hline
 0 & 0 & H_0^1 & G_0^1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & H_0^2 & G_0^2 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\
 \vdots & \vdots \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & H_0^M & G_0^M
 \end{array} \right] \begin{bmatrix} P_0^0 \\ U_0^0 \\ U_1^1 \\ P_1^1 \\ \vdots \\ U_0^M \\ P_0^M \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{H}^0 & \bar{U}^0 + \bar{G}^0 \bar{P}^0 \\ \hline 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

Eq.(5) could be written in an abbreviated form

$$[A]\{X\} = \{F\} \tag{6}$$

One may obtain all the unknown node displacements and node tractions by solving Eq.(6).

Actually, only the node displacements U_0^0 on the outer boundary are wanted. Dividing the matrices in Eq.(6) into submatrices shown in Eq.(5) by dotted lines, one may rewrite matrix $[A]$ as

$$[A] = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

where $A_{11} = [G_0^0 \ H_0^0]$. Let

$$[B] = [A]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where B_{11} and B_{22} are in the same order as A_{11} and A_{22} . Obviously, one need only compute B_{11} and B_{12} to obtain U_0^o . Utilizing $A_{21}=[0]$, the following may be derived

$$\left. \begin{aligned} B_{11} &= A_{11}^{-1} + WR^{-1}P \\ B_{12} &= -WR^{-1} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} W &= A_{11}^{-1}A_{12} \\ P &= A_{21}A_{11}^{-1} \\ R &= A_{22} - PA_{12} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (10)$$

In general, it will save much compute time to obtain U_0^o through Eq.(9) and Eq.(10) in stead of solving Eq.(6).

3. EXAMPLE FOR COMPUTING THE MODULUS OF GRAIN REINFORCED COMPOSITE

Take a typical element from the material of epoxy resin reinforced with 100/200 μ sphere shaped Al grain. Suppose there are three Al spheres included in the element and let the volum ratio of Al to epoxy in the element be equal to that in the given material. Let the element be subjected to load Q uniformly distributed on its upper surface, and displacement constraint on its four lateral surfaces (see Fig.2). According to reference [4], the modulus of Al can be expressed as a function of temperature

$$E_f = 6934.5 + 4.3804 \times 10^{-2}T^2 - 5.1570 \times 10^{-4}T^3 + 8.2148 \times 10^{-7}T^4 \quad (11)$$

The temperature of thermo-deformation of the epoxy resin solidified by MPD agent is 155°C which is much higher than the working temperature of the injection dies (90°C). One may take the modulus of the epoxy matrix as $E_m=320\text{kg/mm}^2$, and consider it as linear elastomer approximately.

The typical element was divided into four subregions and all the boundaries are discretized. To save more compute time, triangular constant elements are used. The total number of the constant elements is 144 (see Fig.3). The average displacement in the load direction on the upper surface of the typical element may be obtained by the method described in section 2, and then the modulus of the composite material can be calculated according to the value of the load and the size of the typical element.

It is found that the modulus computed by this method varies with the position coordinates of the spheres. The coordinates of the sphere centres were randomly given 50 times by the computer and the boundary element meshes were plotted automatically. Repeating the modulus calculation for each of the 50 times, one obtains 50 values of the modulus. After frequency grouping, a histogram for above data is made and the frequency distribution curve is plotted (Fig.4). Let the computed frequency distribution curve be approximated to the Weibull frequency distribution function

$$F(E) = \frac{b}{E_* - E_0} \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^{b-1} \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^b \right\} \quad (12)$$

then the parameters E_0 , E_* and b in Eq.(12) are determined. The mean of the weibull variable may be written as

$$E_c = \int_{E_0}^{\infty} \frac{Eb}{E_* - E_0} \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^{b-1} \exp \left\{ - \left[\frac{E - E_0}{E_* - E_0} \right]^b \right\} dE \quad (13)$$

Using variable transformation, one obtains

$$E_0 = E_0 + (E_* - E_0) \Gamma(1+b) \quad (14)$$

where Γ represents Γ function. The value of E_0 computed from Eq.(14) may be considered as the modulus of the Al grain reinforced epoxy resin at the temperature when the injection die works. The variance of the Weibull variable may be written as follows

$$\sigma^2 = (E_* - E_0)^2 \left[\Gamma \left(1 + \frac{2}{b} \right) - \Gamma^2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{b} \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

The value of σ^2 may become smaller if one takes more sphere grains in the typical element.

4. EXPERIMENT

Following the testing standard ISO 604 for thermosetting plastics, 12 test specimen were made in the same volumn ratio as in the above example. High temperature gauges was used for the load and the temperature of the specimen was kept by a controled electricity heating circle. The value of the modulus measured may be evaluated

$$E = \frac{\Delta \sigma}{\Delta \epsilon} \quad (16)$$

where $\Delta \sigma$ and $\Delta \epsilon$ are the increments of the stress and the strain measured respectively.

For 100/200 μ sphere shaped Al grain reinforced epoxy resin with 50% volume ratio, at the die temperature of 80°C for the injection molding of Amide 1010[7], the modulus computed by the boundary element method is $E_c=1160.\text{kg/mm}^2$ and the measured value is $E=965.12\text{kg/mm}^2$.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

The advantages of the boundary element method are simple data preparing, easy to produce element mesh, good accuracy and shorter compute time etc. The numerical technique proposed in this paper for modulus calculation of grain reinforced composites, combining the boundary element method and statistic theory, may count in the random distribution of the reinforcing grains in the matrix .The computed result for the sphere shaped Al grain reinforced epoxy resin is found in good coincidence with the experiment, which shows the feasibility of this technique.

The deviation of the computed result may come from two aspects. The number of repeatedly computed times is too small or the working temperatuer of the die is so high such that the epoxy resin no long keeps linear elastic. The former may be avoided by taking the number of computed times larger than 50 or taking more inclusions in the typical element. The visioelastic behavior should be considered in the calculations when the second situation occurs.

REFERENCES

1. SinKeits and Yie Soujin, Dies of Plastic Products, Light Industrial Publisher, 1985.
2. Robert N., Hand Book of Composite Materials, Prentice-Hall, Inc., New Jersey, 1983, P296-308.
3. Brebbia, C.A., Tells, J.C.F. and Wrobel, L.C., Boundary Element Techniques, Springer-Verlag, New York, 1984, P253-275.
4. Ying Dishin, On Fatigue Behavior of Al Alloys at High Temperature, master these's of Luoyang Institute of Technology, 1988.

5. Beijing Institute of GRP, Hand Book of GRP Design, China Construction Industry Publisher, 1986, P35, P161.
6. Go Zhinton, Statistic Theory of Fatigue, National Defence Industry Publisher, 1986, P82-90
7. Meter and Instrument Bureau of the ministry of Machine Building Industry, Injection and Compression Molding of Plastics, Machine Building Industry Publisher, 1985, P236-237.

Fig.1 Domain Ω with M Inclusions

Fig.2 Typical Element

Fig.3 Boundary Element Mesh

Fig.4 Weibull Distribution Function

TYPICAL DAMAGE ANALYSIS FOR FIBER COMPOSITES

G.S. Yang and Y.C.Lu
 (Dept. of Applied Mechanics, National University of Defense
 Technology Changsha, Hunan, China)

SUMMARY

Damage in composite materials is generally of highly complex nature. Recently, extensive study on selected configurations of composite laminates using various non-destructive techniques has helped advance the understanding of damage mechanisms (Hahn, 1979) and has shown that cracking both of unidirectional lamina and off-ply laminates occur in the form of matrix cracks growing parallel to the orientation of fibers (Master and Reifsnider, 1982; Yang et al., 1988). And the nonlinear mechanical behavior and reduction in stiffness of laminates have been investigated both experimentally and analytically (Hahn and Tsai, 1973; Highsmith and Reifsnider, 1982; R. Talreja, 1985; Yang and Shan, 1988; Yang and Lu, 1988).

In this paper, the typical damage characters for glass/epoxy composite materials are found from experimental results, which are quite different from in metals, such as matrix cracks occur and grow parallel to the orientation of fibers, even if under loading in the orientation of fibers for unidirectional lamina or under complex loading of shear and tension for symmetrically plied laminates; poisson's ratios and shear coupling ratios increase with increasing load, and tension in the orientation of fibers effects shear stress-strain curves. Along the line of micro-cracks damage theory presented by G.S. Yang and Y.C. Lu, 1988, the predictions of typical damage show very good agreement with the experimental results.

ELASTIC RESPONSE OF DAMAGED LAMINATES

Following the procedure suggested by G.S. Yang and Y.C. Lu, 1988, we obtain the damaged elastic coefficients as follows.

The effective off-axis modulus, poisson's ratios and shear coupling ratios are expressed as.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{E}_x &= E_x / (1 + D_1^{\beta_{xx_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{xx_2}}) \\
 \bar{E}_y &= E_y / (1 + D_1^{\beta_{yy_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{yy_2}}) \\
 \bar{G}_{xy} &= G_{xy} / (1 + D_1^{\beta_{\gamma\gamma_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{\gamma\gamma_2}}) \\
 \bar{\nu}_{yx} &= \nu_{yx} \frac{1 + D_1^{\beta_{xy_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{xy_2}}}{1 + D_1^{\beta_{xx_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{xx_2}}} \\
 \bar{\eta}_{xy,x} &= \eta_{xy,x} \frac{1 + D_1^{\beta_{x\gamma_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{x\gamma_2}}}{1 + D_1^{\beta_{xx_1}} + D_2^{\beta_{xx_2}}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

$$\bar{\eta}_{xy,y} = \eta_{xy,y} \frac{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{y1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{y2}}{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{y1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{y2}}$$

and

$$\bar{\nu}_{xy} = \bar{\nu}_{yx} \frac{\bar{E}_y}{\bar{E}_x} = \nu_{xy} \frac{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{xy1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{xy2}}{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{y1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{y2}}$$

$$\bar{\eta}_{x,xy} = \bar{\eta}_{xy,x} \frac{\bar{G}_{xy}}{\bar{E}_x} = \eta_{y,xy} \frac{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{xy1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{xy2}}{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{y1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{y2}} \quad (2)$$

$$\bar{\eta}_{y,xy} = \bar{\eta}_{xy,y} \frac{\bar{G}_{xy}}{\bar{E}_y} = \eta_{y,xy} \frac{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{xy1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{xy2}}{1 + D_1^\beta \gamma_{y1} + D_2^\beta \gamma_{y2}}$$

in which D_1, D_2 represent the damage variables corresponding to the tensile mode and shear mode, and β_{ij} are material's constants.

The nominal engineering coefficients can be expressed as.

$$\begin{aligned} E_x &= 1/\bar{a}_{11}^* & E_y &= 1/\bar{a}_{22}^* \\ G_{xy} &= 1/\bar{a}_{66}^* & \gamma_{yx} &= -\bar{a}_{12}^*/\bar{a}_{11}^* \\ \eta_{xy,x} &= \bar{a}_{16}^*/\bar{a}_{11}^* & \eta_{xy,y} &= \bar{a}_{26}^*/\bar{a}_{22}^* \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

in which \bar{a}_{ij}^* ($i, j=1, 2, 6$) represent the normalized effective compliance components.

COMPARISON BETWEEN PREDICTION AND EXPERIMENTAL DATA

In this investigation, glass/epoxy composite material was used. The dimensions of specimens and loading conditions are the same as shown by G.S. Yang and X.Q. Shan, 1988.

Fig.1 shows the poisson's ratios of 60°, 45° and 30° degree symmetrically plied laminates, respectively. It is obvious to note that, for 30° and 45° degree specimens, the poisson's ratios increase with increasing load.

Fig.2 shows the shear coupling coefficients of 60°, 45° and 30° degree symmetrically plied laminates, respectively. Although there was no coupling effect for symmetrically plied laminates during initial load, it is found that the coupling coefficients increase with further increasing load due to growing matrix cracks.

Fig.3 shows the shear stress-strain curves of unidirectional laminae under tensile stress along the orientation of fibers. It is clear to note that the larger tensile stress, the smaller fracture stress and fracture strain.

All the prediction results, calculated by micro-cracks damage model, show very good agreement with the experimental data, as illustrated in figs.

(Conclusions and References are neglected)

Fig.1

Fig.2

Fig.3

STUDY ON TEST METHOD FOR SHEAR PROPERTIES OF SANDWICH CONSTRUCTIONS
OR CORES

Zhou Zhulin
Yong Yundi
(Shanghai GRP Research Institute, China)

ABSTRACT

The shear properties of sandwich constructions or cores are one of main performance indexes in the design of sandwich construction products. The selection of the test specimen dimensions is studied for the test and the theory in this paper. It is proved that the length-to-thickness ratio of the test specimen $l/h \geq 12$ is reasonable. The scientific conclusion and reasonableness of Chinese State Standard of GB 1455 1 are demonstrated.

TEST RESULTS

1. The test results of the specimen having different dimensions
The shear test results of different length specimen of sandwich constructions having polyurethane foamed core are shown in Table 1 (the thickness of the specimen is 12mm). The shear test results of different thickness specimen are shown in Table 2.

Table 1 The effect of the specimen length on test results

Dimensions of specimen	1(mm)	150		90		60		
	1/h	12		7.5		5		
Shear properties	τ_c		G_c		τ_c		G_c	
Test average value MPa	0.32	4.76	0.27	5.01	0.21	3.11		
Coefficient of variance Cv (%)	5.7	2.8	17.5	2.7	5.8	1.5		

Table 2 The effect of the specimen thickness on test results

Dimensions of specimen	h mm	12	17	15	30	45	60					
	1 mm	150	150	60	60	60	60					
	1/h	12	8.8	4	2	1.3	1					
Shear Properties	τ_c	G_c										
Test average value MPa	0.32	4.47	0.26	3.53	0.22	3.51	0.16	2.93	0.092	2.01	0.056	1.36
Coefficient of variance Cv (%)	4.4	1.5	7.5	2.7	6.8	3.9	4.4	13.8	12.8	10.6	6.3	11.9

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

In order to determine accurately the shear properties of sandwich constructions or cores, the distribution of the shear stresses in core along the length of specimen should be uniform as far as possible, and the stress caused by additional bending moment should be reduced as lower as possible, so that it may be approaching the pure shear state.

1. The distribution of the shear stress along length of specimen

From the force equilibrium and the deformation compatibility of elements 1*, 2* and 3*, the following differential equation may be obtained finally

$$r_{,xx} - \beta^2 r_x = 0 \quad (1)$$

The distribution of the shear stress along the specimen length may be solved from Eq. (1) as follows:

$$\tau_c = \frac{P\beta \cosh \beta x}{2b \sin \beta l/2} \quad (\text{when single shear})$$

$$\tau_c = \frac{P\beta \cosh \beta x}{4b \sin \beta l/2} \quad (\text{when double shear}) \quad (2)$$

where P is load, b and l are width and length of the specimen, respectively. For the test fixture and the specimen dimensions specified in Chinese State Standard of shear test method (GB 1455) and the shear moduli range (2-300 MPa) of the sandwich construction, the relative errors between the maximum shear stress and the minimum one are

$$\frac{\tau_{\max} - \tau_{\min}}{\tau_{\min}} \times 100 = \begin{array}{l} 4.7\% \text{ (when } G_c=300 \text{ MPa)} \\ 0.9\% \text{ (when } G_c=60 \text{ MPa)} \\ 0.03\% \text{ (when } G_c=2 \text{ MPa)} \end{array}$$

For ordinary sandwich cores, their shear moduli generally are smaller, but the rigidity of loading steel plate specified in test method of GB 1455 is bigger, hence, β is very small. If the hyperbolic function $\sin h(\beta l/2)$, $\cosh \beta x$ in the formula (2) are spreaded into the series of power function, and taking the first term of the series then the formula (2) will become as follows:

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{bl} \quad (\text{when single shear})$$

$$\tau_c = \frac{P}{2bl} \quad (\text{when double shear}) \quad (3)$$

The formula (3) is a calculating formula in the test method of GB 1455, and consequently, GB 1455 is reasonable.

2. The stress caused by the additional bending moment of load

When the test specimen of sandwich constructions or cores are tested by shear load in tension and compression, the additional bending moment will be produced because the load apply on the loading steel plates. Due to the normal stress caused by additional bending moment in core, the shear strength of core is reduced. Therefore, it is very important to design reasonably the tested fixture and the specimen dimensions.

The maximum normal stress caused by this additional bending moment in the both ends of the specimen is approximately as follows:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{6M}{bl^2} = \frac{3Ph}{bl^2} \quad (4)$$

Whether honeycomb core or foamed plastic, their strength of compression and shear are all controlled by stability^{2,3}. For the foamed core of polyurethane as shown in Table 1 and 2, they are simultaneously subjected to the stress of compression and shear. According to the criterion of stability under combined stress of axial compression and shear

$$\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_{cr}} + \left(\frac{\tau}{\tau_{cr}}\right)^n = 1 \quad (5)$$

The relation between the shear strength of core and the dimensions of the specimen

may be got finally

$$\tau_c = \tau_{cr} (1-1.92 h/l)^{1/n} \quad (6)$$

According to formula (6), The theoretical value of shear strength are calculated for the cores in Table 1 and 2, and the calculating results are shown in Table 3 (n take 1.5). Thus it can be seen, the calculated results by stability criterion under action of combined stresses are accorded with the test value.

Table 3 Comparison of the theoretical value with test value of the core shear strength

Ratio of specimen dimensions 1/h	12	7.5	5	4
Test value MPa	0.32	0.27	0.21	0.21
Theoretical value MPa	0.34	0.28	0.25	0.23
Relative error (%)	5.9	3.6	16.0	8.7

CONCLUSION

From the results of sandwich construction or core specimens tested by us and theoretical analysis, the following conclusions may be given:

1. Provided the dimensions of the specimens are same and the design of test fixture is reasonable, whether adopting the single and double shear or tension-shear and compression-shear, the difference of test results is less, and their test results may be compared. Therefore, it is reasonable that Chinese State Standard GB 1455 adopts single tension-shear or compression-shear.
2. When the length-to-thickness ratio of the specimen 1/h is smaller, the effect of the specimen dimension on test results is very great. When $1/h \geq 12$, the effect is less, according to calculation of the strength theory of maximum shear, this effect is less than 1%, by calculating of the stability criterion under combined stress, this effect is less than 10%. The theoretical value calculated by the latter is accorded with the test results.
3. Using the test fixture and specimen dimension specified in Chinese State Standard of test method GB 1455, the shear stress distributions along the length of specimen are uniform, and the normal stress caused by additional bending moment is smaller. Therefore, Chinese State Standard of test method GB 1455 is reasonable and scientific. The shear properties determined by this method are more accurate than that determined by flexural one.

REFERENCES

1. GB 1455, Test method for shear properties of sandwich constructions or cores (in Chinese).
2. Zhou Zhulin, Basic properties of honeycomb core (paper proceeding of 5th on GRP/ Composites), 1983, (in Chinese).
3. HILYARD, N.C., MECHANIC OF CELLULAR PLASTIC, LONDON, 1982.
4. Handbook of mechanism Manufacture, Mosko, 1962, (in Russian).

EVALUATION OF THE STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR AT A T-SHAPED CRACK LOCATED AT THE INTERFACE OF TWO BONDED STRIPS BY THE OPTICAL METHOD OF CAUSTICS

Wen-Xue Wang*, Yoshihiro Takao**, Toshiro Suhara***

* : Department of Mechanics, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan, CHINA

** : Research Institute for Applied Mechanics, Kyushu University, Kasuga JAPAN

***: Department of Mechanics, Toua University, Shimonoseki, JAPAN

ABSTRACT

One of the basic crack problems in composite materials, that is, a T-shaped crack located at the bimaterial interface is investigated experimentally by means of the optical method of caustics. The T-shaped crack consists of the interface crack and the perpendicular crack. A new experimental method for the bimaterial interface crack is developed to obtain the stress intensity factors. It uses the transverse and longitudinal sizes of caustics instead of two distances between and points of each caustic curve. This method is applied to a T-shaped crack at the interface between two sectionally bonded epoxy strips with different material constants. Present experimental results are compared with the previous theoretical ones.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials consist of the matrix and the fiber with the diameter and volume content of about 0.01mm and 30 to 50%, respectively. Thus, the interface between constituents has a significant role in various aspects of the strength of composite materials. For example, the fracture process in composites is quite complicated compared to the previous structural materials due to the interface. Usually it exhibits a variety of failure modes such as fiber breaking, matrix cracking, debonding and delamination even in a small fractured area. It is supposed that a small crack initiating in either one of constituents propagates and hits the interface at the early stage of the fracture. The interface may arrest it, keep up the propagation into the other medium, or deviate it into debonding or delamination along the interface itself as a T-shaped crack (see Fig.1). Each process depends on the mechanical properties of the matrix and fiber and also their interface. The T-shaped crack could also be seen macroscopically at the final stage of fracture in laminates. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the mechanical characteristics of the T-shaped crack

Fig.1 A model specimen for a T-shaped crack at the interface in composites (mm).

Fig.2 Optical analysis of a caustics.

for the profound understanding of the strength of composite materials. Many efforts have been made on this subject [1-3] theoretically. There is no experimental report on this subject within the knowledge of authors.

In this paper, the stress intensity factors at the T-shaped crack tips will be obtained experimentally with the use of the optical method of caustics. First, a new method to handle the caustics is presented. It is effective to a bimaterial interface crack. The previous technique used two distances between end points of each caustics curve. In practice, it is quite difficult to locate these points in the case of a bimaterial interface crack. Here, both transverse and longitudinal sizes of caustics are used. Next, this method is applied to two types of bimaterial T-shaped crack to obtain the stress intensity factors. Finally, these factors are compared with the theoretical values [1], which shows the acceptable capability of the present experimental method.

2. CAUSTIC EQUATION AND STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS

A light beam passing through a transparent plate near the crack tip under loading is deviated by the variation of thickness and refractive index of the plate as shown in Fig.2. Consequently, a strongly illuminated curve appears on a screen as the caustics. Basic equations for the caustics with nomenclatures in Fig.2 are as follows [4],

$$\bar{r}' = \lambda_m \bar{r} - z_o t c_o \text{grad}[(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2) \pm \xi(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)], \quad \lambda_m = \frac{z_o + z_i}{z_i} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial x'}{\partial r} \frac{\partial y'}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial x'}{\partial \theta} \frac{\partial y'}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where t is the plate thickness and c_o and ξ are stress optical constants of the plate. Moreover, σ_1 and σ_2 are principal stresses near the crack tip and can be expressed in term of the stress intensity factors k_i . Thus, the caustic curves yield the stress intensity factors using Eqs.(1) and (2).

A bimaterial interface crack tip has the singularity of both opening and in-plane sliding modes in general. Therefore, its caustic curves are rather complicated than the opening mode case as shown in Fig.3, where two pairs of caustics in solid and dotted lines are obtained in case of a non-vanishing ξ . The vanishing ξ turns two pairs into one pair. The above equations do not yield the simple explicit relation between k_i and the representative values of caustic curves, being different from the opening mode with a quite simple relation between k_1 and D_1 . Theocaris [3] used two distances, AB and CD. However, it is quite difficult to measure them.

Here, a new method using the transverse and longitudinal global sizes, D_1 and D_2 , is proposed. It is shown numerically that D_2/D_1 is a function of $\eta = k_1/k_2$ in practice within the wide range of k_2 as shown in Fig.4. We can obtain the relation between D_1 and k_2 for each η , too. The present process is as follows. First, D_1 and D_2 are mea-

(a) Opening mode (b) Mixed mode
Fig.3 Caustics in epoxy specimen (see Table 1).

Fig.4 D_2/D_1 as a function of $-\eta (= -k_1/k_2)$

Table 1 Material constants.

Epoxy	Young's modulus $E(\text{kg/mm}^2)$	Poisson's ratio ν	Stress optical coefficient $c'_o(\text{mm}^2/\text{kg}\cdot 10^{-3})$	Coefficient of optical anisotropy
A	334.50	0.35	-1.04	0.26
B	201.50	-0.38	-2.05	0.12

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The specimens are 4mm thick and made of two sectionally bonded epoxy strips with various crack lengths, a and b . Material constants are given in Table 1. Two types of Young's modulus ratio are provided. The interface crack tip in Fig. 1 closes under tension due to the Poisson's effect. Thus, the compressive load P is used to obtain k_1 and k_2 at the interface crack tip of a specimen-C with a little wider perpendicular slit. The k_1 at the perpendicular crack tip is obtained under tension T from a specimen-T with a little wider interface slit. These slits are checked not to close in the experiment. Figure 5 shows the optical arrangement. A He-Ne laser light beam was used. The z_o and z_i are set to be about 2m and 1m, respectively. Caustic curves on the screen were photographed at each loading step as shown in Fig. 6. Two pairs of open curves are formed around each crack tip as predicted in Fig. 3. Figure 7 shows the present stress intensity factors in solid lines. They are in good agreement with the previous theoretical ones [1]. This is the first experimental verification to these problems within the knowledge of authors and shows that the present experimental method is acceptable.

4. CONCLUSION

1. A new experimental technique for the bimaterial interface crack is proposed, using the optical method of caustics.
2. Stress intensity factors of a T-shaped crack at the bimaterial interface in composites are obtained. These are in good agreement with the previous theoretical values.

This work was carried out as a part of the dissertation of the first author at the Research Institute for Applied Mechanics, Kyushu University. We are grateful to Professors K. Takahashi and K. Kawatate for their valuable discussions.

REFERENCES

1. Wang, W.X., Takao, Y. & Suhara, T., JSME Int. J., Ser. I, 31(1988), pp. 201-208.
2. Wang, W.X., Takao, Y. & Suhara, T., JSME Int. J., Ser. I, 31(1988), pp. 709-717.
3. Theocaris, P.S., Acta Mechanica, 24(1976), pp. 807-819.
4. Wang, W.X., Ph. D. Dissertation, Kyushu University, (1988), (in Japanese).

Fig. 5 Optical arrangement.

sured from the caustic curves on the screen. Figure 4 yields k_1/k_2 for each D_2/D_1 . The relation between D_1 and k_2 for the fixed k_1/k_2 is used to obtain k_2 . Finally, k_1 is determined. The detailed numerical processes are presented in [4].

(a) P=200kgf (b) T=50kgf
 Fig.6 Caustics at (a) interface and (b) perpendicular crack of a bimaterial T-shaped crack.

(a) interface crack (b) perpendicular crack
 Fig.7 Stress intensity factors.

CRACK POINT STRESS SINGULARITIES AT DIFFERENT ANISOTROPIC MEDIA INTERFACE

Cai Siwei
Hefei Polytechnic University, China

ABSTRACT

The expressions for the stresses at a general point around the interfacial crack between two dissimilar anisotropic materials are derived in this paper. The analysis is based on Lekhniskii's stress potential of anisotropic elastic theory and the Fourier Transformation is applied. The order of strength of crack stress singularity is determined. It is easy to check and see that the crack in a homogeneous anisotropic medium and the crack between two dissimilar isotropic media are only the special cases of the problem discussed in this paper.

1. Formulation

Two semiinfinite anisotropic plates bonded together along the x-axis. Assume there is a through crack at the interface $y=0$, $-a < x < a$. According to the plane elastic problem, the Airy stress function U satisfies the compatibility equation

$$a_{11}U_{,yyyy} - 2a_{16}U_{,xyyy} + (2a_{12} + a_{66})U_{,xxyy} - 2a_{26}U_{,xxyy} + a_{22}U_{,xxxx} = 0 \quad (1)$$

a_{ij} are elastic constants of the anisotropic material. The stresses are given by

$$\sigma_x = U_{,yy}, \quad \sigma_y = U_{,xx}, \quad \tau_{xy} = -U_{,xy} \quad (2)$$

$U(x,y)$ is a function of real with Fourier Transformation $G(\xi, y)$

$$G(\xi, y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} U(x,y) e^{i\xi x} dx \quad \xi > 0, \xi < 0 \quad (3)$$

Taking the Fourier Transformation of equation (1) we have

$$a_{11}G_{,yyyy} + 2ia_{26}\xi G_{,yyy} - (2a_{12} + a_{66})\xi^2 G_{,yy} - 2ia_{26}\xi^3 G_{,y} + a_{22}\xi^4 G = 0 \quad (4)$$

The general solution of equation (4) is

$$\text{For } y > 0; \quad G^{(1)}(\xi, y) = \begin{cases} A_1(\xi) \exp(-is_1 \xi y) + B_1(\xi) \exp(-is_2 \xi y) & \xi < 0 \\ C_1(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_1 \xi y) + D_1(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_2 \xi y) & \xi > 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{For } y < 0; \quad G^{(2)}(\xi, y) = \begin{cases} A_2(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_1 \xi y) + B_2(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_2 \xi y) & \xi < 0 \\ C_2(\xi) \exp(-is_1 \xi y) + D_2(\xi) \exp(-is_2 \xi y) & \xi > 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

$A_1(\xi), B_1(\xi) \dots D_2(\xi)$ are arbitrary complex valued functions of their arguments, $s_1, \bar{s}_1, s_2, \bar{s}_2$ satisfy

$$a_{11}s^4 - 2a_{16}s^3 + (2a_{12} + a_{66})s^2 - 2a_{26}s + a_{22} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } s_1 = \alpha_1 + i\beta_1, \quad s_2 = \alpha_2 + i\beta_2, \quad \beta_1 > 0, \quad \beta_2 > 0 \quad (8)$$

\bar{s}_1, \bar{s}_2 are complex conjugates of s_1, s_2 . $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ are real constants.

Invert the Fourier Transformation in (3) we get

$$U^{(k)}(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} G^{(k)}(\xi, y) e^{-i\xi x} d\xi \quad k=1,2 \quad (9)$$

as $U(x, y)$ must be real function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_1(\xi) &= \overline{A_1(-\xi)}, \quad D_1(\xi) = \overline{B_1(-\xi)}, \quad C_2(\xi) = \overline{A_2(-\xi)}, \\ D_2(\xi) &= \overline{B_2(-\xi)} \quad \xi > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

in (5), (6). Hence we get

$$\text{For } y > 0, \quad G^{(1)}(\xi, y) = \begin{cases} A_1(\xi) \exp(-is_1 \xi y) + B_1(\xi) \exp(-is_2 \xi y), & \xi < 0 \\ \overline{A_1(-\xi)} \exp(-i\bar{s}_1 \xi y) + \overline{B_1(-\xi)} \exp(-i\bar{s}_2 \xi y), & \xi > 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$\text{For } y < 0, \quad G^{(2)}(\xi, y) = \begin{cases} A_2(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_1 \xi y) + B_2(\xi) \exp(-i\bar{s}_2 \xi y), & \xi < 0 \\ \overline{A_2(-\xi)} \exp(-is_1 \xi y) + \overline{B_2(-\xi)} \exp(-is_2 \xi y), & \xi > 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

As the region $y > 0$ and $y < 0$ are occupied by different anisotropic materials in our problem, we write down

1. For $y > 0$

$$U^{(1)}(x, y) = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \{ A_1(\xi) \exp(-is_1 \xi y) + B_1(\xi) \exp(-is_2 \xi y) \} e^{-i\xi x} d\xi \quad (13)$$

$$\sigma_y^{(1)} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \{ A_1(\xi) e^{-is_1 y \xi} + B_1(\xi) e^{-is_2 y \xi} \} e^{-i\xi x} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (14)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^{(1)} = \frac{-\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \{ s_1 A_1(\xi) e^{-is_1 \xi y} + s_2 B_1(\xi) e^{-is_2 \xi y} \} e^{-i\xi x} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (15)$$

$$\sigma_x^{(1)} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \{ A_1(\xi) e^{-is_1 \xi y} s_1^2 + B_1(\xi) e^{-is_2 \xi y} s_2^2 \} e^{-i\xi x} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (16)$$

If on region $y > 0$ we have

$$\begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{16} \\ & a_{22} & a_{26} \\ \text{sym} & & a_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}$$

then

$$\frac{\partial u_x^{(1)}}{\partial x} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left\{ A_1(\xi) e^{-is_1 \xi y} (a_{11}s_1^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_1) + B_1(\xi) e^{-is_2 \xi y} (a_{11}s_2^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_2) \right\} e^{-i\xi x} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (17)$$

Assume the external force applied on the cracked surfaces only. Letting

$$u_x^{(1)} = 0 \quad \text{when } x=y=\infty, \text{ we have}$$

$$u_x^{(1)} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left\{ A(\xi) e^{-is_1 \xi y} (a_{11}s_1^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_1) (-\xi^2) + B(\xi) e^{-is_2 \xi y} (a_{11}s_2^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_2) (-\xi^2) \right\} \frac{e^{-i\xi x}}{-i\xi} d\xi$$

From

$$\frac{\partial u_y^{(1)}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u_x^{(1)}}{\partial y} = a_{16} \sigma_x + a_{26} \sigma_y + a_{66} \tau_{xy} \quad \text{we get}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_y^{(1)}}{\partial x} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left\{ A_1(\xi) e^{-is_1 y \xi} (q_1 - s_1 p_1) (-\xi^2) e^{-i\xi x} + B_1(\xi) e^{-is_2 y \xi} (q_2 - s_2 p_2) (-\xi^2) e^{-i\xi x} \right\} d\xi \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &= a_{11}s_1^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_1 \\ p_2 &= a_{11}s_2^2 + a_{12} - a_{16}s_2 \\ q_1 &= a_{16}s_1^2 + a_{26} - a_{66}s_1 \\ q_2 &= a_{16}s_2^2 + a_{26} - a_{66}s_2 \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

2. For $y < 0$

$$u^{(2)}(x, y) = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left\{ A_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_1 y \xi} + B_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_2 y \xi} \right\} e^{-i\xi x} d\xi \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_y^{(2)} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[A_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_1 y \xi} + B_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_2 y \xi} \right] e^{-ix\xi} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (21)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^{(2)} = \frac{-\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[\bar{s}_1 A_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_1 y \xi} + \bar{s}_2 B_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_2 y \xi} \right] e^{-ix\xi} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_x^{(2)}}{\partial x} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[A_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_1 y \xi} \tilde{p}_1 + B_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_2 y \xi} \tilde{p}_2 \right] e^{-ix\xi} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_y^{(2)}}{\partial x} = \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \left[A_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_1 y \xi} (\tilde{q}_1 - \bar{s}_1 \tilde{p}_1) e^{-ix\xi} (-\xi^2) + B_2(\xi) e^{-i\bar{s}_2 y \xi} (\tilde{q}_2 - \bar{s}_2 \tilde{p}_2) e^{-ix\xi} (-\xi^2) \right] d\xi \quad (24)$$

Here we use

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{a}_{11} & \tilde{a}_{12} & \tilde{a}_{16} \\ & \tilde{a}_{22} & \tilde{a}_{26} \\ \text{sym} & & \tilde{a}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{bmatrix}$$

for material on region $y \leq 0$. \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2 satisfy the equation (7) but a_{ij} in (7) should be instead of by \tilde{a}_{ij} . \bar{s}_1, \bar{s}_2 are conjugates of \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2 and

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{p}_1 &= \tilde{a}_{11} \bar{s}_1^2 + \tilde{a}_{12} \bar{s}_1 - \tilde{a}_{16} \bar{s}_1 \\ \tilde{p}_2 &= \tilde{a}_{11} \bar{s}_2^2 + \tilde{a}_{12} \bar{s}_2 - \tilde{a}_{16} \bar{s}_2 \\ \tilde{q}_1 &= \tilde{a}_{16} \bar{s}_1^2 + \tilde{a}_{26} \bar{s}_1 - \tilde{a}_{66} \bar{s}_1 \\ \tilde{q}_2 &= \tilde{a}_{16} \bar{s}_2^2 + \tilde{a}_{26} \bar{s}_2 - \tilde{a}_{66} \bar{s}_2 \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

The four unknown functions $A_1(\xi), B_1(\xi), A_2(\xi), B_2(\xi)$ in the above equations may be expressed in terms of the stress and displacement discontinuities across the crack-line. It is convenient to introduce the following definitions

$$A(x) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[u_x^{(1)}(x,0) - u_x^{(2)}(x,0) \right] \quad (26)$$

$$B(x) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[u_y^{(1)}(x,0) - u_y^{(2)}(x,0) \right] \quad (27)$$

$$C(x) = \tau_{xy}^{(1)}(x,0) - \tau_{xy}^{(2)}(x,0) \quad (28)$$

$$D(x) = \sigma_y^{(1)}(x,0) - \sigma_y^{(2)}(x,0) \quad (29)$$

The boundary conditions for determining $A_1 \dots B_2$ will be

$$|x| > a \quad A(x)=B(x)=0 \quad C(x)=D(x)=0 \quad (30)$$

$$|x| < a \quad C(x) = \text{known function } C^*(x) \quad (31)$$

$$D(x) = \text{known function } D^*(x) \quad (32)$$

As an example since $\sigma_y^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} - \sigma_y^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = D(x)$, from (14), (21) we have

$$\frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_{-\infty}^0 \{ A_1(\xi) + B_1(\xi) - A_2(\xi) - B_2(\xi) \} (-\xi^2) e^{-i\xi x} d\xi = D(x)$$

as $D(x)$ is a function of real. Using Fourier Transformation we have

$$A_1(\xi) + B_1(\xi) - A_2(\xi) - B_2(\xi) = -D_0/2 \xi^2 \quad (33)$$

where

$$D_0 = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} D e^{i\xi x} dx = \int_{-a}^a D^* e^{i\xi x} dx \quad (34)$$

In the same manner from

$$\tau_{xy}^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} - \tau_{xy}^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = C(x)$$

we have

$$s_1 A_1(\xi) + s_2 B_1(\xi) - \bar{s}_1 A_2(\xi) - \bar{s}_2 B_2(\xi) = c_0/2 \xi^2 \quad (35)$$

$$c_0 = \int_{-a}^a C^*(x) e^{i\xi x} dx \quad (36)$$

from

$$\frac{\partial u_x^{(1)}}{\partial x} \Big|_{y=0} - \frac{\partial u_x^{(2)}}{\partial x} \Big|_{y=0} = A(x)$$

we have

$$A_1(\xi) p_1 + B_1(\xi) p_2 - A_2(\xi) \bar{p}_1 - B_2(\xi) \bar{p}_2 = -A_0/2 \xi^2 \quad (37)$$

$$A_0 = \int_{-a}^a A(x) e^{i\xi x} dx \quad (38)$$

from

$$\frac{\partial u_y^{(1)}}{\partial x} \Big|_{y=0} - \frac{\partial u_y^{(2)}}{\partial x} \Big|_{y=0} = B(x)$$

we have

$$A_1(\xi) (q_1 - p_1 s_1) + B_1(\xi) (q_2 - p_2 s_2) - A_2(\xi) (\bar{q}_1 - \bar{p}_1 \bar{s}_1) - B_2(\xi) (\bar{q}_2 - \bar{p}_2 \bar{s}_2) = B_0/2 \xi^2 \quad (39)$$

$$B_0 = \int_{-a}^a B(x) e^{i\xi x} dx \quad (40)$$

From (33), (35), (37), (39) we can solve A_1, B_1, A_2, B_2 . we get

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(\xi) &= (a_1 A_0 + b_1 B_0 + c_1 C_0 + d_1 D_0) / (-\xi^2) \\ B_1(\xi) &= (a_2 A_0 + b_2 B_0 + c_2 C_0 + d_2 D_0) / (-\xi^2) \\ A_2(\xi) &= (a_3 A_0 + b_3 B_0 + c_3 C_0 + d_3 D_0) / (-\xi^2) \\ B_2(\xi) &= (a_4 A_0 + b_4 B_0 + c_4 C_0 + d_4 D_0) / (-\xi^2) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

a_1, b_1, \dots, d_4 are complex valued constants given in the Appendix. Make sure $A(x), B(x)$ are unknown functions between $-a \leq x \leq a$, we should find their expressions as in the following;

From (14) we write down

$$\sigma_y^{(1)} = \frac{-\text{Re}}{\pi} \int_0^\infty A_1(-\xi) e^{i s_1 y \xi} + B_1(-\xi) e^{i s_2 y \xi} e^{i \xi x} (-\xi^2) d\xi \quad (42)$$

Substituting (34) — (41) in the relation and owing to the intergration

$$\int_0^\infty e^{i(z_j - t)\xi} d\xi = i(z_j - t)^{-1}$$

z_j is a complex variable, we take

$$z_1 = x + s_1 y \quad z_2 = x + s_2 y$$

in the following discussion. Thus we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^{(1)} &= \frac{-\text{Re}}{\pi} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{a_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{a_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) A(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{b_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{b_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) B(t) dt \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{c_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{c_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) C(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{d_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{d_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) D(t) dt \right\} \quad (43) \end{aligned}$$

In the same way we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xy}^{(1)} &= \frac{-\text{Re}}{\pi} \left\{ \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{s_1 a_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 a_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) A(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{s_1 b_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 b_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) B(t) dt \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{s_1 c_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 c_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) C(t) dt + \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left(\frac{s_1 d_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 d_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) D(t) dt \right\} \quad (44) \end{aligned}$$

Introducing other definitions as

$$\sigma_y^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} + \sigma_y^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = H^* \quad |x| < a \quad (45)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} + \tau_{xy}^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = G^* \quad |x| < a \quad (46)$$

Since

$$\sigma_y^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} - \sigma_y^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = D^* \quad |x| < a$$

$$\tau_{xy}^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} - \tau_{xy}^{(2)} \Big|_{y=0} = C^* \quad |x| < a$$

We get

$$2\sigma_y^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} = D^* + H^* \quad (47)$$

$$2\tau_{xy}^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0} = C^* + G^* \quad (48)$$

Substituting $\sigma_y^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0}$, $\tau_{xy}^{(1)} \Big|_{y=0}$ into (47), (48) we have two integral equations, from which we have

$$A(t) = \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi \sqrt{a^2 - t^2}} \left(\int_{-a}^a \frac{F(x) \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}{x-t} dx + L_1 \right) \right. \\ \left. - \left[\operatorname{Re}(c_1 + c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1 + b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \right] C(t) \right. \\ \left. - \left[\operatorname{Re}(d_1 + d_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1 + b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \right] D(t) \right\} dt \\ \div \left[\operatorname{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1 + b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i \right] \quad (49)$$

$$F(x) = (H^* + D^*) \operatorname{Re}(s_1 b_1 + s_2 b_2) i + (C^* + G^*) \operatorname{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \quad (50)$$

$$B(t) = \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi \sqrt{a^2 - t^2}} \left(\int_{-a}^a \frac{T(x) \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}{x-t} dx + L_2 \right) \right. \\ \left. - \left[\operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(c_1 + c_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \right] C(t) \right. \\ \left. - \left[\operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(d_1 + d_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 d_1 + s_2 d_2) i \right] D(t) \right\} \\ \div \left[\operatorname{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 b_1 + s_2 b_2) i \right] \quad (51)$$

$$T(x) = (H^* + D^*) \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i + (C^* + G^*) \operatorname{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \quad (52)$$

L_1, L_2 are constants. Since the displacement components on the crack line are supposed to be continuous across the crack tip $x=0, y=0$. We have

$$\int_{-a}^a A(x) dx = 0, \quad \int_{-a}^a B(x) dx = 0 \quad (53)$$

(53) will be the conditions for us to determine L_1, L_2 . Substituting (49), (51) into (53) we get

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 = & \int_{-a}^a \{ \operatorname{Re}(c_1+c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1+b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \} C^*(t) dt \\ & + \int_{-a}^a \{ \operatorname{Re}(d_1+d_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1+b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \} D^*(t) dt \\ & + \int_{-a}^a \frac{1}{2 \sqrt{a^2-t^2}} dt \quad (54) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_2 = & \int_{-a}^a \{ \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(c_1+c_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \} C^*(t) dt \\ & - \int_{-a}^a \{ \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(d_1+d_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 d_1+s_2 d_2) i \} D^*(t) dt \\ & + \int_{-a}^a \frac{1}{2 \sqrt{a^2-t^2}} dt \quad (55) \end{aligned}$$

2. Stress distribution and stress singularity

From (43), (49)–(52) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_y^{(1)} = & \frac{\operatorname{Re}}{\pi} \left\{ \int_{-a}^a \left\{ \frac{a_1 i}{z_1-t} + \frac{a_2 i}{z_2-t} \right\} \frac{1}{2 \pi \sqrt{a^2-t^2}} \left\{ \int_{-a}^a \frac{F(x) \sqrt{a^2-x^2}}{x-t} dx + L_1 \right\} - \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(c_1+c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1+b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \right\} C^*(t) \right. \\ & \left. - \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(d_1+d_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1+b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \right\} D^*(t) \right. dt + \\ & \left. \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1 s_1+b_2 s_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \right\} \right. \\ & \left. - \int_{-a}^a \left\{ \frac{b_1 i}{z_1-t} + \frac{b_2 i}{z_2-t} \right\} \frac{1}{2 \pi \sqrt{a^2-t^2}} \left\{ \int_{-a}^a \frac{I(x) \sqrt{a^2-x^2}}{x-t} dx + L_2 \right\} - \right. \\ & \left. \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(c_1+c_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 c_1+s_2 c_2) i \right\} C^*(t) \right. \\ & \left. - \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(d_1+d_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 d_1+s_2 d_2) i \right\} D^*(t) \right. dt + \\ & \left. \left\{ \operatorname{Re}(b_1+b_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 a_1+s_2 a_2) i - \operatorname{Re}(a_1+a_2) i \operatorname{Re}(s_1 b_1+s_2 b_2) i \right\} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \int_{-\infty}^a \left(\frac{c_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{c_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) C^*(t) dt + \int_{-a}^a \left(\frac{d_1 i}{z_1 - t} - \frac{d_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) D^*(t) dt \quad (56)$$

$F(x)$, $T(x)$, L_1 , L_2 as shown in (50), (52), (54), (55). Since we have the integration

$$\int_{-a}^a \frac{dt}{(z-t) \sqrt{a^2 - t^2}} = \frac{\pi}{\sqrt{z^2 - a^2}} \quad \text{The singularity of stress at the}$$

vicinity of crack tip will be in order of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{z_1^2 - a^2}}$ or $\frac{1}{\sqrt{z_2^2 - a^2}}$. (1) (2) has

given the special cases of this paper.

From (44) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xy}^{(1)} = & \frac{\text{Re}}{\pi} \left\{ \int_{-a}^a \frac{s_1 a_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 a_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right\} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi \sqrt{a^2 - t^2}} \left(\int_{-a}^a \frac{F(x) \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}{x - t} dx + L_1 \right) \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\text{Re}(c_1 + c_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 b_1 + s_2 b_2) i - \text{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \right) C^*(t) \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\text{Re}(d_1 + d_2) i \text{Re}(b_1 s_1 + b_2 s_2) i - \text{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \right) D^*(t) \right\} dt + \\ & \left(\text{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \text{Re}(b_1 s_1 + b_2 s_2) i - \text{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) \text{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \right) \\ & - \int_{-a}^a \left(\frac{s_1 b_1 i}{z_1 - t} - \frac{s_2 b_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi \sqrt{a^2 - t^2}} \left(\int_{-a}^a \frac{T(x) \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}{x - t} dx + L_2 \right) \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\text{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i \text{Re}(c_1 + c_2) i - \text{Re}(s_1 c_1 + s_2 c_2) i \text{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \right) C^*(t) \right. \\ & - \left. \left(\text{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i \text{Re}(d_1 + d_2) i - \text{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 d_1 + s_2 d_2) i \right) D^*(t) \right\} dt \\ & - \left(\text{Re}(b_1 + b_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 a_1 + s_2 a_2) i - \text{Re}(a_1 + a_2) i \text{Re}(s_1 b_1 + s_2 b_2) i \right) \\ & + \int_{-a}^a \left(\frac{s_1 c_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 c_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) C^*(t) dt + \int_{-a}^a \left(\frac{s_1 d_1 i}{z_1 - t} + \frac{s_2 d_2 i}{z_2 - t} \right) D^*(t) dt \quad (57) \end{aligned}$$

In the same manner we can get $\sigma_y^{(2)}$ $\tau_{xy}^{(2)}$. The formulars are too long and are omitted here.

Appendix

$$\begin{aligned} a_1 = & \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(\frac{s_2 - \bar{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{Q_2 \alpha - Q_1 \beta}{P_2 Q_2 - P_1 Q_2} + \frac{s_2 - \bar{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{Q_1 \gamma + Q_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} \right) \\ b_1 = & \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(\frac{s_2 - \bar{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-P_2 \alpha - P_1 \beta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} + \frac{s_2 - \bar{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-P_1 \gamma - P_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$c_1 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(\frac{s_2 - \tilde{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{\alpha + \beta}{s_1 - s_2} + \frac{s_2 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-\gamma - \delta}{s_1 - s_2} - \frac{\Delta}{s_2 - s_1} \right)$$

$$d_1 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(\frac{s_2 - \tilde{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{s_2 \alpha - s_1 \beta}{s_1 - s_2} + \frac{-s_2 + \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} - \frac{s_1 \gamma + s_2 \delta}{s_1 - s_2} - \frac{s_2 \Delta}{s_2 - s_1} \right)$$

$$a_2 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(\frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{Q_2 \alpha - Q_1 \beta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} - \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{Q_1 \gamma + Q_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} \right)$$

$$b_2 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(- \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-P_2 \alpha - P_1 \beta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} - \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-P_1 \gamma - P_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} \right)$$

$$c_2 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(- \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{\alpha + \beta}{s_1 - s_2} - \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{-\gamma - \delta}{s_1 - s_2} + \frac{\Delta}{s_2 - s_1} \right)$$

$$d_2 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \left(- \frac{s_1 - s_1}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{s_2 \alpha + s_1 \beta}{s_1 - s_2} + \frac{s_1 - s_2}{s_2 - s_1} \frac{s_1 \gamma + s_2 \delta}{s_1 - s_2} + \frac{s_1 \Delta}{s_2 - s_1} \right)$$

$$a_3 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \cdot \frac{Q_2 (\alpha - Q_1 \beta)}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2}$$

$$b_3 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \cdot \frac{P_2 (\alpha + P_1 \beta)}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2}$$

$$c_3 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \cdot \frac{\alpha + \beta}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$d_3 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \cdot \frac{s_1 \alpha + s_2 \beta}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$a_4 = \frac{-1}{2\Delta} \frac{Q_1 \gamma + Q_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2}$$

$$b_4 = \frac{1}{2\Delta} \frac{P_1 \gamma + P_2 \delta}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2}$$

$$c_4 = \frac{1}{2\Delta} \frac{\gamma + \delta}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$d_4 = \frac{1}{2\Delta} \frac{s_1 \gamma + s_2 \delta}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$\Delta = \alpha \cdot \gamma - \delta \cdot \beta$$

$$a = - \frac{\tilde{P}_2 Q_1 - P_1 \tilde{Q}_2}{P_1 Q_2 - P_2 Q_1} + \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_2 - s_1}$$

$$\gamma = - \frac{\tilde{P}_1 Q_2 - P_2 \tilde{Q}_1}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} + \frac{s_2 - \tilde{s}_1}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$\delta = \frac{\tilde{P}_1 Q_1 - P_1 \tilde{Q}_1}{P_1 Q_2 - P_2 Q_1} + \frac{s_1 - \tilde{s}_1}{s_2 - s_1}$$

$$\beta = \frac{P_2 \tilde{Q}_2 - \tilde{P}_2 Q_2}{P_2 Q_1 - P_1 Q_2} + \frac{s_2 - \tilde{s}_2}{s_1 - s_2}$$

$$Q_1 = q_1 - p_1 s_1, \quad Q_2 = q_2 - p_2 s_2, \quad \tilde{Q}_1 = \tilde{q}_1 - \tilde{p}_1 \tilde{s}_1, \quad \tilde{Q}_2 = \tilde{q}_2 - \tilde{p}_2 \tilde{s}_2$$

References

1. K.S.Parihar S.Sowdamini "Stress Distribution in a two dimensional infinite Anisotropic Medium with Collinear Cracks" J.of Elasticity 15 pp193-214 1985
2. K.S.Parihar S. Sowdamini "Stress Distribution in the Neighborhood of Griffith and External Cracks Under General Surface Loading" Eng. Fracture Mech. 16 pp539-555 1982

MOIRE INTERFEROMETRY FOR DEFORMATION MEASUREMENT OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE PLATES

A. Asundi
Department of Mechanical Engineering
University of Hong Kong
Hong Kong

INTRODUCTION

Moire interferometry is a high sensitivity whole-field method for inplane deformation measurement. The corrugations of a high frequency (greater than 500 lines/mm) phase grating along with a reflective film of aluminium are transferred onto the specimen surface via a thin film of epoxy. This specimen grating is interrogated by a virtual reference grating of twice the frequency. Deformation of the specimen and thus the specimen grating, reveals a moire pattern representing contours of the inplane displacement component. By using a cross-line specimen grating, displacement components in two mutually perpendicular directions can be simultaneously recorded for complete determination of the three strain components. Despite its high sensitivity (equal to the pitch of the reference grating), moire interferometry can be used for large deformation studies as well. Furthermore, since the moire effect is geometric in nature, this technique can be used for deformation measurement on isotropic as well as anisotropic materials. In this paper, moire interferometry has been applied for deformation studies on various carbon fibre reinforced composites. Deformation behaviour of these materials will help us to better understand the phenomenon of damage in composite materials.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The specimens (fig. 1(a)) made from carbon fiber reinforced epoxy were of two types. One set of specimens had eight unidirectional plies with fibers oriented along the load (i.e. 0°) direction. The other set also with eight plies were built up as $\pm 45^{\circ}_{2s}$

configuration. One of the unidirectional composite and the $\pm 45^{\circ}$ composite were tested as tensile specimens with a central hole; while the third unidirectional composite was tested as an edge crack specimen subject to uniaxial tension. On the surface of each of these specimens a 600 lines/mm cross grating was created.

These specimens were then placed in the moire intreferometric set-up, schematically shown in fig. 1(b), to simultaneously record both in-plane displacement components. Due to the high sensitivity of the moire interferometric method and the low quality of optics used, initially, at no load, there are a few fringes present. These have to be subtracted from the final pattern to obtain the deformation due to load alone. This subtraction is achieved optically using the moire effect. This effect can be summarised as - the superposition of two nearly identical geometric patterns results in a moire pattern which contours the difference between the two primary patterns. In order for the primary patterns to have good contrast, the primary patterns should be relatively dense. To achieve this high density in moire interferometry, where the initial pattern is sparse, a carrier pattern is added to both the final and initial pattern. This is done by changing the frequency of the reference grating to create carrier fringes parallel to the grating lines and by rotation of the specimen grating to create carrier

fringes approximately perpendicular to the grating lines. In all these tests, this procedure was adopted and hence the patterns represent contours of displacement component due to applied load increment only.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 2 is the u and v displacement contours for the $\pm 45^\circ$ composite. The deformation in all three cases is due to a load increment of 1000N. The difference is that the initial load in the three cases were not identical. The initial loads were (a) 500N, (b) 1500N and (c) 2500N. All three patterns appear identical overall except for some small rotation in 2(a) u-field and 2(b) v-field patterns. However, closer inspection reveals that the band of deformation along the $\pm 45^\circ$ direction is more pronounced in (c) than in (a) or (b). Thus indicating greater damage for higher load as expected. This abrupt change in deformation resulting in these bands are characteristic of composite deformation. The ability to notice these regions even at the small loads indicates the high sensitivity of the moire interferometric method.

Fig. 3 depicts the u and v patterns for a unidirectional composite with a central hole loaded in tension. The anisotropic deformation is quite apparent when these patterns are compared to fig. 2. The load increments for the three cases are (a) 1000N, (b) 2000N and (c) 4000N, with the initial load being identical in the three cases. The u-patterns ought to have been symmetric about the vertical axis, but apparently there is a defect to the left of the hole which causes this asymmetry. Although, this does not seem to appear in the v-patterns, closer examination does show a change in the deformation pattern. The u-pattern contains a fewer number of fringes, and thus the change in deformation due to the defect is more dominant. The bands created due to abrupt change in deformation are as before parallel to the fiber direction. These, however, are more apparent in the v-field patterns, however, the u-field would also reveal these bands if the patterns were quantified. Being parallel to fiber direction, these bands indicate regions of high shear indicative of the load transfer mechanism in composites.

Fig. 4 is the u and v patterns for the unidirectional composite with an edge crack. These were recorded to represent deformation due to load increments of (a) 1000N, (b) 2000N and (c) 4000N. Note that despite the fact that the composite cracked on loading, the gratings were still intact and capable of providing the deformation information. Initially the pattern is quite similar to that for an isotropic case, but then the crack does not extend as for an isotropic material. The crack in fact propagates along the fiber direction indicating that not only the stress but also the material property have a part to play in the fracture of composites. Another interesting feature, is that once the crack is quite large (as in 4(c)), the composite specimen seems to act as two different specimens. The larger width shows deformation characteristic of a specimen under uniform tension, while the smaller strips behave as two separate specimens hinged at the crack tip.

These fringe patterns can be quantified to determine the strain distribution. The relative displacement between neighbouring fringes is 0.83 and thus a first approximation of the strain distribution could be readily determined. However, a more accurate method for strain derivation is desired and is currently being researched.

CONCLUSION

Moire interferometry can provide useful information in obtaining the deformation and strain behaviour of composites. The high sensitivity of the methods enables early detection of damage but the excellent fringes even when the damage is great will provide means of monitoring and predicting damage growth in composites. Quantitative values can be determined but an accurate scheme for strain derivation is desired.

Fig. 1(a)

Fig. 1(b)

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

AN APPROXIMATE METHOD FOR PHOTOELASTIC ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITES

Xu Luwen Luo Wenlin
(Nanjing Aeronautical Institute)

ABSTRACT

A simplified strain-optic law for photoelastic composites has been derived in this paper. According to the law the difference and direction of principal strain of orthotropic model materials can be obtained from only two photoelastic measurements (isochromatic-fringe order and isoclinic angle). It is an approximate method for orthotropic photoelastic analysis. The relative maximum error between the experimental results and the predictions of the approximate method is approaching to 10 percent. By using the law the orthotropic photoelastic analysis is easier to make. Therefore the method is ideal for practical engineering utilization.

INTRODUCTION

In conventional photoelasticity with model materials, the isochromatic-fringe order and the isoclinic parameters are known to give the principal stress difference and the principal stress directions. However, in the case of orthotropic model materials, the isochromatic-fringe order does not directly give the difference in principal stresses, as well as the isoclinic angle does not give the principal stress directions. Several stress (or strain) - optic laws have been proposed to attempt accurately to explain orthotropic photoelasticity in recent years ¹⁻³. Based on the following two conceptions, a simplified strain-optic law for photoelastic composites is presented. First, the isochromatic fringe order for photoelastic composites not only is related to the principal stresses of model but it is also related to principal strains of model. ⁴ Thus, the three independent strain-fringe values f_L^0 , f_T^0 , f_{LT}^0 may be employed in description of orthotropic photoelasticity instead of the three fundamental photoelastic constants f_L , f_T , f_{LT} proposed by Sampson. The second, it has been observed that the degree of orthotropy exhibited by photoelastic composite materials with respect to strain-optic properties is considerably smaller than that with respect to stress-optic properties. Further the isoclinic parameters are much closer to the directions of principal strains than the principal stresses. Therefore, it is rational to introduce an approximate method of orthotropic photoelastic analysis by using the simplified strain-optic law.

SIMPLIFICATION OF THE STAIN-OPTIC LAW

The general form of stress-optic law as proposed by Sampson ² can be written as follows

$$N = \frac{\sigma_1}{f_L} \left\{ \left[(\cos^2 \alpha + \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1} \sin^2 \alpha) - (\sin^2 \alpha + \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1} \cos^2 \alpha) \frac{f_L}{f_T} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{f_L}{f_{LT}} (1 - \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_1}) \sin 2\alpha \right]^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (1)$$

where N is the fringe order per unit thickness of orthotropic model, σ_1 and σ_2 are the

principal stresses, f_L, f_T, f_{LT} are the three independent material-fringe values, and α is the angle between σ_1 and the major-reinforcement direction, L-axis. By introducing the stress-strain relationship for anisotropic materials and employing the three independent strain-fringe values, Eq.(1) can also be written as

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1}{f_L^0} \left\{ \left[(\cos^2 \beta + \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} \sin^2 \beta) - (\sin^2 \beta + \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} \cos^2 \beta) \frac{f_L^0}{f_T^0} \right]^2 + \left[\left(1 - \frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} \right) \frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0} \sin 2\beta \right]^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (2)$$

Fig.1 The coordinate

where ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are the principal strains, β is the angle between ϵ_1 and the major-reinforcement direction, L-axis, and f_L^0, f_T^0, f_{LT}^0 are the strain-fringe values. It is obvious that the relationship between the material-fringe values and the strain-fringe values is given by

$$f_L^0 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_1 - E_2\nu_{12}} \quad f_T^0 = \frac{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}{E_2 - E_1\nu_{21}} \quad f_{LT}^0 = \frac{f_{LT}}{2G_{12}} \quad (3)$$

It may be noted that the degree of orthotropy exhibited by photoelastic composite materials is quite small and so there is no harm in assuming $f_L^0 \approx f_T^0$. Substituting Eq.(3) into Eq.(2), the linear relation between the principal-strain difference and the isochromatic-fringe order of orthotropic model is may be obtained

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2}{f_L^0} \left[\cos^2 2\beta + \left(\frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0} \right)^2 \sin^2 2\beta \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (4)$$

Eq.(4) is a simplified formula. However, Eq.(4) is satisfied only when both principal strain-fringe values are equal each other. Agarwal considered the ratio f_L^0/f_T^0 to be close to 1 (between 1.056 and 0.9664)⁵. The strain-fringe values have been measured by the author through the test of tensile calibration specimens. Optical-characterization results for the test were found to be $f_L^0 = 3.1 \times 10^6$ m/fringe and $f_T^0 = 3.24 \times 10^6$ m/fringe. In view of the fact that the observed value $f_L^0/f_T^0 = 0.957$ is close to the results given by Agarwal. Hence Eq.(4) can be set down as an approximate solution. But in general the angle β in Eq.(4) cannot be directly measured through photoelastic experiments. However, it is of interest to note that the isoclinic parameters are observed to be close approach to the principal-strain directions of the orthotropic model.⁶ Therefore, as an approximation, employing directly the isoclinic parameter ϕ instead of the angle β in Eq.(4), a simplified strain-optic law can be obtained as

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2}{f_L^0} \left[\cos^2 2\phi + \left(\frac{f_L^0}{f_{LT}^0} \right)^2 \sin^2 2\phi \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The error introduced by Eq.(5) is somewhat equivalent to the assuming $f_L^0 \approx f_T^0$ and $\beta \approx \phi$. The terms above are necessary to be verified through test. Based on the result provided by Agarwal⁵ the principal strains for models of orthotropic materials are calculated through Eq.(4) and Eq.(5) respectively and the errors are compared with each and all. The results of calculation are given in Table 1. In view of the fact that the computed results by employing Eq.(4) or Eq.(5) comparing with the experiments are still considered in good agreement, although the relative errors by employing Eq.(5) are big

slightly in some cases.

To verify the simplified strain-optic law, three unidirectionally reinforced tensile specimens oriented at 0 deg, 45 deg and 90 deg were fabricated⁷. For each of the three specimens the strain-fringe values of material and the isoclinical parameters were measured. The principal-strain difference and directions of principal strains were obtained through strain-gage measurements. The experimental results and comparison between measured values and computed values by employing Eq.(4) or Eq.(5) are given in Table 2, where the isoclinical parameter ϕ and angle β are initiated from the reinforced direction of material (L-axis) as shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 Relationship between L-axis and angle

Table 1. Compute Results Based on Agarwal's Datum

Fiber Orientation (deg)	Fringe Order N	Isoclinic Angle ϕ' (deg)	Principal-Strain Angle β' (deg)	Principal-Strain Difference ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)			Error in Principal-strain Difference (%)	
				Experimental	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)
0	0.19	0	0	1747	1774	1774	-1.5	1.5
15	0.33	30	32.8	3260	3249	3245	0.3	0.46
30	0.5	43	43.2	5144	5141	5140	0.1	0.1
45	0.53	53	50.4	6036	6400	6396	-6.0	5.9
60	0.54	62	58.2	5720	5704	5969	0.3	0.4
75	0.49	72	70.3	4660	4798	4790	-3.0	2.7
90	0.44	90	90	3980	4531	4531	-13.8	13.8

Note: Isoclinic angle ϕ' and principal-strain angle β' provided by agarwal are all initiated from the X-axis.

Table 2. Comparison Between Measure and Compute Results

Fiber Orientation (deg)	Fringe Order N	Isoclinic Angle ϕ (deg)	Principal-Strain Angle β (deg)	Principal-Strain Difference ($\mu\text{m}/\text{m}$)			Error in Principal-strain Difference (%)	
				Experimental	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)	Eq.(4)	Eq.(5)
0	0.27	0	0	820	837	837	2	2
45	0.77	4	4.15	2505	2375	2398	5.2	4.6
90	0.65	0	0	2236	2015	2015	9.8	9.8

CONCLUSIONS

For the convenience of engineering application, the method of orthotropic photo-elasticity must be simplified. An approximate analysis of orthotropic photoelasticity employing strain-optic law is provided due to the degree of orthotropic exhibited by photoelastic composite materials with respect to strain-optic properties is considerably small. The principal-strain difference and direction can be obtained from only two photoelastic measurements, the isochromatic-fringe order and isoclinic parameter, by means of the simplified strain-optic law proposed in this paper. This is an approximate method, but with the limited experiments showing a good agreement between the experimental results and predictions of the strain-optic law. Therefore, it is a practical orthotropic photoelastic analysis due to the error levels are within permissible range.

REFERENCES

1. Prabhakaran, R., Experimental Mechanics, 16, 6-10 (1976).
2. Sampson, R.C., Experimental Mechanics, 10(5), 210-216.

3. Prabhakaran, R., Composite Structures, 235-246 (1982).
4. Prabhakaran, R., Fiber Sci. and Tech., 13, 245-253 (1980).
5. Agarwal, B.D., Experimental Mechanics, 23, 55-58 (1983).
6. Xu Luwen, GRP/CM, Supplement, 150-155 (1986).
7. Xu Luwen, Wang Yuoing, Cheng Peiwen, J. Applied Mechanics, Vol.3, No.2, 75-80 (1986).

RESEARCH OF THE BEARING FAILURE
CRITERION FOR COMPOSITES

Xie Ming Jiu Chai Ya Nan
Aircraft Structural Strength Research Institute, China

SUMMARY

The bearing failure criteria for composites were researched using load-deflection ($P-\delta$) curve, TBE-enhanced X-ray technique and the depley technique. Failure criteria investigated covered the first sudden change in slop of the $P-\delta$ curve, a value of 4% the hole diameter elongation, maximum load (P_{max}) and P_{max} divided by 1.5.

Research results showed that there was little difference between the first sudden in slop of $P-\delta$ curve and the $P_{max}/1.5$, which is lower than a value of 4% elongation of the hole diameter. It is possible that the $p_{max}/1.5$ was selected as the bearing failure load simply and conveniently, at this load although there is damage but it did not affect capability of the carrying load.

1. Introduction

Bolted joints were applied widely because of the reliability, transferring higher load and reassemble. Bolted joints have three principle failure modes: tension, shearout and bearing. suitable ratio of the width-diameter and the distance from the centre of the hole to the end of the specimen to diameter were generally given in design handbook in order to avoid tension and shearout failure, only bearing failure is permitted. It is well known that the bearing failure means local failure in contact with the bolt such that an elongation of the hole, but how much deformation is regarded as failure, so criteria are required.

Bearing failure criteria are divided into types: one is based on the limited stress in order that joints have enough strength, so joints can not be broken; the other is based on the limited deformation of bearing holes to ensure that joints cannot be loosened, so integral structures have enough stiffness and too much deformation will be avoided.

Prof. Yang Bing-zhang suggested the damage bearing load is selected according to the first knee point or sudden change in slop of $P-\delta$ curve. Collings used the maximum load sustained by the joint, ASTM stipulated a value of 4% of the hole diameter for plastics, Dasting, Strauss and Oleesky also used a value of 4% of the hole diameter for GRP, Dasting recommends 4% of the hole diameter for all composites, webb used 1% for bolts and 2% for rivets in CFRP, Althof used 0.5% for CFRP. A number of failure are considered by Johson and Mathews who showed that for CFRP and GRP significant damage has occurred around the hole edge when the hole deformation is as low as 0.4% of the diameter. They suggested that this can be met as the definition of failure simply by imposing a safety factor of the maximum load.

As stated above, definitions of the bearing failure are very different, some depend on load, the others depend on deformation. The majority of authors seem to agree on the advisability of a definition based on the latter criteria, however, there is little agreement as to what value should be used.

2. Wxperimental details

The laminates from which the bolted joint specimens were fabricated were made of carbon-epoxy composite. The laminates had a fiber volume fraction of 60%. The nominal layer thickness was 0.125mm. Ply percentages were used 0 : 45 : 90 = 50 : 40 : 10. 0 layers carry the main load. Function of 45 layer is to reduce the effect of stresses concentration in order to soften the joint. Function of 90 layup is to prevent excessive transverse contraction, i.e. to prevent high shear stress within the 45 layers.

Layup sequence of 45,0,-45,0.90.0.45,0.-45.0 was used. The layup sequence were selected to intersperse the ply orientations as thoroughly as possible so as to minimize the number of parallel adjacent plies and, thereby, to minimize the matrix stresses.

Specimen width were 30mm. Edge distances from the center of the hole to the end of the specimen were 20mm. Hole diameter were 5mm.

All the static tensile tests were performed in an INSTRON 1195 test machine. The bolts used throughout the tests were made of 30CrMnSiA. The bolts were torqued to 3.92Nm. A double shear loading fixture was used for tests.

3. Experimental results and analysis

34 specimens were tested. Mean value, standard deviation and variance factor obtained according to the criteria of the sudden slope change, 4% elongation of the hole diameter. $P_{max}/1.5$ and P_{max} are presented in table 1.

The results shows that mean value from the sudden in slope of P- δ curve, which is close to 6.76kN from $P_{max}/1.5$ and is lower than 7.74kN from 4% of the hole diameter. Variance factor respectively are 10% and 13% for the sudden slope change and 4% of the hole diameter, which are larger than 7% based on load. Data scatter based on deformation criteria are larger than that based on load criteria. Specimen precision, assembly technology and experimental operation had a stronger influence on P- δ curves than on failure load.

4. Bearing damage check

The formation of damage zones was examined on a series of specimens by using the TBE-enhanced X-ray technique. TBE-enhanced X-ray picture were taken at four different load levels: 0, 60, 75 and 100% of the ultimate load. Figure 1(a) shows the virgin specimen, where the dark around the hole boundary probably is caused by the heat developed during the drilling and grinding of the hole. Little damage in figure 1(b) is observed at the load of 6.1kN. Bigger damage in figure 1(c) is occurred at the load of 7.5kN, joint should be no use at this load. Figure 1(d) shows big damage at ultimate load.

Using TBE-enhanced X-ray photography technique only shows size of damage zones, it can not point out which layer was damaged. For detection of the concrete damage in each ply specimens were depled at certain load levels. Depleting a specimen loaded to 7.2kN, it was possible to obtain the distribution of fiber failure among the plies. Figure 2 shows the photographs depled from the first ply to the tenth ply. No fibre damage were detected in the 90 ply. On the other hand the notable damage were observed in the 0 and 45 plies. Joint limit load for use should not exceed 7.0 kN from the view of the bearing damage.

5. Conclusions

The ultimate load divided by 1.5 is recommended as the bearing strength failure load on basis of our research. The average hole elongation at that load was lower than 4% of diameter. It has the suitable margins of both strength and stiffness. Moreover, it is very convenient for the engineering use. The X-ray and depley photographs show that the damage was observed at that load, but it is smaller, the capacity of the carrying load may not be effected.

REFERENCES

1. Yang Bing-Zhang, etc. "Method of test for bolt bearing strength of CFRP", Northwest Industrial University

2. Collings. T. A, "The strength of bolted joints in multidirectional CFRP laminates", RAE TR 75127
3. ASTM "Standard method of test for bearing strength of plastics", ASTM D 953-75
4. Dasting. S "Joining and machining techniques", in "Handbook of fibreglass and advanced plastics composites", edited by Lubin
5. Strauss. E. L "Mechanical joints in reinforced plastics structures", Machine Design 32 (1960.3)
6. Oleasky. S. S, Mohr. J. G "SPI Handbook of reinforced plastics"
7. Dasting. S "Joining and machine techniques" in "Handbook of composites", 1981
8. Webb. A. L "Riveting and bolting in carbon fibre composite" in "Jointing in fibre reinforced plastics", 1978
9. Althof. W, Muller. J. "Investigations on bonded and demoun-table joints made from fibre reinforced plastics", Sulzer technical review
10. Johson. M, Matthews "Determinations of safety factors for use when designing bolted joints in GRP", Composites 10 No.2 (1979.4)

	Change of the slop	4% elongation of the hole diameter	$\frac{P_{max}}{1.5}$	P_{max}
mean value	6.58	7.74	6.76	10.14
Standard deviation	0.66	1.00	0.50	0.74
Variance factor	10%	13%	7%	7%

Tab.1 Test Results

Figure 1. X-ray Pictures.

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

Figure 2. Depty pictures.

A NEW FINITE ELEMENT METHOD FOR THE STUDY OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

Xie Zhicheng, Li Rufeng
 Department of Engineering Mechanics
 Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

In present paper, the separate Mindlin's theory is developed and a new approach of FEM has been performed.

Consider a laminated plate made of a thin film and N layers of anisotropic plates bonded in order. The independent variables are chosen as the in-plane displacements and deflection w of the film and the shear strains $\gamma_{xz}^{(k)}$, $\gamma_{yz}^{(k)}$ in the k th layer. On this model, locking can be avoided. To reduce the number of degrees of freedom, the asymptotic and iterative methods are employed. And then, the variables of film and shear can be computed independently and the maximum degrees of freedom of the uncoupled equations are equal to that of one layer Kirchhoff plate. Thus, the computing efficiency is improved considerably, and also the shearing effect is taken into account successfully.

Let k denote a particular ply singled out for study (Fig.1). The generalized displacements of the k th ply are
 where u_k, v_k, w_k are the midplane displacements

$$\{q\} = [u_k, v_k, w_k, \gamma_{1k}, \gamma_{2k}] \quad (1)$$

ply; γ_{1k}, γ_{2k} are the transverse shear strains and $\gamma_{1k} = \gamma_{xz}^{(k)}$, $\gamma_{2k} = \gamma_{yz}^{(k)}$.

Fig.1

Fig.2

According to the separated Mindlin assumption and the continuity conditions at lamina interface of the k th and $k+1$ th plies, these midplane displacements are given as

$$\begin{aligned} u_k &= u_0 + \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} h_l \gamma_{1l} + \frac{1}{2} h \gamma_{1k} - H_k \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} \\ v_k &= v_0 + \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} h_l \gamma_{2l} + \frac{1}{2} h \gamma_{2k} - H_k \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} \\ w_k &= w_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where h_k -- thickness of k th ply; u_0, v_0, w_0 -- displacements of film; $H_k = \sum_{l=1}^{k-1} h_l + \frac{1}{2} h_k$.

In illustration of this theory, the simplest Moley's finite element of the film has

been used. The variables are: u_0^i, v_0^i, w_0^i ($i=1,2,3$) on corner nodes; $\frac{\partial w_0^i}{\partial n}$ ($i=4,5,6$) on mid-side nodes; $\gamma_{1k}^i, \gamma_{2k}^i$ ($i=1,2,3, k=1,2,3, \dots, n$) on corner nodes of the k lamina (fig.2). So the degrees of freedom can be written as

$$\{q\}_e = [u_0^1, u_0^2, u_0^3, v_0^1, v_0^2, v_0^3, w_0^1, w_0^2, w_0^3, \dots]_{(6n+12) \times 1}$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial w_0^4}{\partial n}, \frac{\partial w_0^5}{\partial n}, \frac{\partial w_0^6}{\partial n}, \gamma_{11}^1, \gamma_{11}^2, \gamma_{11}^3, \gamma_{21}^1, \gamma_{21}^2, \gamma_{21}^3, \dots, \gamma_{1n}^1, \gamma_{1n}^2, \gamma_{1n}^3, \gamma_{2n}^1, \gamma_{2n}^2, \gamma_{2n}^3 \right]^T \quad (3)$$

and the generalized displacements of the k ply are

$$\{q\}_k = [N]_k \{q\}_e \quad (4)$$

where matrix $[N]_k$ can be derived from the shape functions.

The variational functional of the k ply can now be expressed as

$$\Pi_{pe}^k = \frac{1}{2} \{q\}_e^T [K_e]_k \{q\}_e - \{q\}_e^T \{F_e\}_k \quad (5)$$

$[K_e]_k$ is the stiffness matrix of the k ply of the element and $\{F_e\}_k$ denotes the loading vector.

Introducing the nondimensional variables $\bar{x}=x/1, \bar{y}=y/1, \bar{u}_0=u_0/1/h, \bar{v}_0=v_0/1/h, \bar{w}_0=w_0/h, \bar{\gamma}_{1k}=\gamma_{1k}/h, \bar{\gamma}_{2k}=\gamma_{2k}/h$. By taking variation of equ. (5), the global stiffness matrix and the loading vector can be obtained as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_w]_1, & \delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_w \bar{\gamma}]_1, & \dots & \dots & \delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_\gamma]_n \\ & \delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_\gamma]_{11}, & \dots & \dots & \delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_\gamma]_{1n} \\ & \delta G_{23}/E_{11} [\bar{K}_\gamma]_{11}, & & & \\ \text{Symm.} & & & \delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_\gamma]_{nn} & \\ & & & \delta G_{23}/E_{11} [\bar{K}_\gamma]_{nn} & \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\bar{w}\} & \epsilon^2 \{\bar{F}_w\} \\ \{\bar{\gamma}_1\} & \delta \{\bar{F}_\gamma\}_{10} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \{\bar{\gamma}_n\} & \delta \{\bar{F}_\gamma\}_{no} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

in which $\epsilon = h/1, \delta = \max(h_k, k=1,2,3, \dots, n)/h$; w -- generalized nodal displacements of the film; γ_k ($k=1,2,3, \dots, n$) -- transverse shear strains of the k ply; E_{11} -- maximum elastic modulus; G_{23} -- minimum shear modulus. If $(G_{23}/E_{11}) \gg \epsilon^2$, the displacement vectors can be expanded in series as

$$\{\bar{w}\} = \{\bar{w}_0\} + \epsilon^2 \{\bar{w}_2\} + \epsilon^4 \{\bar{w}_4\} + \dots \quad (7)$$

$$\{\bar{\gamma}_k\} = \{\bar{\gamma}_{k0}\} + \epsilon^2 \{\bar{\gamma}_{k2}\} + \epsilon^4 \{\bar{\gamma}_{k4}\} + \dots$$

From equations(6),(7), the perturbation equations can be obtained as

$$\epsilon^0 : (G_{23}/E_{11}) [\bar{K}_{\gamma k}] \{\bar{\gamma}_{k0}\} = \{\bar{F}_{\gamma k0}\}$$

$$\epsilon^2 : [\bar{K}_w] \{\bar{w}_0\} = \{\bar{F}_{w0}\} - \delta \sum_{k=1}^n [\bar{K}_{w\gamma k}] \{\bar{\gamma}_{k0}\}$$

$$(G_{23}/E_{11}) [\bar{K}_{\gamma k}] \{\bar{\gamma}_{k2}\} = -[\bar{K}_w] \{\bar{w}_0\} - \delta \sum_{k=1}^n [\bar{K}_{\gamma k1}] \{\bar{\gamma}_{k0}\} \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon^4 : [\bar{K}_w] \{\bar{w}_2\} = -\delta \sum_{k=1}^n [\bar{K}_{w\gamma k}] \{\bar{\gamma}_{k2}\}$$

.....

If condition $(G_{23}/E_{11} \gg \epsilon^2)$ is not satisfied, by the Gauss-Seidel iteration process, the governing equations can be written as:

$$[\bar{K}_w] \{\bar{w}\}_i = \{\bar{F}_{w0}\} - \delta \sum_{l=1}^n [\bar{K}_{w\gamma l}] \{\bar{\gamma}_l\}_{i-1}$$

$$(\delta \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_{\gamma k k}] + G_{23}/E_{11} [\bar{K}_{\gamma k}]) \{\bar{\gamma}_k\}_i = \{\bar{F}_{\gamma 10}\} - \epsilon^2 [\bar{K}_{w\gamma k}] \{\bar{w}\}_i - \delta \epsilon^2 \sum_{l=1}^n [\bar{K}_{\gamma k l}] \{\bar{\gamma}_l\}_i - \delta \epsilon^2 \sum_{l=k+1}^n [\bar{K}_{\gamma k l}] \{\bar{\gamma}_l\}_{i-1} \quad (9)$$

where i indicates the iterative times. In equations (8),(9), the degrees of freedom associated with the film and each layer will not be coupled each other, so these equations can be solved atep by step. The orders of submatrices are obviously smaller than global stiffness matrix. A good result can be obtained with less computation time and storage.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

1. Isotropic square plate subjected to uniformly distributed load q

Fig.3

—Ref. [1]; --Present
 w_0 --deflection in centre;
 t ---thickness; l ---span of plate; $D = Et^3/12(1-\nu^2)$.

2. Simply supported crossply($0^0/90^0/0^0$) square laminate under sinusoidal load

($h_1=.25h, h_2=.5h, h_3=.25h; E_1/E_2=25, G_{12}=G_{13}=.5E_2, G_{23}=.2E_2, \nu_{12}=.25$).

The maximum nondimensional deflections and stresses are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

1/h	Source	\bar{w}	$\bar{\sigma}_x$	$\bar{\sigma}_y$	$\bar{\tau}_{xy}$
1/h=100	Ref 2	4.3369	.5296	.2661	.0210
	(FEM)				
	Present	4.6961	.5342	.2997	.0227
1/h=10	Ref 2	6.6415	.4907	.3561	.0238
	(FEM)				
	Present	7.6108	.5493	.4126	.0418

$$\bar{w} = \left(\frac{10^3 E_2 h^3}{q_0 l^4} \right) w(0,0,0);$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_x = \left(\frac{h^2}{q_0 l^2} \right) \sigma_x(0,0,h/2);$$

$$\bar{\sigma}_y = \left(\frac{h^2}{q_0 l^2} \right) \sigma_y(0,0,h/4);$$

$$\bar{\tau}_{xy} = \left(\frac{h^2}{q_0 l^2} \right) \tau_{xy}(1/2,1/2,h/2).$$

The distributions of $\bar{\tau}_{xz}, \bar{\tau}_{yz}$ through thickness are shown in Fig.4.

Fig. 4 (i)

1/h=10
 — Present
 -- HSDT (Ref. 2)
 - - FSDT (Ref. 2)

Fig. 4 (ii)

Fig.4

$$\bar{\tau}_{xz} = \left(\frac{h}{q_0 l} \right) \tau_{xz}(1/2,0,z);$$

$$\bar{\tau}_{yz} = \left(\frac{h}{q_0 l} \right) \tau_{yz}(0,1/2,z);$$

$$\bar{z} = z/h.$$

3. Simply supported angle-ply($45^\circ/-45^\circ$) square plate subjected to uniform load.

Table 2 and Fig.5 show the result of centre deflections and shear stresses of the plates with two ratios ($h/1=1/10, h/1=1/100$). As we know, these results are not available in previous theories.

Table 2.

w	Ref. 3 (FEM)	Ref. 3 (Series)	Present
1/h=100	9.09	10.30	10.51
1/h=10	11.58	12.79	14.56

Fig.5

$$\bar{\tau}_{xz} = \left(\frac{h}{q_0 l} \right) \tau_{xz} (1/20, 0, z);$$

$$\bar{\tau}_{yz} = \left(\frac{h}{q_0 l} \right) \tau_{yz} (0, 1/20, z);$$

REFERENCES

1. Pugh, E.D.L., Int. Num. Meth. Engng., vol.12, 1978.
2. Reddy, J.N., J. Appl. Mech., vol.51, 1984.
3. Putcha, N.S. and Reddy, J.N., Compu. Meth. Appl. & Eng., 1984.

THREE DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF STRESSES AROUND A
PIN-LOADED HOLE IN A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

Ma Shuya, Li Xiong
Second Institute of Ministry of
Aero-Space, Beijing, China

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results from a 3-dimensional finite element analysis and photoelasticity experiment of stresses around a pin-loaded hole in G/E composite laminates. The 3D-finite element analysis employs the program LXC-3D developed by author, it can be operated in micro-computer PC-XT or AT. The calculated results show good agreement with experimental date.

INTRODUCTION

Because of the widespread usage of fiber-reinforced composite materials in structures, there have been a number of studies to determine the stress distribution around a pin-loaded hole in composite laminates and to predict strengths of pin jointed composite laminates [1-8]. However, these studies were only twodimensional plane stress analysis based on Classical Lamination Theory, and can neither determine the interlaminar stress nor predict accurately the bearing strength since its failure mechanisms are three-dimensional.

In the present work, a 3-dimensional finite element model, named composite element [14], is adopted. Taking into account of that the pin elasticity causes little effect on stress distributions at the hole edge [6], the loaded hole boundary conditions are imposed by introducing radial displacement constraints at the contact surface.

In the experiment, the reflection photoelasticity is used to determine stresses around pin-loaded holes in composite laminates. this method is particularly useful for determining stresses on free(unloaded) surface of the prototype.

DESCRIPTION OF THE COMPOSITE ELEMENT

In the present paper, a 20-noded isoparametric composite element is chosen. Different from Classical Lamination Theory, for the composite element, the material properties are not taken as homogeneous within an element. They are taken discontinuous from layer to layer (of course, taken as continuous, homogeneous and anisotropic within a layer), and displacement within an element is still formulated as ordinary isoparametric elements.

Fig.1 shows the element containing n unidirectional layers. The element stiffness matrix can be given as follows:

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^n \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 B^T D_i B |J| A_i d\xi d\eta d\zeta$$

Fig. 1

where B is the element strain matrix and J is Jacobian transformation matrix.

$$A_i = (t_i - t_{i-1})/2$$

$D_i = T_i C T_i^T$ is the elastic properties matrix for the i th layer.

T_i is the usual transformation relating Cartesian strains to strains in the principal directions of the i th Layer, and C is elastic properties matrix in the principal directions of a layer.

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND EXPERIMENT DATA

In the numerical procedure, a pin joint is treated as a frictionless rigid core inserted into a laminate with a hole of the same diameter as that of the pin. Figure 2 shows the laminate with a pin-loaded hole, coordinate axes, geometry and simple uniaxial loads. A G/E laminate $\{0_2/90_2/0\}_s$ is taken as a representative composite materials for the numerical calculations. Each unidirectional ply has a thickness of 0.6mm giving a 10-ply laminate 6 mm thick. Due to the symmetry of the laminate and the applied load, only 1/4 of the laminate is modeled, and the corresponding boundary conditions are imposed. Fig.3 shows the finite element mesh, only one composite element is used through the half-thickness of the laminate. The boundary conditions of the loaded hole are imposed by introducing radial displacement constraints at the nodes of the contact surface between the pin and the hole. In this study, the limit of the contact angle is given by $\theta = 72^\circ$ (only 9° increments being possible with the mesh adopted). This compares with 74° found by workers [6].

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4 In-plane stress distributions around the pin-loaded hole

Fig. 5 Variation of interlaminar shear stress σ_{z0} in each ply around the hole edge

Fig. 6 Variation of direct stress σ_z in each ply around the hole edge

Fig.4 shows the results of the in-plane stress distribution around a pin-loaded hole in the laminate by 3D-finite element analysis. The results of photoelastic experiment are also given in the figure. It is found that the results of 3D-analysis agree well with experimental data.

Fig.5 shows the distribution of interlaminar shear stress $\sigma_{z\theta}$ in plies. For all plies, the high value occurs around $\theta=30^\circ$ and $\theta=70^\circ$ with the maximum value of 15% nominal bearing stress σ_b ($\sigma_b=P/dt$) at $\theta=30^\circ$ in the outer 0° ply. The values of $\sigma_{z\theta}$ is very small at $\theta=0$ and $\theta=90^\circ$.

Fig.6 shows the distribution of the through-thickness stress σ_z around the hole edge in plies (that of ply 3 and 5 are not given since they are similar to ply 2 and 4, respectively). It is found that at $\theta=0^\circ$, σ_z is very small in the 0° ply but reaches its maximum tensile value $0.075\sigma_b$ in 90° plies. In all 0° plies the maximum tensile stress σ_z occurs around $\theta=90^\circ$ with the value about $0.07\sigma_b$.

There occurs the high tensile stress σ_z around the bearing region of the hole edge in the 90° ply. It may contribute to split of the matrix or to delamination between plies and reduce the bearing strength of laminates. This is consistent with the experimentally observed failure mode [16].

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the present analysis shows that the 3D-finite element model used here gives good agreement with experimental data. The 3D-analysis also suggest that the interlaminar stresses around a pin-loaded hole in a composite laminate are unnegligible. The strength analysis must include interlaminar stresses. The present results also show that it is convenient and feasible using radial displacement boundary conditions.

MICROMECHANICAL ANALYSIS OF 3-D COMPOSITES

S. V. Kuznetsov
 USSR, Moscow
 Moscow Institute of Civil Engineering

3-d composites, especially those made by Sol-Gel-Synthes method are becoming now more and more popular in various applicatons. Temperature fields of different nature and external stress fields produce microstructural stresses, which can exceed adhesive or cohesive strengths of the matrix and the reinforced particles. But micromechanical analysis is needed also in obtaining the average, or 'homogenized' properties of a composite, such as elasticity tensor, linear thermal expansion tensor etc., obtained by two-scale asymptotic analysis.

To solve typical 3-d cell problem of a composite, numerical analysis is needed. For numerical implementation such methods as finite difference (FDM), finite element method (FEM), fast Fourier transform method (FFTM), boundary element method (BEM) can be applied. The great advantage of the latter is the reduction of a 3-d problem to a 2-d one. While those BEM variants which lead to the second kind Fredholm equations are, in general, not applicable to the cell-problem because of cell corners and edges, the BEM formulations connected with the first kind Fredholm equations and separate surfaces supporting vector densities, are better adjusted for the solution of the cell-problem.

The indirect BEM formulation which leads to the first kind integral equations is presented bellow. Let Ω_0 denote the translating-invariant typical cell, containing N reinforced particles, occupying regions Ω_i , $i=1, \dots, N$, such that $\bar{\Omega}_i \cap \bar{\Omega}_j = \emptyset$, $i \neq j$, so none of the particles contact with each other, but instead separated by the matrix material. With minor modifications of the present method it is possible to regard the case of non empty intersections $\Omega_i \cap \Omega_j$ and the case 'particle-inside-particle', which represents thick coated particles. Corresponding boundaries of the cell and particles will be denoted $\partial\Omega_0, \partial\Omega_1, \dots, \partial\Omega_n$.

In the boundaries $\partial\Omega_i$, $i=1, \dots, N$ between particles and matrix an ideal mechanical contact is assumed, so

$$(1) \quad u_{(i)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} = u_{(0)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} ; \quad t_{(i)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} = t_{(0)}|_{\partial\Omega_i} ; \quad i=1, \dots, N$$

where $t_{(i)}$ -corresponding tractions, $u_{(i)}$ is the displacement field. For the cell boundary translate-invariant conditions should be given

$$(2) \quad u_{(0)}(x') = u_{(0)}(x) - A \cdot (x - x')$$

$$\frac{\partial u_{(0)}(x')}{\partial e_p} = \frac{\partial u_{(0)}(x)}{\partial e_p} ; \quad x' \in \Gamma'_p, \quad x \in \Gamma_p$$

where $e_p, p=1,2,3$ -basis in R^3 of the translation group of a periodic structure;
 $\Gamma'_p, \Gamma_p \subset \partial\Omega_0$ -opposite sides of the cell-boundary, so the cell itself is homeomor-
 phic to a cube; A -external deformation tensor.

To construct a periodic solution of (1), (2) auxiliary surfaces are chosen in such way,
 that $\bar{\Omega}_0 \subset \Omega_0$, while $\Omega_i \supset \bar{\Omega}_i, i=1, \dots, N$ so the surfaces $\partial\Omega_i, i=0, \dots, N$ have no inter-
 sections with boundaries $\partial\Omega_j, j=0, \dots, N$. Now integral representation for the dis-
 placement in matrix material has the form

$$(3) \quad u_{(0)}(x) = \sum_{i=0}^N \int_{\partial\Omega_i} E_{(0)}(x-y) \cdot d\mu_{(i)}^0(y), \quad x \in \Omega_0 \setminus \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^N \Omega_i \right)$$

where $E_{(0)}$ is Kelvin's fundamental solution; $d\mu_{(i)}^0$ -unknown vector Radon's measure
 on $\partial\Omega_i$. It should be noted, that $u_{(0)}$ satisfies equations of equilibrium everywhere
 in Ω_0 . Similar procedure can be used to derive integral representations for reinfor-
 ced particles

$$(4) \quad u_{(i)}(x) = \int_{\partial\Omega_i} E_{(i)}(x-y) \cdot d\mu^i(y), \quad x \in \Omega_i$$

where auxiliary surfaces $\partial\Omega_i$ satisfies condition $\bar{\Omega}_i \subset \Omega_i$.

Substitution of the representations (3),(4) into (1),(2) gives a system of the linear
 integral equations, which in operator form can be written

$$(5) \quad B(d\mu) = g$$

where $d\mu = \Pi d\mu^i \times \Pi d\mu_i^0$ while right-hand side g is equivalent to the right-hand side
 of (1), (2).

The solution of (5) can be obtained with the regularization techniques. With minor
 modifications of this method, it is possible to construct the solutions of the thermal
 microstructural stresses in 3-d composites.

A Refined Shear Deformation Theory of Laminated Plates and Shells

Ji-Fan He

Department of Engineering Mechanics
Tsinghua University, Beijing, China

Abstract

Transverse shear effects are important for analysis of laminated plates and shells made of advanced composite materials. Piecewise linear tangential displacements (and constant transverse displacement) across the thickness are fit to model the warpage of cross section of them after deformation. To simplify the model, we may connect the rotary angles of the normals to the undeformed middle surface of each layer in accordance with an assumption that the transverse shear strains across any two different layers are linearly dependent each other. Then no matter how many the number of layers is, the set of governing differential equations given is merely of the twelfth order, only two orders higher than that in the usual shear deformation theory.

1. Introduction

Transverse shear effects are important for analysis of laminated plates and shells made of advanced filamentary composite materials with low span-to-depth ratios. The usual shear deformation theory given by Yang, Norris and Stavsky (1966), Whitney and Pagano (1970) and Dong and Tso (1972) is much more accurate than the classical lamination theory for the prediction of transverse deflections. However, the accuracy for determining tangential stresses is not improved. Piecewise linear tangential displacements (and constant transverse displacement) across the thickness are fit to model the warpage of cross section after deformation and predict tangential responses. It was proposed by Sun and Whitney (1973), Srinivas (1973), Epstein and Glockner (1977) and Seide (1980). However, as the number of layers is large, the order of the set of governing equations is too high. To simplify it, in this paper we connect the rotary angles of the normals to the undeformed middle surface of each layer after deformation in accordance with an assumption that the transverse shear strains across any two different layers are linearly dependent each other. Then the governing equations are derived on the basis of the principle of minimum potential energy.

2. The Governing Equations of Equilibrium of Laminated Shells and Plates

A laminated shell of thickness h with $N_1 + N_2 + 1$ layers of each thickness t_i is considered. A system of orthogonal curvilinear coordinates is defined by the coordinates α_1 and α_2 corresponding to the lines of curvature on the middle surface of the shell and the coordinate z along the normal to the middle surface. The Lamé's coefficients and the normal curvatures in the directions of α_1 and α_2 are denoted by A_1, A_2 and k_1, k_2 respectively. The number of the layer including the middle surface of the shell is zero. Suppose the displacements in the i -th layer of the shell after deformation as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} u_1^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, z) &= u_{1m}^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) + (z - z_i) \psi_1^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \\ u_2^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, z) &= u_{2m}^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2) + (z - z_i) \psi_2^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \\ w^{(i)}(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, z) &= W(\alpha_1, \alpha_2), \\ &(i = -N_2, \dots, 0, \dots, N_1) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Here $u_{1m}^{(i)}$, $u_{2m}^{(i)}$ and z_i are the tangential displacements and the value of the coordinate z of the points on the middle surface of the i -th layer. $\psi_1^{(i)}$ and $\psi_2^{(i)}$ are the rotary angles of the normals to the undeformed middle surface. Considering $k_1 h, k_2 h \ll 1$, we can obtain the transverse shear strains in the i -th layer as

$$\gamma_{13}^{(i)} = \psi_1^{(i)} + \frac{1}{A_1} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \alpha_1} - k_1 u_{1m}^{(i)}, \quad \gamma_{23}^{(i)} = \psi_2^{(i)} + \frac{1}{A_2} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \alpha_2} - k_2 u_{2m}^{(i)}, \quad (2)$$

In accordance with the aforementioned assumption we can express $\gamma_{13}^{(i)}$ and $\gamma_{23}^{(i)}$ by means of $\gamma_{13}^{(o)}$ and $\gamma_{23}^{(o)}$

$$\gamma_{13}^{(i)} = \lambda_{11}^{(i)} \gamma_{13}^{(o)} + \lambda_{12}^{(i)} \gamma_{23}^{(o)}, \quad \gamma_{23}^{(i)} = \lambda_{21}^{(i)} \gamma_{13}^{(o)} + \lambda_{22}^{(i)} \gamma_{23}^{(o)}, \quad (3)$$

Here $\lambda_{ij}^{(i)}$ etc. are undetermined constants. Besides, the continuity of interlaminar tangential displacements has to be kept. Define $U_1(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ and $U_2(\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$ as the tangential displacements of the points on the middle surface of the shell ($z=0$). Then the tangential displacements of the points in every layer can be expressed in terms of $U_1, U_2, W, \psi_1^{(o)}$ and $\psi_2^{(o)}$. The expression of the strain energy density per unit middle surface area of the shell can be obtained as

$$E = \frac{1}{2} (N_1 \varepsilon_1 + N_2 \varepsilon_2 + S \varepsilon_{12} + M_1 \kappa_1 + M_2 \kappa_2 + M_{12} \tau_{12} + M_{21} \tau_{21} + M'_1 \kappa'_1 + M'_2 \kappa'_2 + M'_{12} \cdot 2\kappa'_{12} + Q_1 \gamma_{13}^{(o)} + Q_2 \gamma_{23}^{(o)}) \quad (4)$$

Here N_1, N_2, \dots, Q_2 are all generalized internal forces. The expression for the overall generalized force-strain relations is

$$\begin{bmatrix} \{N\} \\ \{M\} \\ \{M'\} \\ \{Q\} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B_I] & [B_{II}] & [F] \\ [B_I]^T & [D] & [D_c] & [H_I] \\ [B_{II}]^T & [D_c]^T & [D'] & [H_{II}] \\ [F]^T & [H_I]^T & [H_{II}]^T & [G] \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \{\varepsilon\} \\ \{\kappa\} \\ \{\kappa'\} \\ \{\gamma\} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The external forces acting on the shell consist of the body forces, the forces applied on the upper and lower surfaces and those applied on the part S_I of the side boundary S of the shell. The equations of equilibrium of laminated shells can be obtained on the basis of the principle of minimum potential energy as follows.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (N_1 A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (N_{21} A_1) + N_{12} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} - N_2 \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} + k_1 A_1 A_2 (Q_1 + Q'_1) + A_1 A_2 F_1 &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (N_{12} A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (N_2 A_1) + N_{21} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} - N_1 \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} + k_2 A_1 A_2 (Q_2 + Q'_2) + A_1 A_2 F_2 &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} [(Q_1 + Q'_1) A_2] + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} [(Q_2 + Q'_2) A_1] - A_1 A_2 (k_1 N_1 + k_2 N_2) + A_1 A_2 F_z &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (M_1 A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (M_{21} A_1) + M_{12} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} - M_2 \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} - A_1 A_2 Q_1 + A_1 A_2 m_1 &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (M_{12} A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (M_2 A_1) + M_{21} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} - M_1 \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} - A_1 A_2 Q_2 + A_1 A_2 m_2 &= 0, \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Here

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N_{12} &= S + k_2(M_{21} + M'_{12}), & N_{21} &= S + k_1(M_{12} + M'_{12}), \\ Q'_1 &= \frac{1}{A_1 A_2} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (M'_{12} A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (M'_{12} A_1) + M'_{12} \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} - M'_2 \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} \right], \\ Q'_2 &= \frac{1}{A_1 A_2} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_1} (M'_{12} A_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha_2} (M'_{12} A_1) + M'_{12} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \alpha_1} - M'_1 \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \alpha_2} \right], \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

The set of Eq.(6) can be expressed with the displacements U_1, U_2, W and rotary angles $\psi_1^{(o)}, \psi_2^{(o)}$. It is of the twelfth order. No shear correction factors are introduced. Consistent boundary conditions can be given: Besides, two independent sets of simultaneous linear algebraic equations which $\lambda_{ij}^{(i)}$ etc. for $i > 0$ or $i < 0$ must satisfy respectively can also be obtained. There exists coupling between them and Eq.(6) through the coefficients in the equations. We can solve Eq.(6) and them together with iteration methods. Having obtained the solution of $U_1, U_2, W, \psi_1^{(c)}$ and $\psi_2^{(o)}$ and $\lambda_{ij}^{(i)}$ etc., we can further calculate the displacements and the tangential strain and stress components of each point in the shell. Then from the equations of equilibrium of three-dimensional elasticity we can calculate transverse shear stresses, which are also important for analysis and design of laminated shells.

In the case of laminated plates we have $k_1 = k_2 = 0$. We adopt a cartesian system of coordinates. Then $\alpha_1 = x, \alpha_2 = y$ and $A_1 = A_2 = 1$. The expressions of the strains and changes of curvature become simpler. In Eq. (5) the submatrices [F], [H_I] and [H_{II}] become zero ones. The expressions of the elements of the submatrix [G] become simpler, but the other submatrices are identical with those in the case of laminated shells. The differential equations of equilibrium of laminated plates for the middle plane displacements U, V, W and rotary angles $\psi_x^{(o)}, \psi_y^{(o)}$ can be obtained in a symmetric form.

Because the space is limited, some typical examples are not given here. They indicate that even though a laminated plate or shell with a low span-to-depth ratio is calculated, a better estimate of displacements and stresses, both tangential and transverse, can be obtained.

References

- [1] Yang, P.C., Norris, C.H. and Stavsky, Y., Elastic Wave Propagation in Heterogeneous Plates, Int.J. Solid Struct., 2,4(1966) 665-684.
- [2] Whitney, J.M. and Pagano, N.J., Shear Deformation in Heterogeneous Anisotropic Plates, J. Appl. Mech., 37,4 (1970) 1031-1036.
- [3] Dong, S.B. and Tso, F.K.W., On a Laminated Orthotropic Shell Theory Including Transverse Shear Deformation, J. Appl. Mech. 39, 4(1972) 1091-1097.
- [4] Sun, C.T. and Whitney, J.M., Theories for the Dynamic Response of Laminated Plates, AIAA J. 11,2 (1973) 178-183.
- [5] Srinivas, S., A Refined Analysis of Composite Laminates, J. Sound Vibra., 30, 4 (1973) 495-507.
- [6] Epstein, M. and Glockner, P.G., Nonlinear Analysis of Multilayered Shells, Int.J. Solid Struct., 13, 11 (1977) 1081-1089.
- [7] Seide, P., An Improved Approximate Theory for the Bending of Laminated Plates, in Mechanics Today. Vol.5, ed. by Nemat-Nasser, S., Pergamon Press (1980), 451-466.

AN ANALYSIS OF LARGE DEFLECTION BENDING OF
SHALLOW LAMINATED COMPOSITE SHELLS

Chen Xiaodan

(Guangzhou Municipal Engineering Technology Development & Research
Centre, Guangzhou, China)

Dong Wanlin and Huang Xiaoqing

(South China Univ. of Tech., Guangzhou, China)

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the application of Dynamic Relaxation (DR) method to the problem of large deflection bending of shallow laminated composite shells. The numerical results are given for orthotropic doubly curved shallow shells as well as two-layer, cross-ply cylindrical and doubly curved shallow shells. The results obtained are compared with available data. The phenomenon that central deflection of cylindrical shells may jump to the opposite direction when load increases to some larger value has been found.

MAIN FORMULAE OF ITERATIONS

We consider the shallow shells over a square plane shown in Fig. 1. A certain properly curved panel paralleled with the shell surface and the z-axis is taken in the direction normal to the oxy surface. The radii of curvatures along x-direction and y-direction are denoted as R_x and R_y respectively. According to finite deflection bending equilibrium equations of shallow shells, the corresponding dynamic equations can be written as

Fig. 1

$$N_{1,x} + N_{6,y} = \rho_u \cdot U_{,tt} + \mu_u \cdot U_{,t}$$

$$N_{6,x} + N_{2,y} = \rho_v \cdot V_{,tt} + \mu_v \cdot V_{,t}$$

$$M_{1,xx} + 2M_{6,xy} + M_{2,yy} + N_1 W_{,xx} + 2N_6 W_{,xy} + N_2 W_{,yy} + (N_{1,x} + N_{6,y}) W_{,x} + (N_{6,x} + N_{2,y}) W_{,y} - (N_1/R_x + N_2/R_y) + q_z = \rho_w \cdot W_{,tt} + \mu_w \cdot W_{,t}$$

where ρ_r and μ_r ($r=u,v,w$) are fictitious densities and damping factors respectively; subscript t denotes time.

performing center finite-difference procedure to the above equations, the iterative form formulae for the velocities \dot{U} , \dot{V} and \dot{W} at each nodal point can be written. From $U_{,t} = \dot{U}$, ect., the iterative formulae of displacements U, V and W can be obtained.

The method of calculating fictitious densities may be found in Refs. [1,2]. The damping factors can be evaluated by the method proposed in reference [3].

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In all examples for computation, following clamped boundary condition is considered:

$$U = V = W = W_{,x} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, a$$

$$U = V = W = W_{,y} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0, a$$

The problem of large deflection bending of specially orthotropic doubly equal curved shallow shells under uniformly distributed external pressures has been first considered. In the analyses the following geometrical data are used: $a = 15(\text{in})$; $h = 0.193(\text{in})$; $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$, $200(\text{in})$ and ∞ (i.e. orthotropic plate). The material properties used in the analyses are: $E_L = 36.39 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $E_T = 4.79 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $G_{LT} = 1.96 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $\nu_{LT} = 0.3$.

The obtained results are plotted in Figs. 2-3. From the analyzing of the numerical results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From Fig. 2 it can be seen that present results for orthotropic plate ($R_x = \infty$ $R_y = \infty$) agree well with the results in Ref. [4].
2. The influence of the curvatures of shallow shells on the deflections are very pronounced. The central deflections of shallow shells with $R_x = R_y = 200(\text{in})$ are larger than that with $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$ under same load.
3. From Fig. 2 it can be seen that when the load increases to a certain extent the central deflection of the shallow shell with very small curvature (e.g. $R_x = R_y = 200(\text{in})$) becomes larger than that of the plate because the deflection of the shell has offsetted the influence of the curvature and it has become almost flat panel, and the plate has become curved.
4. From Fig. 3 it is demonstrated that for the shell with $R_x = R_y = 50(\text{in})$ the jump of deflection may occur when the load increases to $160(\text{psi})$.

The problem of large deflection bending of laminated composite shallow shells subjected to uniformly distributed external pressures has been considered. In the computations, $a = 508(\text{in})$; $h = 2.54(\text{in})$; and R_x and R_y are chosen as following three cases: (a) $R_x = R_y = 2540(\text{in})$, (b) $R_x = R_y = \infty$ (i.e. laminate), (c) $R_x = \infty$ and $R_y = 2540(\text{in})$ (i.e. cylindrically shallow shell). The material properties used in the analyses are: $E_L = 40 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $E_T = 10^6 (\text{psi})$, $G_{LT} = 0.6 \times 10^6 (\text{psi})$; $\nu_{LT} = 0.25$. The obtained results are plotted in Fig. 4-5. From the analyzing of the numerical results obtained, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. From Fig. 4 it can be seen that under same load the central deflections of the doubly equal curved shallow shell are less than that of the cylindrically shallow shell, and when load is lower the central deflections of the cylindrically shallow shell are less than that of the laminate.
2. From comparisons between present results for cylindrically shallow shell and finite-element results in Ref. [5] (see Fig. 4) it is found that when loads are lower both are coincident, and when loads are higher they are different to each other. And when load reaches $1.8(\text{psi})$ a phenomenon that the central deflection of the shell jumps to opposite direction will occur, which had not be reported in Ref. [5]. The shaps of crosssection at $x = a/2$ before and after the jump are shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) respectively.

REFERENCES

1. Huang Xiaqing, ACTA Materiae Composite Sinica, 2(2) (1985), 47. (in Chinese).
2. Cassell, A. C. and Hobbs, R. E., Int. J. Num. Meth. Engng., 10(1976), 1407.
3. Dong wanlin, Huang Xiaqing and Fan Fuqun, J. of South China Univ. of Tech., (to be published, in Chinese).
4. Chandra, R., Fibre Sci. and Tech., 10(1977), 123.
5. Reddy, J. N. and Chandrashekhara, K., AIAA J., 23(3) (1985), 440.

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

A REFINED HIGHER-ORDER THEORY FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES

L. ZHANG J.G. CHEN

Department of Engineering Mechanics, Shanghai Jiaotong University,
Shanghai, The People's Republic of China

A refined higher-order shear deformation theory of laminated composite plates is presented. The theory accounts for a parabolic variations of the transverse shear strains and the transverse deflections through the thickness of the plate. Exact closed-form solutions of symmetric cross-ply laminates are obtained and the results are compared with three-dimensional elasticity solutions, first-order shear deformation theory solutions and other higher-order shear deformation theory solutions. The present theory predicts the deflections and stresses more accurately when compared to the first-order theory and other higher-order theory.

INTRODUCTION

A number of articles dealing with the transverse shear deformation have appeared in the literature. These are too numerous to review here. We only cite some classical⁽¹⁻⁹⁾ papers and those which constitute a background for the present paper. The theories that account for transverse shear deformations can be classified into two major classes on the basis of assumed fields: (1) stress based theories^(2-4,8,9) and (2) displacement based theories^(1-5,7). The stress-based theories are derived from assumed stress fields, which are assumed to vary linearly over the thickness of the plate. The transverse normal and shear stresses are then derived from the equilibrium equations of the three-dimensional problem in the theory of elasticity. The governing equations of the theory are derived using a stationary variational theorem. The displacement based theories are derived from an assumed displacement field. The governing equations are derived using the principle of minimum total potential energy.

The theory used in the present work comes under the class of displacement based theories. In Reissner-Mindlin type theories^(1,5-7,10-14), the displacement field accounts for linear or higher-order variations of midplane displacements through thickness. In higher-order theories, an additional dependent unknown is introduced into the theory with each additional power of the thickness coordinate. In addition, these shear deformation theories do not satisfy the conditions of zero transverse shear stresses on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate, and require a shear correction to the transverse shear stiffnesses. Recently, Levinson⁽¹⁵⁾, Murthy⁽¹⁶⁾ and Reddy⁽¹⁷⁻¹⁹⁾ presented refined plate theories that use the idea of Basset¹ in expanding displacements in the powers of the thickness coordinate. The main novelty of these works is to expand the in-plane displacements as cubic functions of the thickness coordinate, treat the transverse deflection as a function of the x and y coordinates and satisfy the conditions of zero transverse shear strains on the top and bottom surfaces of the plate. Murthy's work differs from Levinson's in two respects: first, Murthy uses average displacements through thickness; secondly, the theory is also developed for laminated plates. The work of Reddy differs from the other two in that the governing equations are derived from the principle of virtual work. The present development is to expand the in-plane displacements as cubic functions of the thickness coordinate and the transverse deflection as a parabolic function of the thickness coordinate. The governing

equations are also derived from the principle of virtual work. To illustrate the accuracy of the present theory, exact solutions are presented for symmetrically laminated cross-ply rectangular plates.

KINEMATICS

The present refined theory uses a displacement approach, much like in the Reissner-Mindlin type theories. It not only satisfies the conditions that the transverse shear stresses vanish on the plate surfaces but also accounts for the effect of the variation of the transverse deflection along the thickness.

The displacement field is written as

$$U = U_0 + Z \left(\psi_x - \frac{z}{2} \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial x} - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \psi_x + \frac{h^2}{4} \frac{\partial \epsilon_z}{\partial x} \right) \right)$$

$$V = U_0 + Z \left(\psi_x - \frac{z}{2} \frac{\partial \psi_z}{\partial x} - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \psi_x + \frac{h^2}{4} \frac{\partial \epsilon_z}{\partial x} \right) \right)$$

$$W = W_0 + Z \psi_z + z^2 \epsilon_z$$

EQUILIBRIUM EQUATIONS

Here we use the principle of virtual displacements to derive the equilibrium equations appropriate for the displacement field and constitutive equations. The principle of virtual displacements can be written in analytical form as

$$\int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{\Omega} (\sigma_1 \delta \epsilon_1 + \sigma_2 \delta \epsilon_2 + \sigma_3 \delta \epsilon_3 + \sigma_4 \delta \epsilon_4 + \sigma_5 \delta \epsilon_5 + \sigma_6 \delta \epsilon_6) dAdz - \int_{\Omega} q \delta w dx dy = 0$$

EXACT SOLUTIONS FOR SYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY PLATES

We consider the exact solutions for simply supported, symmetric cross-ply rectangular plates. The Navier approach is used.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

The three-dimensional elasticity solutions of Pagano⁽²⁰⁾ and Pagano and Hatfield⁽²¹⁾ for simply supported rectangular plates under sinusoidal loading are used to assess the improvement by the present theory. Table 1-3 contain nondimensionalized deflections and stresses for the three problems. For Problem 1 and 2, the results obtained using the present

Theory are compared with those obtained by three-dimensional elasticity theory⁽²⁰⁾⁽²¹⁾, the higher-order shear deformation plate theory (HSDPT)⁽¹⁸⁾ and the first-order shear deformation theory⁽²²⁾, respectively. The exact stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and σ_6 computed using the constitutive equations of the present theory are greatly improved over the results obtained using the first-order and classical plate theory and are also more accurate than those obtained by the higher-order shear deformation plate theory⁽¹⁸⁾ when the ratio a/h is less than 10. The shear stresses obtained using constitutive equations are not as accurate as the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_6 . This error might be due to the fact that the stress continuity across each layer interface is not imposed in the present theory. As in the case of the Classical Plate Theory (CPT), the transverse shear stresses can also be determined by integrating equilibrium equations (of

three-dimensional elasticity in the absence of body forces) with respect to the thickness coordinate:

$$\sigma_5 = - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_{x,x} + \sigma_{xy,y}) dz$$

$$\sigma_4 = - \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_{y,y} + \sigma_{xy,x}) dz$$

The foregoing approach not only gives single-value shear stresses at the interfaces but yields excellent results in comparison with the three-dimensional solutions. Typical stress distributions of $\sigma_5 = \sigma_{xz}$ and $\sigma_4 = \sigma_{yz}$ through the thickness ($a/h=10$) are shown in Fig.2. It is also shown that the shear stresses obtained by the present theory is more accurate than those obtained using the higher-order shear deformation plate theory when the ratio a/h is equal to 4. According to Whitney and Pagano⁽¹²⁾, the severity of shear deformation effects also depends on the material anisotropy of the layers. The exact maximum deflections of simply supported four-layer(0/90/90/0) cross-ply laminates are compared in Fig.3 for various ratios of moduli, E_1/E_2 (for a given thickness, $a/h=10$). The CPT underpredicts the deflections even at lower ratios of moduli.

CONCLUSIONS

An improved higher-order shear deformation theory that gives parabolic variation of the transverse shear strains and the transverse deflections is presented. It still can satisfy the zero tangential traction boundary conditions on the surfaces of the plate. Exact closed-form solutions of symmetric cross-ply laminates are obtained. From the results in Table 1-2 one can calculate that the present theory, in general, gives more accurate results than the first-order shear deformation theory when compared to the three-dimensional elasticity solution. It can also be shown that the results obtained by the present theory are better than those obtained using the higher-order shear deformation plate theory when the ratio a/h is less than 10. The present theory gives, relatively speaking, faster convergent solution when compared to the FSDT results, as can be seen from Table 3. The results for uniform loading should serve as reference for finite-element analyses.

The results reported herein were obtained during an investigation supported by the National Science Foundation of China. The support is gratefully acknowledged.

A NEW HIGHER-ORDER THEORY TO LAMINATED PLATES AND SHELLS

Zeng Jia-Xiong, Fan Ye-Li
Department of Mechanics Engineering, South
China University of Science and Technology, China

We shall present a new higher-order theory to laminated plates and shells in the paper. We suggest the assumed displacement field in a laminated plate be :

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_0 + z\psi_x(x,y) + z^2\varphi_x(x,y) + z^3\xi_x(x,y) + z^4\eta_x(x,y) \\ v &= v_0 + z\psi_y(x,y) + z^2\varphi_y(x,y) + z^3\xi_y(x,y) + z^4\eta_y(x,y) \\ w &= w_0(x,y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and the assumed displacement field of a thin laminated shell be.

$$\begin{aligned} u(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_1}\right) u_0 + \zeta\psi_1 + \zeta^2\varphi_1 + \xi^3\vartheta_1 + \xi^4\eta_1 \\ v(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_2}\right) v_0 + \zeta\psi_2 + \zeta^2\varphi_2 + \xi^3\vartheta_2 + \xi^4\eta_2 \\ w(\xi_1, \xi_2, \zeta) &= w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, in a shell of orthotropic laminas, refer to the condition that the shears on the surfaces vanish, We can infer the displacement field as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_1}\right) u_0 + \zeta\psi_1 + \zeta\varphi_1 - \frac{4}{3h^2}\zeta^3\left(\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{\alpha_1}\frac{\partial\omega}{\partial\xi}\right) - \frac{2}{h^2}\zeta^4\varphi_1 \\ v &= \left(1 + \frac{\zeta}{R_2}\right) v_0 + \zeta\psi_2 + \zeta\varphi_2 - \frac{4}{3h^2}\zeta^3\left(\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{\alpha_2}\frac{\partial\omega}{\partial\xi_2}\right) - \frac{2}{h^2}\zeta^4\varphi_2 \\ w &= w_0(\xi_1, \xi_2) \end{aligned}$$

We can deduce the equilibrium equations of a shell by the principle of virtual displacement. If we substitute the constitutive relations into the preceding equations, we can acquire the equilibrium equations expressed by displacement functions. In order to examine the accuracy of the theory this paper offers, symmetric and antisymmetric cross-ply laminated plates, cylindrical bending and bending to spherical shells are also studied, respectively. From the numerical results we come to the conclusions as follows:

1. The examples above about plates and shells display that the higher-order theory offered in this paper possesses high accuracy. It can be seen from the results that with this both deflection and in-plane stress are more exact than with first-order shear theory.

2. The authors have also calculated cylindrical bending of plates. The results is much closed to that form pagano's theory and indicates this theory is in good agreement with the exact theory.

3. This thory wants less unknowns than LCW theory and is conrenient in application. The computation can be carrjed out by small computers.

BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF UNSYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY RECTANGULAR PLATES

Wu Daihua Wang Jihui
(Wuhan University of Technology, Wuhan, China)

BUCKLING OF UNSYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY PLATE WITH VARIOUS EDGD CONDITIONS

Consider an unsymmetric angle-ply rectangular plate under uniform compressive in the x -direction as shown in Figure 1. The differential equations governing the buckling behavior of the plate can be expressed as

$$L_i(\delta u, \delta v, \delta w) = 0 \quad (i=1,2,3) \quad (1)$$

We chose to solve the problem that the plate is simple supported edge along the loaded edges and arbitrary boundary conditions along the other edges. The variations of buckling deformations are assumed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta u &= \sum_{i=0}^N a_i \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} u_i(y) & \delta v &= \sum_{i=0}^N b_i \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} v_i(y) \\ \delta w &= \sum_{i=0}^N c_i \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} w_i(y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

in which $u_i(y)$, $v_i(y)$ and $w_i(y)$ are liner combinations of equidistant point quintic B spline function $\phi_s(y/h-i)$.

Substituting the expression (2) into equations (1) yields internal residual

$$R_{Ii} = \bar{L}_i [(\{u_j(y)\})^T, (\{v_j(y)\})^T, (\{w_j(y)\})^T] \cdot (\{a_j\}, \{b_j\}, \{c_j\}) \cdot S_j(x) \quad (3)$$

$(i = 1, 2, 3)$

Selecting the weighted function as follow

$$W_{Ii} = h_i(x) \delta(y-y_j) \quad i=1,2,3 \quad j=0,1,2, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

then

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b R_{Ii} W_{Ii} dx dy = 0 \quad (5)$$

After a series of complicated calculations, we obtain the following standard eigenvalue equation by Caussion elimination method.

$$|A - \lambda I|_{n \times n} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Solving the equation (6), the buckling load is obtained.

ANALYSES AND DISCUSSIONS

Numerical calculations were made for unsymmetric angle-ply square plates; the materials considered are graphite/epoxy. The Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio for that are, respectively $E1/E2=40$, $G12/E2=0.5$, $\nu12=0.25$. For convenience to illus-

trate, we only list the results of the calculations and analyses of three type boundary condition laminates.

- (1) Simply supported boundary condition along four edges (denoted by A).
- (2) Simply supported boundary conditions along the loaded edges, clamped supportde along the other edges (denoted by B).
- (3) Simply supported along the loaded edges, the other edges one is simply supported, one clamped (denoted by C).

Figure 2 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon the buckling load $K = \bar{N}c^2/E_2t^3$ of unsymmetric four layer square plates in different edge boundary conditions. The buckling load is a function of ply angles. As the ply angles increase to a proper value, the buckling load attains a maximum. Its value is 57.67% larger than that of at $\theta=0$. But the coupling stiffnesses increase in the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$ as shown in Figure 3, the coupling stiffnesses are the factors of decreasing the buckling load. Studying the reason of generating the phenomenon is very useful and interesting.

The buckling load of four layer equal ply thickness simply supported laminated plate is expressed as

$$\bar{N}_x = \left(\frac{a}{m\pi}\right)^2 (T_{33} + \frac{2T_{12}T_{23}T_{13} - T_{22}T_{13}^2 - T_{11}T_{23}^2}{T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2}) \quad K = \bar{N}_x b^2/E_2t^3 \quad K = K_1 + K_2$$

$$K_1 = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{T_{33}}{E_2t^3} \quad K_2 = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{2T_{12}T_{23}T_{13} - T_{22}T_{13}^2 - T_{11}T_{23}^2}{E_2t^3(T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2)} \quad (7)$$

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon K , K_1 and K_2 . The variety of K_1 is the most significant in this Figure, it is the main factor which has influence on K . The variety of K_1 is less, and K_2 is negative value (influenced by the coupling effect) and has negative influence on K . The K and K_1 attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$ in the same time.

$$K_1 = K_{s1} + K_{s2}$$

$$K_{s1} = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{E_2t^3} [D_{11}\left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^4 + D_{22}\left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^4] \quad (8)$$

$$K_{s2} = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{E_2t^3} [2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^2\left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^2]$$

Figure 5 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon K_1 , K_{s1} . When ply angles vary the variation of the value of K_{s1} is small. But its slope suddenly varies which leads to K_1 's slope change. The change of K_{s2} value is the largest in this Figure. The K_1 and K_{s2} attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$. We have come to the conclusion that D_{12} and D_{66} are the key factors increasing the buckling load.

The bending stiffnesses D_{12} and D_{66} are ascending in the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$ as shown in Figure 6. The reason that D_{12} and D_{66} increase with ply angle is the effect of stiffnesses coefficients \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} on that, which are monotonic ascension in this region and attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$.

Figure 7 illustrates the effect of ply thickness t_1 upon the buckling load of unsymmetric four layer simply supported laminated square plate. Selecting the proper ply thicknesses can make the buckling load increases. The reason that the variations of ply thicknesses lead to the coupling stiffnesses decreasing rapidly. When the ply thickness varies to a certain fixed value, the coupling stiffnesses will vanish. The strict theoretical proof is omitted from this paper.

The buckling load of unsymmetric four-layer simply supported edges laminated plates by selecting proper ply thicknesses compared with that of equal ply thicknesses in shown as Figure 8.

The numerical results of the maximum values of the buckling load in the three boundary conditions is shown in table 1.

CONCLUSION

(1). The boundary effect seriously influences upon the value of the buckling load. The buckling load in B type boundary condition is the largest in the three boundary conditions. The buckling load is 58% larger than that of in A type boundary condition. So to change the supported conditions is a important way to increase the critical load.

(2) Selecting proper ply thickness, the coupling stiffnesses vanish and the buckling load will increase.

(3) The main reason that the buckling load increases with ply angles increase is the effect of \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} . In the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$, the stiffness coefficients \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} are monotonic increasing, so \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} are very important factors to increase the buckling load.

Table 1. Maximum value of the buckling loads in the three boundary conditions for unsymmetric laminated square plates

$$K = \bar{N}_x b^2 / E_2 t^3 \quad a/b=1 \quad \text{number of half-wave } m=1$$

LN	BC	ply angle (degree)						ply thickness (mm)			K'	K''	K''/K'
		θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_5	θ_6	t1	t2	t3			
IV	A	45.00	45.00	45.00	45.00			.1486	.3594		35.838	67.623	1.89
	B	40.58	40.58	40.58	40.58			.1490	.3590		39.914	107.73	1.67
	C	47.65	47.65	47.65	47.65			.1488	.3592		37.378	89.994	1.41
VI	A	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	.1413	.3082	.1325	35.838	67.618	1.89
	B	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	.1415	.3126	.3079	39.914	108.93	1.73
	C	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	.1424	.3100	.3096	37.378	90.207	1.41

In this table K' is the buckling load when ply angles are equal to zero and equal thickness layers; K'' is the absolute maximum value of the buckling load. LN is the number of the layer; BC is the boundary condition.

Fig. 1 Laminated plates with orthotropic layers.

Fig. 2 \$K\$ versus \$\theta\$.

Fig. 3. \$B_{ij}\$ versus \$\theta\$.

Fig. 4 Effect of \$\theta\$ on \$K, K_1\$, and \$K_2\$.

Fig. 5 Effect of \$\theta\$ on \$K_1, K_{s1}\$ and \$K_{s2}\$.

Fig. 6 \$D_{ij}\$ versus \$\theta\$.

Fig. 7 Relation between \$K\$ and \$t_1\$.

Fig. 8 Relation between \$K\$ and \$\theta\$.

BUCKLING OF AN ELLIPTIC SUBLAMINATE

Huyan Xiaozhi and Liu Fanglong
Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics

The buckling of a elliptic sublaminates located near one surface of laminate was studied in this paper. As shown in Figure 1, the set of intact laminate delamination from a laminate is referred to as the "sublaminates" and the remaining laminate as "base laminate". A strain ϵ is loaded to the laminate in the X-direction. The associated strains in the Y-direction and shear strain are $-\nu_{12}\epsilon$ and $\nu_{16}\epsilon$ respectively. Suppose h to be small compared to the base laminate thickness and Semiaxes a and b . Hence, thin plate linear buckling theory is valid to sublaminates and the inplane strains around the sublaminates boundary can be calculated from the laminate inplane deformation.

Firstly, the Strains of laminate in the xyz coordinate is obtained by using the translation of strains^[4]

$$\{\epsilon_x, \epsilon_y, \nu_{xy}\}^T = [1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{16}]^T T^T \epsilon \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. Model for a buckled Sublaminates

Here, T is the translation Matrix. Then, the inplane forces are

$$[N_x \ N_y \ N_{xy}]^T = \{\epsilon_x \ \epsilon_y \ \nu_{xy}\}^T [A] = [n_x \ n_y \ n_{xy}]^T [A] \epsilon \quad (2)$$

in which, A is inplane stiffness matrix of sublaminates and

$$[n_x \ n_y \ n_{xy}]^T = [1 - \nu_{12} \ \nu_{16}]^T T^T [A] \quad (3)$$

The buckling shape of the sublaminates is shown in Figure 1 (b) and the deflection w is measured from the sublaminates mid-plane, Along the Sublaminates boundary, the transverse displacements and slopes are zero. Now, the buckling initiation problem is reduced to that of an idealized elliptic sublaminates subjected to a set of inplane forces as shown in Figure 1 (c).

Assume the deflection of sublaminates in the z -direction as a function of the coordinates x and y

$$w = [1 - (\frac{x}{a})^2 - (\frac{y}{b})^2] \{C_0 + C_1 x^2 + C_2 y^2 + C_3 xy\} \quad (4)$$

The principal of minimum potential energy

$$\delta \pi = \delta (U - W) = 0 \quad (5)$$

is applied to obtain a system of simultaneous equations for the constants

$$\{C\}^T = \{C_0 \ C_1 \ C_2 \ C_3\}$$

$$\{[K] - \epsilon [K_g]\} \{C\} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Here, U is strain energy of sublaminates and W is the work done by the midplane stresses. The stiffness matrix K is

$$[K] = D_{11}[K_1] + D_{22}[K_2] + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})[K_3] + 2D_{16}[K_4] + 2D_{26}[K_5] \quad (7)$$

and K_g , is the geometric stiffness matrix

$$[K_g] = n_x [K_{g1}] + n_y [K_{g2}] + n_{xy} [K_{g3}] \quad (8)$$

Compared with reference [1], a term $C_3 xy$ is added in deflection w which reflects the bending-torsion effect of the sublaminates during bending. There are matrices K_{16} and K_{26} in stiffness matrix (7) corresponding the constants D_{16} and D_{26} respectively. There is matrix K_{g12} in geometric stiffness matrix (8) which corresponds N_{xy} . The contribution of the shear-extension coupling constants A_{16} and A_{26} to work W are made to reflect. Therefore, the method used in this paper is better than that in reference [1] and can be used for any symmetric sublaminates.

Buckling Strain of a surface sublaminates in a composite laminate is dependent on the sublaminates thickness h , the Semi-axes a and b , the base laminate Poisson's ratios ν_{12} and ν_{16} , the sublaminates angle θ , and fiber angle of each lamina α . That $E_1 = 131.0 \text{ GPa}$, $E_t = 13.0 \text{ GPa}$, $G = 6.4 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_{et} = 0.34$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{16} = 0$, $h = 0.51 \text{ mm}$ was taken as same as that in reference [1], From the result of calculation, it is concluded that:

1. The method used in this paper fits to calculate the critical strains of all symmetric elliptic sublaminates delaminates from a base laminate.
2. The buckling strains of unidirectional sublaminates reduce when the parameter $\lambda = b/a$ increase.
3. The critical strains of unidirectional sublaminates raise when the fiber angle α increases. The change is complex and affected by the parameter λ .
4. The change of the buckling strains with the parameter λ is not affected by the base laminate Poisson's ratio ν_{16} . The critical strains raise as the base laminate Poisson's ratio ν increases and the slopes of their increasing raise for increasing

the fiber angle α of unidirectional sublaminate.

REFERENCES

1. K.N.Shirakumar, J.D.Whitcomb, "Buckling of a Sublaminate in a Quasi-isotropic Composite Laminate", J.C.M., Vol, 19, No. 1, pp2-18, Jan. 1985.
2. Huan Xiaozhi, "One-Dimensional Model of Buckling of Delaminated Laminates", ACTA AERONAUTICA ET ASTRONAUTICA SINICA (Journal of Aeronautics and Astronautics), Vol. 9, No. 3, pp171-176, March 1988.
3. Huan Xiaozhi, Liu Fanglong, "Buckling of a Circular Sublaminate in a Composite Laminate", ACTA MATERIAE COMPOSITAE SINICA (Journal of Composite Materials), Vol. 6, No.4, Dec.1989

LAMINATE DESIGN BY OPTIMIZED PLY-GROUP MAP

Ippei Susuki
 Fatigue Branch, Airframe Division
 Japan National Aerospace Laboratory
 7-44-1 Jindaiji Higashi-machi, Chofu, Tokyo 182, Japan

ABSTRACT

A design method to make the most of multidirectional fiber-reinforced composite plates is proposed in this report. Laminates are assumed to be symmetric about the mid-plane surface and consist of plies with 0, 90, 45 and -45 degree fiber orientations. To normalize in-plane stresses and to express all of them in the closed stress space, a simple transformation is introduced. The prepared computer program finds optimal combination of ply thickness ratio to have the maximum strength for a given set of stresses under the constraint of using a maximum of above four ply angles.

The optimized ply groups are figured for the whole closed stress space by scanning stress conditions. The stress space is divided into areas according to ply groups which can obtain the maximum strength in each area. Given external stress condition, preferable ply groups will be found easily by utilizing this territorial map.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates have the advantage that their mechanical properties can be tailored through fiber orientations, ply thickness ratios, and stacking sequences.

This capability gives a designer an additional degree of flexibility to obtain the desired strength or stiffness. In other words, we need an additional design tool to make the most of composites because of the increase of design parameters.

- S_1, S_2, S_6 : LAMINATE STRESSES (SHOWN ARE POSITIVE)
- ϕ_k : PLY ANGLE OF k-TH PLY GROUP
- $v(\phi_k)$: PLY THICKNESS RATIO OF k-TH PLY GROUP
- H : ONE-HALF OF THE TOTAL THICKNESS
- h_k : ONE-HALF OF k-TH PLY GROUP THICKNESS

Fig.1 Coordinate System and Notation of Multidirectional Laminate

CODE	T	C	S
NAME	TENSION DOMINATED REGION	COMPRESSION DOMINATED REGION	SHEAR DOMINATED REGION
RE-GION			
S_1	1	-1	$-1 \leq S_1 \leq 1$
S_2	$-1 \leq S_2 \leq 1$	$-1 \leq S_2 \leq 1$	$-1 \leq S_2 \leq 1$
S_6	$0 \leq S_6 \leq 1$	$0 \leq S_6 \leq 1$	1

S_1, S_2, S_6 [MPa]

Fig.2 Representation of Normalized In Plane Stresses by T, C, and S Regions

Fig. 3 Schematic Expression of Constraint on $[0p/90q/45r/-45s]$ Symmetric Laminate

NO	SUBREGION	PLY THICKNESS RATIO				LAMINATE	
		$v(0)$	$v(90)$	$v(45)$	$v(-45)$		
		p	g	r	s		
0	VERTEX	A	1	0	0	0	$[0]$
1		B	0	1	0	0	$[90]$
2		C	0	0	1	0	$[45]$
3		O	0	0	0	1	$[-45]$
4	EDGE	AB	$1-x$	x	0	0	$[0p/90q]$
5		AC	$1-x$	0	x	0	$[0p/45r]$
6		OA	$1-x$	0	0	x	$[0p/-45s]$
7		BC	0	$1-x$	x	0	$[90q/45r]$
8		OB	0	$1-x$	0	x	$[90q/-45s]$
9	SURFACE	OC	0	0	$1-x$	x	$[45r/-45s]$
10		OBC	0	$1-x-y$	x	y	$[90q/45r/-45s]$
11		OPC	$1-x-y$	0	x	y	$[0p/45r/-45s]$
12	SURFACE	OAB	$1-x-y$	x	0	y	$[0p/90q/-45s]$
13		ABC	$1-x-y$	x	y	0	$[0p/90q/45r]$
14	BODY	O-ABC	$1-x-y-z$	x	y	z	$[0p/90q/45r/-45s]$

$0 < x, y, z < 1$

Fig. 4 Subregion in Tetrahedron Constraint

Fig. 5 Territorial map of optimized ply-groups for Graphite/Epoxy(T300/N5208) Laminate

Fig. 6 Territorial map of optimized ply-groups for Graphite/PEEK(APC2) Laminate

In this work, we concentrate on laminates which consist of plies with 0, 90, 45, and -45 degree fiber orientations.

We will use the classical laminated plate theory in analyzing the stress and strain in each ply (1). The laminate strength is determined by the first ply failure envelope and evaluated by the strength ratio R (1). We use the quadratic failure criterion to estimate the strength of each ply (1).

Strength characteristics of laminates were taken into considerations in the optimization process (2). Optimized ply group maps were obtained for graphite/epoxy (T300/N5208) and graphite/PEEK(APC2) materials.

2. REPRESENTATION OF NORMALIZED STRESS SPACE

As shown in Fig. 1, a normalized set of stresses (S_1, S_2, S_6) are used in this report. These are laminate stress components represented in the laminate 1-2 coordinate system. The 1-axis is assumed to coincide with fiber direction of 0-degree plies. One of these (S_1, S_2, S_6) stress components should have a unit value.

Denote by $(\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \sigma_6)$ the actual laminate stresses. The normalized (S_1, S_2, S_6) are the values divided by normalization factor S_0 ,

$$S_0 = \max(|\sigma_1|, |\sigma_2|, |\sigma_6|) \quad (1)$$

$$(S_1, S_2, S_6) = (\sigma_1/S_0, \sigma_2/S_0, \sigma_6/S_0) \quad (2)$$

Any normalized set of stresses will be expressed as corresponding points within the one of the shaded stress spaces defined T, C or S region in Fig. 2.

3. PROCESS OF STRENGTH OPTIMIZATION

A computer program was developed to find the optimal combination of ply groups with their best ply thickness ratios. Let p, q, r and s in the symmetric laminate $\{0p/90q/45r/-45s\}$ denote ply thickness ratios of 0, 90, 45 and -45 degree respectively. The optimization goal is, given (S_1, S_2, S_6), to reach the best combination of p, q, r and s under the constraint of $p+q+r+s=1$, or to find the best position (p,q,r) in a tetrahedron illustrated in Fig. 3. In order to obtain better results, we took into consideration the strength discontinuities of multidirectional laminates (2). As we assume that all discontinuities may exist only on the boundary surfaces of this tetrahedron, a direct search optimization was carried out for each 15 sub-region (Fig. 4) first. Then optimum ply thickness ratio for whole tetrahedron region was determined by choosing the best one among 15 regions which gives the global maximum R value.

4. PLY-GROUP MAP FOR T300/N5208 AND Gr/PEEK(APC2)

Numerical studies have been performed for graphite/epoxy (T300/N5208) and graphite/PEEK(APC2) laminates in tension dominated region (T-region). The maps of optimized ply-groups for these materials are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. Given a set of external stresses, we can easily find a preferable ply groups to be used designing laminate. Both maps show that tri-directional laminates $\{0p/45r/-45s\}$ will be better than $\{0p/90q\}$ laminates in tension-tension with no or relatively small shear stress conditions. Numerical results also indicate that there is no territorial area for quadri-directional $\{0p/90q/45r/-45s\}$ laminates. If external load is limited to a single loading case, we can design the optimal laminate by maximim three directions for any in-plane combined stresses.

REFERENCES

1. S. W. Tsai, "Composites Design", Think Composites, 1988
2. I. Susuki, 30th National SAMPE Symposium, p 1179, March, 1985

Fig. 1 Coordinate System and Notation
of Multidirectional Laminate

Fig. 2 Representation of
Normalized In-Plane Stresses
by T, C, and S Regions

Fig. 3 Schematic Expression of
Constraint on $[0_p/90_q/45_r/-45_s]$ Fig. 4 Subregion in Tetrahedron Constraint
Symmetric Laminate

Fig. 5 Territorial map of optimized ply-groups
for Graphite/Epoxy(T300/N5208) Laminate

Fig. 6 Territorial map of optimized ply-groups
for Graphite/PEEK(APC2) Laminate

ON OPTIMUM ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED PLATES UNDER SHEAR*

Tang Jun
(Dalian University of Technology, Dalian, China)

Let us consider the optimization problem of bidirection reinforced laminated plates under shear as the same problem in Ref.1. It is assumed that, the laminate is composed of N layers and each layer of the plate has the same thickness h and an equal number of the same fiber in the θ_k and $-\theta_k$ direction with respect to the x axis (subscript k shows the k-th layer). Taking $R=a/b$ which represents the length-to-width ratio of plate. For the plate of simply supported edges S_2 , the deflections is assumed as

$$\begin{aligned} U &= \sum \sum U_{mn} \cos(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \\ V &= \sum \sum V_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \cos(n\pi y/b) \quad (m=1,2,\dots, m_1, n=1,2,\dots, n_1) \\ W &= \sum \sum W_{mn} \sin(m\pi x/a) \sin(n\pi y/b) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

the buckling differential equations of laminated plates under shear with the Galerken method can be written as following

$$\begin{aligned} [T_{33} - T_C] W_{pq} - \lambda \sum_m \sum_n \frac{mnpq}{(m^2-p^2)(n^2-q^2)} W_{mn} &= 0 \\ (p=1,2,\dots,m_1 \text{ and } q=1,2,\dots,n_1) & (m+p \text{ and } n+q \text{ are odd}) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where p and q are the number of half waves in the x and y directions, respectively, and

$$\lambda = \frac{32abR^2}{\pi^4} N_{xy} \quad (3)$$

$$T_C = \frac{T_{11}T_{23}^2 + T_{22}T_{13}^2 - 2T_{12}T_{13}T_{23}}{T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2} \quad (4)$$

$$T_{11} = A_{11}p^2 + A_{66}q^2R^2, \quad T_{22} = A_{66}p^2 + A_{22}q^2R^2, \quad T_{12} = (A_{12} + A_{66})pqR,$$

$$T_{13} = B_{11}p^3 + (B_{12} + 2B_{66})pq^2R^2, \quad T_{23} = (B_{12} + 2B_{66})p^2qR + B_{22}q^3R^3 \quad (5)$$

$$T_{33} = D_{11}p^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})p^2q^2R^2 + D_{22}q^4R^4$$

where the A_{ij} , B_{ij} and D_{ij} are extensional, coupling and bending stiffnesses of laminate, respectively.

Taking the N angles of all layers as design variables and the λ as the object function to find the maximum value of the λ , This is an unconstrained optimum problem and was used in Refs.1,2. However, it will be proved that, this problem can be simplified.

The equations (2) can be rewritten using matrix notation

$$[K-C] \{W\} - \lambda [G] \{W\} = 0 \quad (6)$$

in which, the elements of $[G]$ and diagonal matrices $[K]$, $[C]$ are:

$$K_{ii} = T_{33}, \quad C_{ii} = T_C, \quad G_{ii} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$G_{il} = \frac{mnpq}{(m^2 - p^2)(n^2 - q^2)} \quad (\text{when } m+p \text{ and } n+q \text{ are odd}) \quad (8)$$

$$G_{il} = 0 \quad (\text{when } m+p \text{ or } n+q \text{ is even})$$

the minimum eigenvalue of equation (6) is given by Rayleigh Quotient

$$\lambda_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [K+C] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad (9)$$

let

$$\beta_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [K] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad \mu_1 = \min \frac{\{W\}^T [C] \{W\}}{\{W\}^T [G] \{W\}} \quad (10)$$

In Ref.3, it was proved that, both the T_{33} and T_C must be positive, i.e. the $[K]$ and $[C]$ all are positive definite matrices. For the generalized eigenvalue problem, as for normal eigenvalue problem⁶, we can prove that

$$\beta_1 \geq \mu_1 + \lambda_1 \quad (11)$$

thus

$$\beta_1 \geq \lambda_1 \quad (12)$$

It represents that, the effect of coupling stiffness, i.e. the effect of $[C]$ must reduce the shear buckling load of laminate. In addition, in Ref.3, it has been proved that, for any nonsymmetric laminate must have a corresponding symmetric laminate making that, the both nonsymmetric and symmetric laminates have the same T_{33} , i.e. have the same β_1 in expression (11). Because of the T_C is zero for symmetric laminate, so we can conclude that, for any nonsymmetric laminate under shear, there must have a symmetric laminate which has higher buckling load than that nonsymmetric laminate, i.e. the optimum laminate with maximum value of buckling load must be a symmetric one.

For symmetric laminate, the expression (6) can be simplified as

$$[K] \{W\} - \lambda [G] \{W\} = 0 \quad (13)$$

Taking the derivative of Eq. (13) with respect to θ_k and, for finding the extremum of λ , let the derivative equal to zero, we obtain

$$\{W\}^T \frac{\partial [K]}{\partial \theta_k} \{W\} = 0 \quad (k=1, 2, \dots, N/2) \quad (14)$$

From Eq. (14), the optimum ply angles can be gotten. let

$$J = U_2(p^4 - q^4 R^4), \quad F = U_3(6p^2 q^2 R^2 - p^4 - q^4 R^4) \quad (15)$$

in which, the U_2, U_3 are invariances of stiffness. The derivative of T with respect to θ_k , i.e. the elements of diagonal matrix $(\partial[K])/(\partial\theta_k)$ are

$$\frac{\partial T_{33}}{\partial \theta_k} = \frac{4}{3}(Z_k^3 - Z_{k-1}^3) \sin 2\theta_k (4F \cos 2\theta_k - J) \quad (16)$$

Substituting the Eq.(16) into Eq.(14), it can be seen, there are $N/2$ Eqs. and which have the same form and contain only one unknown variable θ_k in each equation, so we can get the same values of θ_k from these equations. It is easy to know, the roots of Eq.(14) can not more than three, containing the 0° and 90° .

For example, Taking the laminate same as that in Ref.1 the number of layers $N=6$, and the $m_1=n_1=4$, the objective function $\phi=10^5/\lambda$. Because of the laminated plate, which have the optimum ply orientation under shear load, must be symmetrical, so we can only use the symmetric laminate for optimum analysis. The numerical results of calculation are given in Tab.1, The Powell method are used for optimization. The results quoted from Ref.2 are given in Tab.3. The results in Tab.1 are quite agree with the results in Tab.3. but it is only analysis for symmetric laminate, so not only the equations of calculation can be simplified, but also the number of design variable can be reduced to one half. It has proved that, as mentioned before, for any number of laminae in an laminated plate, the number of different optimum ply angles no more than three, including 0° and 90° , and the another angle, between 0° and 90° , must be equal each other. It can be seen, the values of optimum ply angle of each lamina in Tab. 1 or Tab.3 are very close each other and that values increase with the R . if the R of two plates are reciprocal each other, the optimum ply angles of the two plates are complement each other. Thus, we can let the ply angles of each layer be all equal each other, i.e. the optimization analysis as mentioned before can be simplified as an analysis of single design variable. Calculating the same example, as mentioned before, with the single design variable. The result of calculation are given in Tab.2. It can be seen, they are all agree with those in Tab.1.

Table 1 Optimum Fiber Direction (Deg.)

R	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	ϕ
0.5	32.67	32.98	32.77	2.826
0.8	40.13	40.13	40.13	1.477
1.0	45	45	44.95	0.980
1.5	54.26	54.26	54.27	0.387
2.0	57.35	57.08	57	0.177
4.0	80.64	80.5	81.21	0.021
5.0	90	89.87	89.81	0.009

Table 2

R	θ	ϕ
0.5	32.76	2.826
0.8	40.11	1.477
1.0	45.03	0.980
1.5	54.24	0.387
2.0	57.25	0.177
4.0	80.53	0.0205
5.0	89.97	0.0087

Table 3 Optimum Fiber Direction for Laminated Plates (Deg.)

R	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_5	θ_6	ϕ
0.5	32	33	33.6	33.6	33	32	2.8
0.8	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	40.1	1.495
1.0	45	45	45	45	45	45	0.992
1.5	54	54.6	54.6	54.1	54	54	0.307
2.0	58.6	59.7	60.4	60.4	59.7	58.6	0.177

As already discussed, we obtain.

1. The optimum structure of laminated plates under shear for buckling load must be symmetric laminate, the number of different optimum ply angles, including 0° and 90° , is no more than three.
2. The optimization analysis, mentioned before, can be simplified to single variable optimization.
3. As the length-to-width ratio R of plate increases, both the optimum ply angle and the buckling load increase.
4. If exchange the length a and width b , i.e. the length-to-width ratio of two plates

are reciprocal each other, the optimum ply angles of the two plate are complement and the buckling loads are equal each other.

REFERENCES

1. Y.Hirano, J.Composite Materials, 13, (1979), 329-334.
2. Jiang Yongqiu, Computational Structural Mechanics and Applications, 1(1), 1984, 39-46, (in Chinese).
3. Tang Jun, Computational Structural Mechanics and Applications, 1(2), 1984, 75-84. (in Chinese).
4. Tang Jun, Acta Mechanica Sinica, 19, 1987, Supplementary Issue, 268-272.
5. Jones, R.M., Mechanics of Composite Materials, McGRAW-HILL Book Company, 1975.
6. Chao Zhihao, Zhang Yude, Li Ruixia, Calculation of Matrix and Equation Roots, (in Chinese). Education Publication House, 1984.

The Viscoelastic Properties of Composites under Dynamic Load

Du Lingxuan Li Jianxin
Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials

ABSTRACT

The viscoelastic properties of carbon fiber / epoxy composites under dynamic load were investigated in the present work. The storage modulus E' and the loss factor $\text{tg}\delta$ of the T300 / 648 laminate of typical configuration cutting in 0° direction were measured. The temperature spectra $E'--T$ and $\text{tg}\delta--T$ at different frequencies and the frequency spectra $E'--f$ and $\text{tg}\delta--f$ at different temperatures were obtained. The influence of frequency on the glass transition temperature T_g and the influence of temperature on frequency spectra were studied. The relations between the viscoelastic properties of the composite and its practical performance of application were expounded. Considerations were taken in the design aspect.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber / epoxy composites as advanced structural materials are finding more applications, especially in the construction of aeroplane, such as being employed in fuselage, airfoil, rudder, the hub of helicopter. The loading modes are mainly periodically changed vibrating load. So the vibrating and damping properties of the components are important for the design of the structure. If each component has appropriate self-oscillation frequency, the disastrous resonance can be prevented. The dynamic stiffness K_a have to be calculated to design the self-oscillating frequency. The calculation can be done only if the storage moduli are obtained beforehand. Also the mechanical loss factors $\text{tg}\delta$ of the material have to be known to design the damping performance. So the dynamic storage moduli E' and the mechanical loss factors $\text{tg}\delta$ are the necessary parameters for the optimization of composite design. Moreover, from the temperature spectra of the dynamic parameters of the composite materials, the glass transition temperature T_g can be obtained. T_g is a critical parameter for the utilization of the material. There are many methods to determine the value of T_g , but only the value from the viscoelastic spectra determined by forced nonresonant method gives definite meaning. The tendency of the change of structural stability with the change of frequency can be predicted from the frequency spectra. It can help to determine the influence of frequency on the T_g of the material and the upper temperature limit for the utilization of the material to exploit the potential of the thermal durability of the material.

Many practical performances can be estimated and pre-designed from the study of the dynamic properties of the composite and can be realized by the choice of the material and structure. For example, the stiffness and the flexibility must be properly matched if we hope the material to have longer fatigue life and the oscillating and damping performances of the composite components to meet the demand of design. This can be realized by the adjustment of chemical components, the processing conditions and the configuration of the material. The storage modulus E' and the loss factor $\text{tg}\delta$ are effective index for the quality control of composites. The technical specification of composite of the french plane Dolphin has used the viscoelastic parameters as essential index for quality control.

EXPERIMENT

1. Instrument: Dynastat viscoelastic spectrometer.

1.1 Principle: Forced nonresonant oscillation method is employed. A sinusoidally changed load is applied to the specimens to force it vibrate. The amplitude of the stress and strain and the phase angle between them are measured to calculate the storage modulus E' and loss modulus E'' and loss factor $\text{tg} \delta$.

$$E' = E^* \cos \delta$$

$$E'' = E^* \sin \delta$$

where $\text{tg} \delta = E'' / E'$
 E' --- storage modulus

E'' ---loss modulus

E^* ---complex modulus

$\text{tg} \delta$ ---loss factor

δ ---phase angle

1.2 Loading mode: Three point bending.

1.3 Viberating mode: Forced flexural vibration with the amplitude fixed

1.4 Temperature rate: $2-5^{\circ}\text{C} / \text{min}$

2. specimens: It is made from T300 / 648. The configuration is $45/0_2/-45/0/-45/45/0/45_2/0/45$ s. The machining angle is 0° . Its size is 50 mm long and 10mm wide and the thickness is 2 mm.

3. Experimental method: The experiment was carried out according to Q / 6S 628-88. The temperature spectra $E''-T$ and $\text{tg} \delta -T$ are taken at constant frequency with the amplitude fixed. The frequency spectra $E''-f$ and $\text{tg} \delta -f$ are taken at constant temperature also with the amplitude of stress fixed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The storage moduli and the loss factors of T300 / 648 composite material with typical configuration at different temperatures or different frequencies were determined. They can be used in the design of the self-oscilating frequency and the damping performace of the component.

1. The temperature spectrum of the loss factor $\text{tg} \delta -T$ is shown in Fig.1. The temperature range is $20^{\circ}\text{C}---220^{\circ}\text{C}$. The frequency is 0.1 HZ. It can be seen in Fig. 1 that the peak temperature of the $\text{tg} \delta -T$ curve is 160°C . This is the glass transition temperature of the material. The upper temperature limit in this situation is 160°C . T_g is an important physical parameter for polymeric materials and also the important parameter for the design of carbon fiber / epoxy composite material.

The peak easily seen in the $\text{tg} \delta -T$ curves indicates that the degree of cure of the material is not too high. If the material is over cured, the peak will not appear. It can also be seen that the curve is not steep and the area under the curve is comparatively large, therefore, the material will dissipate more energy in the form of heat when it is under the viberating load.

2. The temperature spectra $E' - T$ and $\text{tg} \delta - T$ at different frequencies were determined and are shown in Fig.2, the frequencies being 0.1, 1, 10, 50 and 100 HZ.

It can be seen in Fig.2 that with the increase of frequency from 0.1 to 100 HZ, the $E' - T$ curve moves upward. That is, the storage modulus will increase with the increase of frequency. The tendency is in the same way as that for the frequency spectra

of storage modulus in Fig.3.

It can also be seen in Fig.2 that with the gradual increase of frequency from 0.1, 1, 10, 50 to 100 HZ, the glass transition temperature increases from 160°C to 180°C. This is very helpful for the effective application of the material. The material will have higher T_g when it is loaded dynamically compared with the static conditions. Its upper temperature limit for the utilization will increase as the frequency increases in the same way as the glass transition temperature.

3. The frequency spectra E'--f and tgδ -- f at 28°C, 100°C, 160°C and 220°C are shown in Fig.3.

It is the same for each E'-- f curve in Fig.3 that the storage modulus increases with the increase of frequency. It can be deduced that the dynamic stiffness K_a of the composite component will increase and higher structural stability will be achieved when the frequency is increased.

The comparison among the 4 curves in Fig.3 reveals that the E'-- f curves move downward with the increase of temperature. The decrease of storage modulus with the increase of temperature is the same as the change of storage modulus with the change of temperature in Fig.2.

It can be seen in the four tgδ -- f curves in Fig.3 that at 28°C, 100°C and 160°C the loss factor decrease with the increase of temperature while the curve at 220°C has a peak, the peak is in the range of 2--10 HZ. So the change of tgδ with frequency depend on the temperature and therefore in the design of the damping performance of the composite compartment, consideration in the temperature and frequency range involved in the practical application has to be taken in the proper selection of tgδ value.

CONCLUSION

1. The glass transition temperature of the T300 / 648 composite material of typical configuration at 0.1 HZ is 160°C, that is also the upper temperature limit for the practical application.
2. The T_g of the material changes with the change of vibrating frequency. It will increase 20--40°C when the frequency increases from 0.1 to 100 HZ. That is also the increase for the upper temperature limit for the practical application.
3. The toughness and the shock absorption ability of the material are satisfactory.
4. Higher dynamic stiffness and higher structural stability will be achieved when the material is employed in higher frequency conditions.

REFERENCES

1. Ward, I.M. " Mechanical properties of solid polymers "
2. ASTM D 4065-82
3. ASTM D 4092-83a
4. Takayaruki Marayama, " Dynamic Mechanical Analysis of Polymeric Materials"

Fig.1 The temperature spectrum at 0.1HZ

Fig.2 The temperature spectra at different HZs'

Fig.3 The frequency spectra $E' - f$ and $tg - f$

A CLIMATIC STABILITY OF FROST-RESISTANT POLYPROPYLENE

I.S. Philatov, P.E. Nikitin, A.I. Reutov

(Institute of Physical-Technical Problems of the North,
Yakut Branch, Siberian Division, USSR Academy of Sciences,
Yakutsk, USSR)

ABSTRACT

Studied is an aging of frost-resistant composites based on polypropylene in the cold climatic conditions by the change of strain curves under tension within the temperature range of 213-293 K. It is stated that except frost-resistance increase, a light stabilization of frost-resistant polypropylene must be considered. Estimated is a period of material retention for different temperatures. A growing interest to polypropylene is stipulated, on the one hand, by the favourable combination of mechanical, electrical and chemical characteristics with good processability of polymer and, on the other hand, by the availability of cheap monomer. Due to these factors, polypropylene occupies a stable position on the world market. The products made of polypropylene are subjected to aging under use in atmospheric conditions. Besides, brittle temperature of this material is approximately -10°C . An investigation of nonmodified and unstable polypropylene aging under cold climatic conditions has demonstrated its exceptional instability. It results in the development of frost-resistant compositions on the basis of polypropylene to be studied on the stability to the cold climate effect. The climatic stability of the materials based on polypropylene is estimated by the strain curves and the degree of a change of failing stress under tension and relative extension under cracking. Strain curves have been got by means of tension testing machine FP-10 at constant speed (50 mm/min) within the temperature range of 213-293 K. The investigations at low temperature are carried out in a isolated chamber. Liquid nitrogen is used as a cooling medium. The temperature inside the chamber is controlled with an accuracy of $\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Studied have been the specimens made of polypropylene of three frost-resistant grades. As an elastomeric filler, chosen is a mixture of polyisobutylene, siloxane rubber and ethylene-propylene copolymer. Channel furnace is used as a photo stabilizer. After first months of exposition the brightness of unstable frost-resistant compositions of polypropylene is getting worse. In six months a net of microcracks has been well seen on the specimens surface. It results in a sharp deterioration of physical-mechanical characteristics of the material (Fig. 1). A change of retention coefficient by strength $K_G = \sigma(t)/\sigma_0$ is more sufficient in the conditions of Yakutsk than of Tashkent. It can be explained by more intensive aging of polymer as a result of more short wavelength being 270 Hm (in Tashkent - 290 Hm) on the account of more transparent atmosphere (for Yakutsk is 0.86; for Tashkent is 0.76), air temperature gradient (40-50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) and air temperature transition over 0°C in spring /2/. The results obtained indicate that except an increase of frost-resistance of the compositions made on the basis of polypropylene, it is necessary to pay a parti-

Fig. 1. Dependence K_G on the period of aging:
1 - Tashkent; 2 - Yakutsk.

ular attention to the frost-resistant polypropylene photo stabilization. An ultraviolet irradiation causes a material destruction, appearance of free radical which are not always capable to recombine at low temperatures. The characteristics of light stable materials are not changed sharply. For this material calculated is the relative index of climatic stability on the basis of strain curves by the typical A parameter:

$$\mathcal{L}(t) = \frac{A(t) - A_K}{A_0 - A_K}, \quad (1)$$

where: A_0 , A_K , $A(t)$ are the baseline, limiting and running values of the parameter. It is shown that $\mathcal{L}(t)$ is possible to be approximated by the exponential dependence. For arbitrary chosen time t_1 , t_2 , t_3 got is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(t_2) &= \mathcal{L}(t_1) e^{-\kappa(t_2 - t_1)} \\ \mathcal{L}(t_3) &= \mathcal{L}(t_1) e^{-\kappa(t_3 - t_1)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Using this dependence, the speed constant is determined:

$$\kappa = \frac{1}{t_3 - t_2} \ln \frac{\mathcal{L}(t_2)}{\mathcal{L}(t_3)}. \quad (3)$$

A period of retention is estimated at critical value $\mathcal{L}_K = \mathcal{L}(t_{xp})$

$$t_{xp} = t_2 + (t_3 - t_2) \frac{\ln \frac{\mathcal{L}(t_2)}{\mathcal{L}_K}}{\ln \frac{\mathcal{L}(t_2)}{\mathcal{L}(t_3)}}. \quad (4)$$

The results of the retention period calculation of stabilized frost-resistant composition of polypropylene within the temperature range of 213-293 K for quasi-brittle failure are given in Fig. 2. It is clearly seen that frost-resistant stable polypropylene is the long-term material for the manufacture of the products to be used in the zone of cold climate.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence t_{xp} of frost-resistant polypropylene.

REFERENCES

1. Сибирякова Н.А. Морозостойкий полипропилен и его применение. Л.: ЛДНТП. 1976. - 120 с.
2. Филатов И.С. Климатическая устойчивость полимерных материалов. М.: Наука. 1983. - 214 с.

SQUEEZE CAST MAGNESIUM COMPOSITE MATERIALS

J. Schröder and K. U. Kainer
Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik, TU Clausthal,
Agricolastraße 6, D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld

Strengthening of light alloys with short fibres produces materials with an interesting range of properties. Such materials can be employed for highly stressed components in general engineering, aircraft and space, and automobile industry applications where weight saving is necessary.

Short fibre reinforced magnesium alloys possess much higher E-modulus, lower coefficient of thermal expansion and improved wear resistance in addition to an improvement in the mechanical properties at room and elevated temperature. Powder and liquid phase mixing of the fibres is possible as in infiltration of fibre preforms. The advantage of the preforms lie in its universal applicability as well as the possibility of graduated or partial component reinforcement. There are economic advantages due to simple procedures and low investment costs. In this work the structure, mechanical properties, wear resistance and thermal expansion of short fibre reinforced materials are presented and discussed. The influence of the matrix alloy on the properties is also presented. The preforms used were bonded Saffil fibre bondies with a fibre content of %.

POWDER METALLURGICAL PRODUCTION OF WHISKER REINFORCED
MAGNESIUM ALLOYS

K. U. Kainer, J. Schröder and B. L. Mordike
Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik, TU Clausthal
Agricolastr. 6, D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld

Many problems arise in the production of whisker reinforced magnesium matrix composites. One possible technique is based on powder metallurgy. Unlike the production of particle reinforced composites in which relative coarse particle sizes can be mixed mechanically whisker reinforced composites need techniques in which the whiskers are not damaged during mixing and subsequent consolidation. One method is to use mixed size powders which one fine sized component can be used to premix with the whiskers. Difficulties arise in the diffusion anneal to produce a homogeneous matrix alloy. Further problems are encountered in consolidation by deformation and due to pores forming by the Kirkendall effect. The influence of production on whisker damage and properties of the composite is discussed for various whisker materials. In particular the variation of the light alloy powder and the treatment influences markedly the properties of the composites. Selected examples are used to demonstrate the property profile as a function of volume fraction of whiskers. An increase in the E-modulus and decrease in the thermal expansion and improvement in strength properties at elevated temperatures is obtained.

MAGNESIUM PARTICLE COMPOSITES

J. Schröder, K. U. Kainer and B. L. Mordike
Institut für Werkstoffkunde und Werkstofftechnik, TU Clausthal,
Agricolastraße 6, D-3392 Clausthal-Zellerfeld

Magnesium alloys have assumed increased importance as construction material where weight and hence energy must be saved. The disadvantages of low strength, low elastic modulus, poor fatigue resistance and insufficient high temperature strength prevent their use in applications where stringent requirements must be met. Particle reinforcement can remove many of the disadvantages and enable alloys to meet many demands in aircraft, space and automobile applications. Additions of SiC, TiC, Al₂O₃ etc. improve elastic and mechanical properties at room and elevated temperatures. There is also an improvement in wear resistance and a beneficial reduction in thermal expansion. Suitable dispersing methods are available to ensure optimum distribution of particles. In this work the mechanical properties, the microstructure and technological properties of particle reinforced magnesium alloys are presented and discussed. The influence of particle content, type of particle and distribution on the properties is discussed.

ANALYSIS OF FREE VIBRATION OF A PEDESTRIAN GRP BRIDGE WITH SKEW CABLE STAYS

Gong Zhiyu, Feng Guangzhan, Wang Qingyuan
(Chengdu University of Science and Technology, China)

ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this paper is to present the work in analyzing free vibration and computing free vibration frequencies of the pedestrian GRP bridge with skew cable stays built in Chongqing Jiaotong Institute with analytical method and energy method. By both methods, the results are in a good approximation and have also been verified by field tests on the GRP bridge.

The main frame of the bridge is a box structure made of GRP boneycomb sandwich plates. The local free vibration frequencies of top plates and longitudinal webs of the box structure have also been calculated and the results are satisfactory.

1. Free vibration frequency of the main beam of a GRP bridge
- (1) Considering the main beam as an elastic foundation beam

Fig. 1

Reducing the tractive force of cable stays to vertical reactive force of distributed supports of the GRP bridge, which we consider to be an elastic foundation beam (Fig.1) with an elastic coefficient being

$$C = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n K_i}{l} \quad \text{where} \quad K_i = \frac{E A_s \sin^2 \alpha_i}{L_i} \quad (1)$$

Then the differential equation of the main beam in vibration becomes

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 y}{\partial x^4} = -m \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} - C^2 y \quad (2)$$

Resolving equation (2) and basing on constraint condition of the beam with joint supports on two ends, we find free vibration frequency of the main beam as below

$$\omega_1^2 = \frac{k^4 EI + C}{\bar{m}} = \frac{\alpha^2 \pi^4}{l^4} (j^4 + \beta) \quad (j=1,2,\dots) \quad \text{where } \alpha^2 = \frac{EI}{\bar{m}}, \quad \beta = \frac{Cl^4}{EI\pi^4} \quad (3)$$

(2) Calculation of free vibration frequency with energy method Based on the law of energy conservation, we have

$$W_{\max} = V_{\max} \quad (4)$$

Referring to Fig.2, we could find the maximum kinetic energy of the whole bridge system, i.e.

$$W_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \omega^2 \left[\int_0^l \bar{m} y^2(x) dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{m}_s \frac{y_i^2}{L_i^2} \int_0^{L_i} s^2 ds \right] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2

The potential energy of system consists of three parts, besides potential energy of main beam and cables, the work done by the secondary deformation of cables during periodic vibration must be considered, thus the total maximum potential energy is

$$V_{\max} = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_0^l EI \left(\frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^2 \sin^2 \alpha_i}{L_i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^3 \sin \alpha_i \cos^2 \alpha_i}{L_i^2} \right] \quad (6)$$

Putting equation (5) and (6) into equation (4), we get

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\int_0^l EI \left(\frac{d^2 y(x)}{dx^2} \right)^2 dx + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^2 \sin^2 \alpha_i}{L_i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{E A_s y_i^3 \sin \alpha_i \cos^2 \alpha_i}{L_i^2}}{\int_0^l \bar{m} y^2(x) dx + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^n \bar{m}_s y_i^2 L_i} \quad (7)$$

(3) Basic vibration frequency of calculation in comparison with test value Fig.3 shows the cross section of the main beam, depending on dimensions and densities of main beam and cables and applying equations (3) and (7), we obtain basic vibration frequencies $f = \omega/2\pi = 3.26\text{Hz}$ and $f = 3.3\text{Hz}$ respectively. Both values are approximate to the value $f = 3.15\text{Hz}$ of field test which is measured from the bridge in vibration with strain gauges. The comparison demonstrates that the reduced beam could bear a satisfactory basic vibration frequency.

Fig. 3

2. Free vibration of surface plates and longitudinal webs of the box beam of GRP bridge

The main beam of GRP bridge is a box structure which consists of surface plate and transverse and longitudinal webs being made of sandwich honeycomb plates (Fig.3). We analyze free vibration frequency of a surface plate confined by two transverse webs

and two longitudinal webs to be abstracted as a simple support rectangular plate (Fig.4) with an analytical method and a formula is derived as blow

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{m} \{ D [(\frac{m}{a})^4 + (\frac{n}{b})^4] + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) (\frac{mn}{ab})^2 \} \quad (8)$$

Fig. 4

which gives the basic vibration frequency $f = 67\text{Hz}$.

A longitudinal web is reduced to a rectangular plate with boundary condition shown as Fig.5, of which a formula to account free vibration frequency is derived with Reyleigh's method, it is

$$\omega^2 = \frac{\pi^4}{m} \{ D [\frac{1}{4} (\frac{1}{a})^4 + \frac{41}{64} (\frac{1}{b})^4] - \frac{5D_{12}}{8a^2b^2} + \frac{5D_{66}}{4a^2b^2} \} \quad (9)$$

Fig. 5

From the above equation we have got basic free vibration frequency $f=904\text{H}$ for middle longitudinal web and $f=600\text{H}$ for two side longitudinal webs, because the latters have less thickness than the former.

The results show that the local parts are in a better vibration condition than the whole bridge system. By the way, we have also done a stability check about the GRP bridge in another sister paper.

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED
PLASTICS SIMPLY-SUPPORTED BEAM HIGHWAY BRIDGE

Ma Xi-Peng
Research Institute of Highway
The Ministry of Communication
Beijing, China

Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) has many distinguishing characteristics, such as lightweight, high strength, easily being shaped, capability of being designed good failure resistance capability, good impact ductility, corrosion proof and etc. So we introduced the GRP material to highway bridge construction and built the first GRP highway bridge in Mi Yun, Beijing in Oct, 1982. After a trial service of 6 years, the structure working condition of this bridge is very good.

Mi Yun GRP highway bridge is a singlespan, simply-supported beam bridge of two traffic lanes with a span length of 20.7 meters and deck width of 11.38 meters. There are 6 GRP honeycomb box beams. Each GRP box beam weighs 6 ton. The weight of whole bridge including is only 1/5 of that of reinforced concrete bridge of same scale.

The design load standards of this GRP highway bridge are:
calculating load: Automobile 15 class.
checking load: Trail 80 class.

Since the completion, the GRP pioneer highway bridge has been Statically and dynamically loading tested to the safety factor of design code requirements.

The practice of the GRP highway bridge proves:

- It is feasible to build GRP highway bridge from technical point of view.
- GRP bridge is intensely competitive economically.

The main advantages of GRP bridge are:

- The weight of bridge can be decreased to a great extent enabling longer span of bridge to be constructed.
- It can be shaped easily and constructed quickly, so the time of construction is short and no major equipment is needed for installation.
- GRP structure is light in weight, aseismic and corrosion-proofed, so it is suitable to region of frequently-occurring and high intensity earthquakes, strongly corrosive environment and soft soil.

Fibre / matrix compatibility
in new cold-cure phenolic resin-based composites.

M Avella*, S M Tavakoli and M G Phillips.

School of Materials Science, University of Bath,
Claverton Down, BATH BA2 7AY, ENGLAND.

INTRODUCTION

Phenolic resins have been known for a long time, in fact the reaction between phenols and aldehydes was first described by Baeyer in 1872 (1). After the findings of Baekeland (2) in the early years of the twentieth century, phenolic resins were one of the most important and widely-used polymers to be produced.

More recently, with the appearance of other thermosetting resins like polyesters and epoxies, interest in phenolic resins waned, but today their excellent properties of fire-resistance and low smoke emission give them widespread application in uses where high temperatures are encountered (3).

Traditional phenolics have several disadvantages for large composite structures: poor fibre / matrix compatibility, ineffectiveness of fibre finishes and sizing treatments, and the high curing temperatures required; and their use has been restricted despite the fact that their high-temperature properties are superior to those of other thermosetting matrix resins.

The new acid-catalysed cold-cure phenolics overcome many of the above disadvantages. They offer low viscosity, low contents of free phenol and formaldehyde, and are suitable for processing by hand layup and RIM or RTM (4). With the modern emphasis on fire safety in public transport, very large potential markets exist for these resins as matrices for GRP.

In this work, we have used differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) to study the curing process of a cold-cure phenolic resin, and the effect of the presence of fibres on the whole curing cycle. We used as reinforcements plain glass fibres, and glass fibres previously sized with appropriate silane coupling agents.

Using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), we have sought an understanding of the chemical processes in the formation of a cold-cure phenolic resin from a liquid resin during the curing reaction at different temperatures, with and without the presence of reinforcement.

* Present address:

Instituto di Richerche su Tecnologia dei Polimeri e Reologia del
C.N.R. Via Toiano, 6, Arco Felice (NA), Italy.

EXPERIMENTAL

The resin used was "Cellobond J2027L", a second-generation cold-cure phenolic resol for the manufacture of fibre-reinforced composites, supplied, with its proprietary catalyst "Phencat 10", by BP Chemicals Ltd. This resin can be cured at temperatures from ambient to 70C. In all tests the catalyst concentration used was 7% by weight. The reinforcement was E-glass fibre, supplied by Owens Corning UK Ltd. The following coupling agents, supplied by Union Carbide Corporation, were used as received:

gamma-aminopropyltriethoxysilane	(code: A1100).
n-beta-aminoethyl-gamma-aminopropyltrimethoxysilane	(code: A1120).
gamma-glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane	(code: A187).

Temperatures and enthalpies relating to the curing of the resin were determined using a DuPont 910 DSC, equipped with a calorimetric cell that allows temperature scanning from -170 to 600C.

For FTIR work a Model 1720X spectrometer by Perkin Elmer was used. Samples were mixed with KBr powder, mounted in a Specac diffuse reflectance accessory, and scanned at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹, twenty to thirty scans of each sample being collected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The DSC thermograms obtained from plain liquid phenolic resin heated from -30 to 300C are characterised by three different peaks. A small endotherm occurs at 30C, perhaps due to the melting of free phenol, or alternatively to reorganisations in hydrogen bonding, which are characteristic of hydroxyl groups, particularly in the presence of water. Secondly, a strong exotherm at 74C is ascribed to the curing reaction. Thirdly, at 100C there is a very strong endotherm, attributed to evaporation of water condensed by the crosslinking reaction.

By contrast, samples containing glass fibres present an endothermic peak for water evaporation having the same enthalpic value, but spread over a wide temperature range, and centring on a higher temperature. This suggests a delayed release of condensed water, indicating that the curing reaction in the presence of glass fibres is incomplete, leaving water imprisoned in the imperfectly-crosslinked network.

An exception to this behaviour was observed in samples containing one of the three coupling agents listed above: A1100 (gamma-aminopropyltriethoxysilane). These showed much more rapid evaporation of the condensed water.

In further experiments, after isothermal curing of phenolic / glass samples incorporating the different coupling agents, DSC was used to determine the residual curing heat. This indicates the degree of cure achieved in the first treatment. Here the samples incorporating A1100 showed the lowest residual curing heat, giving promise of improved stability of resin properties over time.

Studies using FTIR have yielded information concerning:

- (a) Species present in uncured resin, such as the methylol content.
- (b) The competing cure reactions. For example, ether-linkage formation has been found to predominate at low curing temperatures (20C), whereas methylene-linkage formation predominates at higher temperatures (60C).

Additionally, we are attempting to follow the reactions at the interface between phenolic resin and sized glass fibres, using attenuated total reflectance (ATR) spectroscopy. Preliminary results suggest that the presence of treated glass does not inhibit the curing reaction, but this contradiction of the DSC results cannot be resolved until quantitative analysis has been performed on the reactive groups participating in the cure. FTIR work is continuing to this end.

REFERENCES

1. A Baeyer, Deut. Chem. Ges. 25, 380 (1872)
2. L H Baekeland, Ind. Chem. 1, 142 (1909); *ibid*, 2, 479 (1910)
3. K L Forsdyke, R M Mayer and I Patterson, Proc SAMPE Conference, Engineering with composites, London, 1983.
4. K L Forsdyke, Proc. BPF Reinforced Plastics Congress, Brighton (UK), 1982.

MODELING OF IMPERFECT BONDING IN FIBER REINFORCED BRITTLE MATRIX COMPOSITES

G. P. Tandon , AdTech Systems Research Inc., Dayton , OH 45432, USA
N. J. Pagano, WRDC / MLBM, Wright - Patterson AFB, OH 45433, USA

ABSTRACT

The present work is aimed at evaluating the effective thermoelastic moduli of continuous fiber reinforced brittle matrix composite systems in which debonding and slipping between the constituents is observed. The effective modulus theory relates the averages of the stress and strain tensors over a representative volume element through the effective elastic constants. Physical measurement of composite strain, however, is done by the use of strain gages which report the values on the surfaces. Under perfect bonding, both the mathematical and physical definitions of composite strains are equivalent. However, under imperfect conditions at the interface, it is shown that the two definitions do not necessarily lead to the same value of composite strain and hence the effective moduli. This concept has been critically examined under conditions leading to fiber slipping and debonding. It is further shown that if the fiber strain in the longitudinal direction is different from that of the matrix, then the composite effective stiffness tensor becomes unsymmetric. We also correct certain misconceptions that may arise in the computation of composite effective moduli in the presence of matrix voids and/or hollow fibers.

GENERAL THEORY

The fundamental representative volume element which has been used for analysis is a three-phase* concentric cylinder model developed by the authors¹ as shown in Fig. 1. The following boundary / interface conditions are used to determine the displacement and stress field within the constituents of the composite cylinder :

i) Displacements or tractions are prescribed on the radial boundary of the composite cylinder assemblage ; Equilibrium of the composite cylinder assemblage, however, imposes certain implied connections among the traction components²; ii) Stresses and displacements must be bounded at the origin, $r = 0$; iii) For perfect bonding, all displacements and tractions must be continuous across the interfaces; iv) For a smooth interface, only the normal displacements and tractions are required to be continuous across the boundary and the shear components of the traction vector there are set equal to zero in both the constituents^{3,4}. In addition, it is noted that under sliding boundary conditions, the displacement in the direction of the fiber can take independent values in the various constituents³. Since the displacement in the fiber direction is a linear function of the z-coordinate, the longitudinal strain, ϵ_z , is constant within each constituent. Therefore, let us assume for a two-phase composite as an example,

$$(\epsilon_z)_f = k (\epsilon_z)_m \quad (1)$$

where k is a constant and the subscripts f and m refer to the fiber and matrix, respectively.

THE COMPOSITE RESPONSE

Under prescribed displacements or tractions, the stress-strain relation for the composite takes the form

* We use three phases as an example. No difficulty has been encountered in extending this to more phases.

$$\sigma_{kl}^* = C_{klmn}^* (\epsilon_{mn}^* - e_{mn}^*) \quad \text{or} \quad \epsilon_{kl}^* = S_{klmn}^* \sigma_{mn}^* + e_{kl}^* \quad (2a,2b)$$

where C_{klmn}^* is the effective stiffness, S_{klmn}^* is the effective compliance and e_{kl}^* is the effective expansional (non-mechanical) strain of the composite, while σ_{ij}^* and ϵ_{ij}^* are the composite stress and strain tensors, respectively, and ϵ_{ij}^* may or may not be determined by volume averaging.

In the classical theory of effective modulus stresses and strains averaged over a representative volume element are related through the effective elastic constants, i.e., the composite strains ϵ_{ij}^* are given by $\bar{\epsilon}_{ij}$ (an overbar over a stated quantity denotes an average value over the whole volume). Physical measurement of composite strain, however, is done by the use of strain gages which report the values on the surfaces. Under perfect bonding, both the mathematical and physical definitions of composite strains are equivalent⁵. However, under imperfect conditions at the interface, the two definitions do not necessarily lead to the same value of composite strain and hence the effective moduli.

The composite effective elastic constants can be alternately defined by making use of the physical measurement of composite strain on the surface, ϵ_{ij}^S , as a measure of the actual strain of the composite, ϵ_{ij}^* . For this analysis, we let the composite strain ϵ_{ij}^* be equal to surface strain ϵ_{ij}^S (at least on the radial boundary of the composite cylinder).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to illustrate the application of the present approach, we have selected a unidirectional composite (aligned along x_1) for the analysis. It is assumed that the fibers are uncoated and that no interstitial matrix exists. The effective coefficients are symmetric for a) perfect bonding and ; b) smooth interface and $k = 1$ but when we have relative displacement in the longitudinal direction between the constituents, the symmetric relation between C_{12} and C_{21} ceases to hold good and the composite effective stiffness tensor becomes unsymmetric. We now have a total of six, not five, independent elastic constants. Further, when the fiber strain is set equal to zero, the volume averaged strain $\bar{\epsilon}_{11}$ is lower than that prescribed on the lateral surface, ϵ_{11}^S . The mathematical definition of composite strain, ϵ_{11}^* , therefore leads to a larger value of the composite effective stiffness, C_{21} .

The effective engineering constants can be defined by the following modified relations between the stiffness coefficients where the symmetry between C_{12} and C_{21} is not assumed

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= C_{11} - \frac{2 C_{12} C_{21}}{C_{22} + C_{23}} & G_{12} &= C_{66} \\ \nu_{12} &= \frac{C_{21}}{C_{22} + C_{23}} & K_{23} &= \frac{1}{2} (C_{22} + C_{23}) \\ E_{22} &= C_{22} + \frac{C_{12} C_{21} (-C_{22} + C_{23}) + C_{23} (-C_{11} C_{23} + C_{12} C_{21})}{C_{11} C_{22} - C_{12} C_{21}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Under conditions leading to complete separation of fiber from the matrix, we generate a cylindrical hole of the size of fiber in the matrix material. How do we now define the strain of the composite which resembles a 'Swiss cheese' matrix? Clearly the volume average definition of composite strain appears to be meaningless because we do not know the strain inside the hole. Alternately, the surface strains could be taken as a measure of the composite strain to define the moduli of the debonded composite. We had earlier

stated that if the bonding across the interface is continuous, the mathematical and physical definitions of composite strains are equivalent. It therefore appears that the solution of the void problem reported by Hashin et al ⁶ can be obtained by setting the ' fiber ' elastic modulus equal to zero and retaining the displacement continuity across the interface such that the stresses within the ' void ' region are zero but the strains are non-zero. For numerical computations , we will interpret the ' void ' to be a material of low elastic modulus. This is but one approach to compute the stress field within the (hollow) matrix material. Applying zero traction boundary conditions on the surface of the void leads to the identical stress field. The issue that arises relates to the definition of quantities to be utilized as a measure of the composite strain tensor.

The computed thermoelastic moduli of a debonded composite simulated by a cylindrical void (fiber of low elastic modulus) are found to be different from that obtained by simulation through a perfectly smooth fiber-matrix interface. Complete fiber separation effects all the composite properties. Some of the results are quite curious and represent a discrepancy between the mathematical and physical definitions of composite strain when the fiber vanishes. Clearly the physical value of strain determined by a surface strain gage differs from the volume averaged value. Further, it is interesting to note that the effective moduli of the ' void ' problem computed using surface strains as the measure of the composite strains are independent of the sliding boundary conditions at the interface.

REFERENCES

1. N. J. Pagano and G. P. Tandon, *Comp. Sci. and Techn.*, 31 (4) (1988), 273
2. N. J. Pagano, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 38 (1971), 1
3. Y. Benveniste and J. Aboudi, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, 20 (11/12) (1984), 935
4. T. Mura, I. Jasiuk and B. Tsuchida, *Int. J. Solids Structures*, 21 (12) (1985), 1165
5. N. J. Pagano, *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Vol 2, Ed. by G. P. Sendeckyj, Academic Press N. Y. and London (1974), 1
6. Z. Hashin and B. W. Rosen , *J. Appl. Mech.*, 31 (1964), 223

Fig 1 THEORETICAL MODEL

APPLICATION OF THE TENSOR POLYNOMIAL FAILURE CRITERION TO WOOD-BASED COMPOSITES

J. C. Suhling, K. C. Yeh
(Department of Mechanical Engineering, Auburn University,
Auburn, AL 36849-5341, USA)

J. M. Considine
(U.S.D.A. Forest Products Laboratory, Madison, WI 53705-2398, USA)

ABSTRACT

In this work, the biaxial strength of wood-based composite materials has been investigated. An extensive set of biaxial failure data for paperboard at four levels of shear has been utilized to evaluate the accuracy of the tensor polynomial criterion at RH = 50%. Additional experiments have been performed at other levels of relative humidity to measure the uniaxial and biaxial input parameters of the criterion and predict zero-shear failure envelopes.

INTRODUCTION

Unlike laminated fiber-reinforced composite materials, paper (paperboard) is a multiphase composite composed of moisture, fibers, voids, and chemical additives. A nonrandom arrangement of the fiber network making up a sheet is caused by hydrodynamic forces occurring in the papermaking machine. A single preferred orientation of the fibers results which is called the machine direction (MD). The in-plane direction perpendicular to the preferred direction is called the cross-machine direction (CD). These in-plane directions of material symmetry allow for paper to be modeled macroscopically as an orthotropic solid.

Paper materials tend to exhibit nonlinear mechanical behavior which is affected significantly by slight changes in the surrounding environmental conditions. Accurate predictions of paperboard strength under general biaxial normal loading plus shear are needed by the design engineer when considering typical structural applications. In this work, the tensor polynomial criterion has been applied to paperboard and the effects of moisture content on biaxial failure strength have been examined. In a recent investigation by Suhling, et al [1], an extensive set of biaxial failure data at four levels of shear has been utilized to evaluate the accuracy of the criterion at RH = 50%. Additional experiments have now been performed at other levels of relative humidity to measure the uniaxial and biaxial input parameters of the criterion and predict zero-shear failure envelopes.

TENSOR POLYNOMIAL FAILURE CRITERIA

When considering plane-stress conditions where the coordinate axes are aligned with the axes of material symmetry, the tensor polynomial criterion (Tsai-Wu theory) with linear and quadratic terms predicts failure when

$$F_{11}\sigma_1^2 + 2F_{12}\sigma_1\sigma_2 + F_{22}\sigma_2^2 + F_1\sigma_1 + F_2\sigma_2 + F_{66}\tau_{12}^2 = 1 \quad (1)$$

where subscripts 1 and 2 on stresses σ and τ denote the directions of material symmetry (MD and CD). Most of the coefficients in eq. (1) can be found by requiring that the tensile and compressive strengths X , X' , Y , Y' in the machine and cross-machine directions, respectively, and the pure shear strength S be on the failure surface. These calculations lead to

$$F_{11} = \frac{1}{XX'} \quad , \quad F_{22} = \frac{1}{YY'} \quad , \quad F_1 = \frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'} \quad , \quad F_2 = \frac{1}{Y} - \frac{1}{Y'} \quad , \quad F_{66} = \frac{1}{S^2} \quad (2)$$

Coefficient F_{12} must be evaluated using an experiment where both σ_1 and σ_2 are non-zero. For a single experimentally measured biaxial failure data point $(\sigma_1^f, \sigma_2^f, \tau_{12}^f)$, the value of F_{12} is found by

$$F_{12} = \frac{1}{2\sigma_1^f\sigma_2^f} [1 - (F_{11}\sigma_1^{f2} + F_{22}\sigma_2^{f2} + F_1\sigma_1^f + F_2\sigma_2^f + F_{66}\tau_{12}^{f2})] \quad (3)$$

Many different biaxial tests for evaluation of this coefficient have been proposed.

APPLICATION OF THE CRITERION AT RH = 50%

In a recent investigation by Suhling, et al [1], an extensive set of biaxial failure data for paperboard at four levels of shear and RH = 50% has been utilized to evaluate the predictive capabilities of the tensor polynomial criterion. Experimental measurements were made using on- and off-axis uniaxial, cruciform, and cylinder specimens. Analysis has shown that the best fit to the data at all levels of shear is obtained by taking $F_{12} = 0$. The correlation in this case is shown in Figure 1. The best fit to the zero-shear data alone was found by calculating F_{12} using biaxial tension data. This correlation is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1

Figure 2

MEASUREMENT OF THE INPUT DATA TO THE FAILURE CRITERION AT SEVERAL LEVELS OF HUMIDITY

Uniaxial tensile and compressive strengths in the MD and CD (X, X', Y, Y') have been measured for 100% Lakes State softwood unbleached kraft paper (basis weight 205 g/m², mass density 670 kg/m³) at humidity levels of RH = 50%, 70%, and 90%. Tests were performed using a specially constructed apparatus developed at the Forest Products Laboratory [2]. This device consists of a load frame and vacuum restraint system enclosed in an environmentally controlled chamber. Figure 3 contains a tabulation of the experimentally recorded uniaxial compressive and tensile strength data in the machine and cross-machine directions at the three humidities considered. Each data point represents the average of six uniaxial tests.

In order to evaluate coefficient F_{12} , biaxial tension failure data were measured for the same kraft paperboard by using pressurized cylindrical tube burst tests. Paper tubes were formed from flat sheets using a thin glue seam and the ends were reinforced using additional material. The tubes were then firmly clamped to aluminum end caps and a thin rubber bladder was used to transmit the internal pressure loading. Axial expansion of the tube was allowed using roller bearing supports. In this study, the tubes were constructed with the CD along the cylinder's axial direction and the MD along the hoop direction. Using the approximate strength of materials relations for thin cylindrical pressure vessels leads to an expression for the measured biaxial failure point

$$(\sigma_1^f, \sigma_2^f, \tau_{12}^f) = \left(\frac{p_f R}{t}, \frac{p_f R}{2t}, 0 \right) \quad (4)$$

where p_f is the measure failure pressure, and R, t are the radius and thickness of the cylinder, respectively. Five cylindrical tube burst tests were performed at humidities RH = 50%, 70%, and 90%. Average values of the biaxial failure point are tabulated in Figure 4. A typical failed specimen is shown in Figure 5.

	RH = 50%	RH = 70%	RH = 90%
X (MPa)	51.77	47.41	36.40
X' (MPa)	21.42	20.20	14.74
Y (MPa)	27.88	21.82	15.36
Y' (MPa)	14.70	13.64	9.70

Figure 3

	FAILURE POINT (σ_1, σ_2) - MPa
RH = 50%	(50.42, 25.21)
RH = 70%	(44.92, 22.46)
RH = 90%	(32.20, 16.10)

Figure 4

FAILURE ENVELOPE PREDICTIONS

The zero shear failure envelopes of paperboard at RH = 50%, 70%, and 90% were predicted using the tensor polynomial criterion as expressed in eqs. (1-4) incorporating the failure data tabulated in Figures 3 and 4. A composite of all results is found in Figure 6. The obtained curves show the expected trend that the failure envelopes will reduce in size without overlapping as the humidity is increased. The biaxial tension quadrant is most affected. Current efforts are directed towards expanding the experimental data base so that well-based models can be formulated which describe the humidity dependence of paperboard biaxial strength.

Figure 5

PAPERBOARD FAILURE ENVELOPE USING THE TENSOR POLYNOMIAL CRITERION (RH = 50,70,90)

Figure 6

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the tensor polynomial criterion was used for predicting paperboard biaxial strength. Several experiments have been performed to measure uniaxial and biaxial failure parameters at three levels of relative humidity. The criterion shows excellent correlation with an extensive set of failure data collected at RH = 50%. Obtained results follow expected trends and additional testing is underway to guide future modeling efforts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is based upon work supported by the U.S.D.A. Forest Products Laboratory, Madison, WI, and the Auburn University Pulp and Paper Research and Education Center.

REFERENCES

1. Suhling, J. C., Rowlands, R. E., Johnson, M. W. and Gunderson, D. E., "Tensorial Strength Analysis of Paperboard," *Experimental Mechanics*, Vol. 25(1), pp. 75-84, 1985.
2. Considine, J. M. and Gunderson, D. E., "A Method for Mechanical Property Testing of Paperboard During Compressive Creep in a Cyclic Humidity Environment," *Experimental Techniques*, Vol. 11(9), pp. 18-21, 1987.

ANALOGY BETWEEN THERMAL STRESS AND LATERAL BENDING
OF ORTHOTROPIC MEDIA

Wu Xiuli, Kang Hongwei, Zhang Xiangzhou
(Northwestern Polytechnical University, Xi'an, China)

ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with an analogy between plane thermal stress and plate bending problems of orthotropic media. Based on the analogy, thermal stresses in an orthotropic media can straightforwardly be obtained from bending stresses in a similar orthotropic plate and vice versa. One example has been considered to illustrate the application of the analogy.

THE ANALOGY

Consider the following two problems:

1. Plane Thermal Stress Problem of an Orthotropic Body

It is known that the stress function (x,y) for the body should be determined from the following basic equation and boundary conditions:

$$a_{22} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^4} + (2a_{12} + a_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + a_{11} \frac{\partial^4 \phi}{\partial y^4} = -\alpha_2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - \alpha_1 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}, \quad (1)$$

$$\phi = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial n} = 0, \quad \text{on the boundary.} \quad (2)$$

The meaning of the coefficients in the above equation can best be enunciated via the following strain-stress relations:

$$\epsilon_x = a_{11} \sigma_x + a_{12} \sigma_y + \alpha_1 T, \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_y = a_{12} \sigma_x + a_{22} \sigma_y + \alpha_2 T, \quad (4)$$

$$\nu_{xy} = a_{66} \tau_{xy}. \quad (5)$$

2. Lateral Bending of an Orthotropic Clamped Plate

The deflection of the plate, $w(x,y)$, should be sought from the following basic equation and boundary conditions:

$$D_x \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_1 + 2D_{xy}) \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = q, \quad (6)$$

$$w = \frac{\partial w}{\partial n} = 0. \quad \text{on the boundary.} \quad (7)$$

where

$$(D_x, D_y, D_1, D_{xy}) = (E'_x, E'_y, E''_x, E''_y) \frac{h^3}{12}, \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma_x = -Z(E'_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + E''_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}), \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_y = -Z(E'_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + E''_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}), \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{xy} = -2GZ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y}. \quad (11)$$

The last three equations are used to enunciate the meaning of some orthotropic moduli in equation (8).

It is easy to see that there is a complete analogy between the two problems, i.e., we have

$$\phi(x, y) = w(x, y) \quad (12)$$

Provided that the geometries of the cross section of the orthotropic body and the planform of the orthotropic plate are identical and that

$$(D_x, 2(D_1 + 2D_{xy}), D_y) = (a_{22}, 2a_{12} + a_{66}, a_{11}), \quad (13)$$

$$q(x, y) = -\alpha_2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} - \alpha_1 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2}. \quad (14)$$

Since

$$(\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}) = (\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2}, \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x^2}, -\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x \partial y}) \quad (15)$$

and

$$M_x = -(D_x \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_1 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}), \quad (16)$$

$$M_y = -(D_1 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + D_y \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}), \quad (17)$$

$$M_{xy} = -2D_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (18)$$

hold respectively in the two problems. It can be seen that we can obtain the thermal stresses in the first problem from the bending and twisting moments in the second problem straightforwardly and vice versa.

Thermal Stresses in an Orthotropic Rectangular Plate

Applying the analogy, the problem can be solved exactly if a solution to the corresponding plate bending problem could come into our possession. To develop an effective solution to the lateral bending of an orthotropic rectangular plate clamped on edges, the following procedure is proposed:

A. Find the solution w to a plate with two opposite edges clamped and the other two

- simply supported as well as the rotation angle on the simply supported edges.
 B. Apply bending moments $f(x)$ and $f(x)$ on the simply supported edges of the plate and find the corresponding solution w .
 C. Determine $f(x)$ and $f(x)$ according to on the simply supported edges.
 D. $w = w + w$ is the final solution to the problem.

It can be seen from the above procedure that our solution method is similar to but considerably simpler than that developed by Timoshenko. The final form of the deflection depends on the roots of a characteristic equation. Herein only a solution of a particular case for distinct real characteristic roots and

$$q(x, y) = q_0 = \text{const} \quad (19)$$

are given below for exemplifying purpose:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w(x, y) = & \frac{4q_0 b^4}{D_y \pi^5} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{\sin \frac{n\pi y}{b}}{n^5} \left(1 + \frac{s_2 \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 x}{b} \operatorname{sh} \frac{n\pi s_2 z'}{2} - s_1 \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 x}{b} \operatorname{sh} \frac{n\pi s_1 z'}{2}}{s_1 \operatorname{sh} \frac{n\pi s_1 z'}{2} \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 z'}{2} - s_2 \operatorname{sh} \frac{n\pi s_2 z'}{2} \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 z'}{2}} \right) \\
 & + \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{E_n a^2 \cos \frac{n\pi x}{a}}{D_y n^2 \pi^2 (s_1^2 - s_2^2)} \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 (y - \frac{b}{2})}{a} / \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 z}{2} - \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 (y - \frac{b}{2})}{a} / \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 z}{2} \\
 & + \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots} \frac{C_n \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b}}{I_n} \left(\operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 x}{b} - \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 x}{b} \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_2 z'}{2} / \operatorname{ch} \frac{n\pi s_1 z'}{2} \right), \quad (20)
 \end{aligned}$$

where E_n 's stand for constant coefficients. The solutions to other cases of the characteristic roots can be obtained from equation (20) via some limiting processes.

Table 1 Numerical values of thermal stresses and bending moments ($D_x = 1.425 \times 10^5 h^3 / 12$,

$$D_y = 0.119 \times 10^5 h^3 / 12, a = b, D_{xy} = 0.12 \times 10^5 h^3 / 12, d = D_y / qa)$$

$\frac{x}{a}$	$\frac{y}{b}$	$\frac{\sigma_x d}{10^3}$	$\frac{\sigma_y d}{10^3}$	$\frac{\tau_{xy} d}{10^3}$	$\frac{M_x}{10^3 qa}$	$\frac{M_y}{10^3 qa}$	$\frac{M_{xy}}{10^3 qa}$
0.0	0.0	6.9388	0.0000	0.0000	-83.366	-0.3790	0.0000
0.5	0.5	0.0000	2.6826	0.0000	-0.1465	-2.6826	0.0000
0.1	0.1	0.0348	-0.2234	0.3629	-0.3978	-0.3648	0.7258

The numerical values of thermal stresses and bending moments corresponding to solution (20) are presented in Table 1 showing the validity and effectiveness of the solution and the analogy.

REFERENCES

1. Timoshenko S and Woinowsky-Krieger S, Theory of Plates and Shells, Mcgraw-hill (1959), 364.

APPLICATION OF A NONLINEAR ELASTIC CONSTITUTIVE THEORY FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS TO THIN SHEETS UNDER IN-PLANE LOADING

S. T. Lin and J. C. Suhling
(Department of Mechanical Engineering, Auburn University,
Auburn, AL 36849-5341, USA)

ABSTRACT

In this work, a theory for the nonlinear elastic response of thin orthotropic plates subjected to in-plane loading has been presented and applied. The utilized nonlinear stress-strain relations are based on a hyperelastic formulation and an assumed form for the strain energy density function. The theory has been implemented numerically for paperboard using a nonlinear finite element model on a Cray XMP-24 supercomputer. An example problem consisting of a uniaxially loaded sheet with a hole has been considered.

INTRODUCTION

Many current practical engineering problems involve nonlinear anisotropic media which are subjected to complicated biaxial states of stress, including shear. Insufficient material characterization and lack of reliable strength predictions often hamper analysis in such situations. Paper (paperboard) is prime example of a nonlinear material with great economic importance and yet a limited design technology database. It is a multiphase composite composed of moisture, fibers, voids, and chemical additives. Its three-dimensional structure is basically an assembly of discrete fibers bonded together into a complex network. A single preferred orientation of the fibers results from the hydrodynamic forces present in the papermaking machine. In the terminology of the paper industry, this direction in the sheet with the highest stiffness (x_1 -direction) is referred to as the machine direction (MD). That with the lowest stiffness (x_2 -direction) is called the cross-machine direction (CD). These in-plane directions of material symmetry allow for paper to be modeled macroscopically as an orthotropic solid. Its mechanical behavior is highly nonlinear, and strongly influenced by the environmental conditions of temperature and relative humidity.

Continuum models for paper elastic response have been restricted typically to linear orthotropic analyses. This approach is unsatisfactory since paper behavior is highly nonlinear even at low strains. Thorpe [1] has presented a tangential nonlinear elastic finite element analysis of a paper sheet in uniaxial extension. An incremental approach was adopted to update the stiffness matrix. In the present work, a total strain hyperelastic formulation has been utilized to model paperboard behavior, and a theory for the nonlinear elastic response of thin sheets under in-plane loading has been presented and applied. Solutions to the analytical equations have been found numerically using a nonlinear finite element model on a Cray XMP-24 supercomputer.

A THEORY FOR NONLINEAR ORTHOTROPIC MEDIA

In a hyperelastic material, the stresses are related to the strains using

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial W(\epsilon)}{\partial \epsilon_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

These equations assume small strains and displacement gradients. For nonlinear orthotropic media under plane stress conditions, a new constitutive theory based on an assumed form for the strain energy density function has been suggested [2-4]. It is proposed that a class of materials exist for which strain energy density function W is a nonlinear function of the single variable

$$W = W(e) \quad (2)$$

Positive definite effective strain measure e is given by

$$e = \frac{\epsilon_1^2}{\nu_{21}} + \frac{\epsilon_2^2}{\nu_{12}} + 2\epsilon_1\epsilon_2 + \frac{c}{4} \gamma_{12}^2 \quad (3)$$

where ν_{12}, ν_{21} are constant Poisson's ratios, and C is related to the initial shear modulus by $C = 2 [G_{12}/W'(0)]$. Substitution of eq. (2) into eqs. (1) leads to the stress-strain relations (plane stress) for the proposed nonlinear theory

$$\sigma_1 = 2 W'(e) \left[\frac{\epsilon_1}{\nu_{21}} + \epsilon_2 \right], \quad \sigma_2 = 2 W'(e) \left[\frac{\epsilon_2}{\nu_{12}} + \epsilon_1 \right], \quad \tau_{12} = \frac{C}{2} W'(e) \gamma_{12} \quad (4)$$

These equations are for a coordinate system aligned with the directions of material symmetry. They predict constant Poisson's ratios but allow for nonlinear uniaxial stress-strain curves. The nonlinear formulation can be reduced to linear orthotropic elasticity theory by taking W as a linear function of e .

A theory for in-plane loading of thin nonlinear elastic plates is obtained by combining the stress-strain relations given in eqs. (4) with the linear strain displacement relations

$$\epsilon_1 = \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_1}, \quad \epsilon_2 = \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_2}, \quad \gamma_{12} = \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x_1} \quad (5)$$

and the equilibrium equations (no body forces)

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \tau_{12}}{\partial x_2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \tau_{12}}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial \sigma_2}{\partial x_2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Equations (4-6) are eight equations in eight unknowns. They are approximate in that small strains and displacement gradients have been assumed in eqs. (1,5).

Experimental results have demonstrated that paperboard Poisson's ratios are nearly constant. However, the uniaxial σ vs. ϵ response is highly nonlinear even at small strains. These facts suggest that the proposed nonlinear stress-strain relations have a high potential for accurate modeling of paperboard elastic behavior (and inelastic behavior if only loading situations are considered). Extensive experimental data for paperboard have been utilized to determine material constants and obtain the best form for the strain energy density function found in the nonlinear theory [3-4]. The particular paper considered was machine made 100% Lakes State softwood, unbleached Kraft paper, basis weight 205 g/m², mass density 670 kg/m³. Environmental conditions were maintained at 23°C and 50% R.H. according to TAPPI standard T402 OS-70.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Numerical solutions to the analytical formulation for in-plane loading of thin nonlinear elastic sheets presented in eqs. (4-6) have been obtained for a particular geometries and loadings using a nonlinear iterative finite element approach. A large Fortran computer code has been developed and adapted to run on the Cray XMP-24 supercomputer operated by the Alabama Supercomputer Network. A preprocessor which includes a mesh generation routine was used to define the geometry and loading. Numeric output was written in a format compatible with a popular PC-based finite element software package. This allowed for extensive graphical postprocessing of the results. Recorded execution times indicate that consideration of large meshes (several hundred elements) and/or multiple geometries and loading conditions is feasible only on a supercomputer-class machine such as the Cray XMP-24.

The nonlinear finite element program developed uses quadratic, cubic, and quartic isoparametric elements. In all cases, the nonlinear algebraic equations are solved by a multidimensional Newton's (Newton-Raphson) method. The linear system which must be solved to do a Newton iteration is solved directly by Gaussian elimination. The Cuthill-McKee algorithm and a special bandwidth reduction technique are used to number the nodes and give the linear system a banded structure. To initiate the Newton-Raphson iteration procedure, initial guesses for the two displacement fields are specified. Convergence occurs only when the initial guesses are suitably close to the actual solution. A procedure has been developed to generate loading histories by performing a sequence of finite element analyses using interpolated displacement results from the current loading as input initial guesses for the next loading.

EXAMPLE APPLICATION

An example problem consisting of a uniaxially loaded paperboard sheet with a hole has been considered. Figure 1 shows the specimen geometry (1.5 x 3 x .01 inches with .5 inch diameter hole) and loading. Because of the inherent symmetry present, only one quarter of the specimen was considered. The utilized mesh is shown in Figure 2. It contains 1500 quadratic triangular isoparametric elements. The stress, strain, and displacement distributions have been determined as a function of applied loading by utilizing the finite element model discussed above. This procedure incorporated material constants and strain energy density function measured experimentally for paperboard [3-4]. A typical plot of the horizontal normal stress distribution is shown in Figure 3 (applied stress $\sigma_0 = 3$ psi).

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a total strain hyperelastic formulation has been utilized to model nonlinear orthotropic behavior, and a theory for the nonlinear elastic response of thin sheets under in-plane loading has been presented and applied. Solutions to the analytical equations have been found numerically for paperboard using a nonlinear finite element model on a Cray XMP-24 supercomputer.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research is based upon work supported by the Auburn University Pulp and Paper Research and Education Center, and the Auburn University Grant-in-Aid Program.

REFERENCES

1. Thorpe, J. L., "Paper as an Orthotropic Thin Plate," *TAPPI*, Vol. 64(3), pp. 119-121, 1981.
2. Johnson, M. W. and Urbanik, T. J., "A Nonlinear Theory for Elastic Plates with Applications to Characterizing Paper Properties," *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, Vol. 51(1), pp. 146-152, 1984.
3. Suhling, J. C., Constitutive Relations and Failure Predictions for Nonlinear Orthotropic Media, *Ph.D. Thesis*, University of Wisconsin, 1985.
4. Suhling, J. C., Rowlands, R. E., Johnson, M. W. and Gunderson, D. E., "Analytical-Experimental Investigation of the Constitutive Behavior of Paperboard," in the *Proceeding of the 1986 SEM Fall Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, pp. 150-158, Keystone, CO, November 2-5, 1986.

LINEAR RESPONSE OF POLYCRYSTALS TO COUPLED FIELDS:
EXACT RELATIONS AMONG THE COEFFICIENTS

Mordehai Milgrom
Department of Physics
and
S. Shtrikman
Department of Electronics*

Weizmann Institute of Science
76100 Rehovot, Israel

Abstract:

The response coefficients of a polycrystal, made of domains of a uniaxial crystal, to coupled fields-such as in the thermoelectric or magnetoelectric effects-are not all independent. Only $6n$ constants are needed to determine all the $3n(3n+1)/2$ measurable constants of any such a polycrystal-given the constants of the single crystal. The constraints on $L_{(\alpha\beta)}^*$ -the response matrix of the polycrystal, for the space coordinate α, β -are $L_{(\alpha\beta)}^* (L^{||})^{-1} L^{\perp} - L^{\perp} (L^{||})^{-1} L_{(\alpha\beta)}^* = 0$, where L^{\perp} and $L^{||}$ are the principal response matrices of the single crystal. For two-field phenomena, the most general polycrystal of this kind can have, only 14 independent constants-when no information on the constants of the crystal is available-instead of the 21 of a general crystal.

There is obvious interest in determining the effective linear-response properties-such as the dielectric, magnetic permeability, conductivity, diffusion tensors etc. -of polycrystals made of a crystal whose principal constants are known. Much of the work in this vein has focused on obtaining bounds on the effective constants-given some information on the structure of the polycrystal^{1,2} (for example, that it is statistically isotropic). We shall discuss here effective properties, pertinent to the response of the polycrystal, that is made of a uniaxial crystal, not to the application of a single driving field-as in the example above-but to many coupled fields. As we shall show, in this case the response coefficients of the polycrystal must satisfy a number of relations among themselves, in which the response coefficients of the single crystal appear, but which are otherwise independent of the structure of the polycrystal itself.

Consider the coupled multifield linear-response properties of crystals: the application of driving fields to the material, induces in it fluxes $\vec{J} \equiv (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$ that are related linearly to the driving fields-the latter being derivable from potentials $\phi \equiv (\phi_1, \phi_2, \dots, \phi_n)$:

$$\vec{J} = -L \vec{\nabla} \phi. \quad (1)$$

Here, L is the $n \times n$ response matrix of the material. This description fits equilibrium

*Also with the Department of physics, University of California, San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093.

phenomena such as the magnetoelectric effect, where the driving forces are magnetic and electric fields, and the fluxes are the displacement and magnetic-induction fields. It also fits nonequilibrium processes where the fluxes are currents, such as the thermoelectric effect, in which the potentials are, essentially, the temperature and electric potential; and the conjugate fluxes are, respectively, the heat and electric currents. Another such process is coupled multispecies diffusion, where the potentials are related to the concentrations and the fluxes are the conjugate particle-currents.

In anisotropic materials, the elements of L are spatial tensors (we shall work in three dimensions, but all the results are straightforwardly generalized to any number of dimensions). Thus,

$$J_{\alpha k} = -L_{\alpha\beta km} \partial_{\beta} \epsilon_m. \quad (2)$$

(Latin indices indicate the fields, while Greek ones are reserved for space coordinates.) We shall be dealing with two sets of submatrices of L : the space-tensor moduli, $L_{(km)}$, of the material; and the $n \times n$ matrices $L_{(\alpha\beta)}$: the response matrix of the α component of the currents to gradients applied in the β direction. Their elements are

$$L_{(km)\alpha\beta} = L_{(\alpha\beta)km} = L_{\alpha\beta km}. \quad (3)$$

Barring rare exceptions³, L is symmetric under the simultaneous exchange of the field and space indices:

$$L_{\beta\alpha mk} = L_{\alpha\beta km} \quad \text{or} \quad L_{(mk)} = \tilde{L}_{(km)}, \quad L_{(\beta\alpha)} = \tilde{L}_{(\alpha\beta)}. \quad (4)$$

In nonequilibrium phenomena this symmetry is assured by the Onsager relations⁴; in equilibrium processes it results from the structure of the governing energy function of the problem. The general response matrix thus has $3n(3n+1)/2$ independent elements.

We confine our attention to uniaxial crystals; these have principal axes-common to all the tensors $L_{(km)}$ -two of which are degenerate, and we choose them as the y and z axes; thus,

$$L_{(km)} = \text{diag}(l_{km}^{\perp}, l_{km}^{\perp}, l_{km}^{\parallel}). \quad (5)$$

Antimony and Bismuth are examples of uniaxial crystals showing an appreciable thermoelectric effect, and Chromium oxide is one with prominent magnetoelectric properties.

For convenience of expression we shall be speaking of crystals all along; all we assume, however, is that the building material is one with principal axes that are common to all the tensor moduli, and that two of the axes only are degenerate; the material needs not be a crystal.

Look now at the two $n \times n$ matrices $L^{\parallel} = L_{(zz)}$ and $L^{\perp} = L_{(xx)} = L_{(yy)}$ whose elements are:

$$L_{km}^{\parallel} = l_{km}^{\parallel} = L_{zzkm}, \quad L_{km}^{\perp} \equiv l_{km}^{\perp} = L_{xxkm}. \quad (6)$$

Clearly, L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} are symmetric by virtue of eqs. (3)(6); they are also both positive definite. This has to do with the fact that, by its physical significance, the generating function $G \equiv \sum L_{\alpha\beta km} \partial_{\alpha} \epsilon_k \partial_{\beta} \epsilon_m = -\vec{J} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \epsilon$, has to be positive. In the nonequilibrium case, this function gives the entropy increase rate⁴; in the equilibrium case it is proportional to the energy function near the equilibrium state and has to be positive if the equilibrium is to be stable.

The crux of our argument rests on the fact that any two such real, symmetric, and positive-definite matrices (of the same rank) can be diagonalized, simultaneously, by a congruent transformation using a real matrix W :

$$WL^{\parallel} \tilde{W} = \lambda^{\parallel} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{\parallel}, \lambda_2^{\parallel}, \dots, \lambda_n^{\parallel}), \quad WL^{\perp} \tilde{W} = \lambda^{\perp} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{\perp}, \lambda_2^{\perp}, \dots, \lambda_n^{\perp}). \quad (7)$$

Note that W is, in general, not a unitary matrix, as indeed it cannot be if L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} do not commute. Define now the eigenpotentials and eigenfluxes

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1} \phi, \quad \vec{j} = W \vec{J}; \quad (8)$$

they satisfy

$$j_k^{\parallel} = -\lambda_k^{\parallel} \partial^{\parallel} \psi_k, \quad j_k^{\perp} = -\lambda_k^{\perp} \partial^{\perp} \psi_k, \quad (9)$$

and the response matrix in this basis is thus

$$\lambda_{\alpha\beta km} = \lambda_k^{\alpha} \delta_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{km} \quad (\alpha, \beta = \parallel, \perp): \quad (10)$$

the fields are thus decoupled in the eigenfields. The generating function is form-invariant under this congruent transformation: $G = -\vec{j} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi$. A similar diagonalization procedure underlies the choice of normal modes of small oscillations near equilibrium⁵ through the simultaneous diagonalization of the kinetic- and potential-energy quadratic forms.

If the crystal properties are described in axes other than the principal ones, the response matrix is not diagonal in the space indices but is still diagonal in the fields.

Consider now a polycrystal, made of a uniaxial crystal, by filling space with crystal-lites whose principal axes are arbitrarily oriented. The effective response matrix, L^* , of such a polycrystal can still not connect different eigenfields and so its representation, λ^* , in the eigenbasis must be of the form

$$\lambda^*_{\alpha\beta km} = \lambda^k_{\alpha\beta} \delta_{km}, \quad (11)$$

with $\lambda^k_{\alpha\beta}$ symmetric in α, β . This implies that only the $6n$ elements of $\lambda^k_{\alpha\beta}$ are needed to determine the $3n(3n+1)/2$ elements of L^* -which represent the effective response matrix in the original-"physical" -basis. The latter must then satisfy $9n(n-1)/2$ relations among themselves, that may contain the elements of L , the response matrix of the single crystal, but that are totally independent of the structure of the polycrystal.

These relations are obtained as follows: For every choice of space indices α, β , the $n \times n$ matrix $\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$ whose elements are

$$\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)km} = \lambda^*_{\alpha\beta km}, \quad (12)$$

is diagonal, It represents the response matrix of the polycrystal in the eigenbasis, and is related to the matrix $L^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$ -whose elements are $L^*_{(\alpha\beta)km} = L^*_{\alpha\beta km}$ -by the same congruent transformation:

$$\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)} = W L^*_{(\alpha\beta)} W. \quad (13)$$

Now, $\Lambda^*_{(\alpha\beta)}$, λ^{\parallel} , and λ^{\perp} are all diagonal and thus all commute with each other. We can thus write trivially

$$\Lambda^*(\alpha \beta) (\lambda^{\parallel})^{-1} \lambda^{\perp} - \lambda^{\perp} (\lambda^{\parallel})^{-1} \Lambda^*(\alpha \beta) = 0. \quad (14)$$

Multiplying by W on the left and \tilde{W} on the right, and inserting $\tilde{W}\tilde{W}^{-1}$ and $W^{-1}W$ between the matrices, we get the relations we are after:

$$C [L^*(\alpha \beta), L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp}] = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$C(M_1, M_2, M_3) \equiv M_1 M_2^{-1} M_3^{-1} M_2^{-1} M_1.$$

To recapitulate the points underlying this derivation: (i) Any three matrices, M_1, M_2, M_3 that can be diagonalized simultaneously by a congruent transformation—for this it is necessary that they be symmetric—satisfy $C(M_1, M_2, M_3) = 0$. (ii) The physical input consists of the fact that the submatrices $L^*(\alpha \beta)$, of the response matrix of any polycrystal made of a uniaxial crystal, are diagonal in the eigenbasis of fields that is defined by the submatrices L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} of the single crystal; hence, they are all diagonalized together.

Equation (15) involves nine matrix relations (one for each choice of α, β) each of which consists of $n(n-1)/2$ independent equations: the arguments of C in eq.(15) are all symmetric, and so C itself is antisymmetric, by construction, and has only $n(n-1)/2$ independent elements. When the single crystal is, in fact, isotropic; i.e., $L^{\perp} = L^{\parallel}$ the compatibility conditions reduce to identities and are devoid of any information.

Milgrom and Shtrikman⁶ have employed very similar arguments to cast constraints on the linear-response properties of two-phase mixtures of isotropic materials where similar relations are obtained among the response coefficients of the composites and involve the response matrices of the two components in place of L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} in the present case; they also discuss, in some detail, the properties of these compatibility conditions.

The elements of L enter the compatibility conditions only through certain combinations whose number is, in general, smaller than the number of relations—so is the case, at least, when the polycrystal is anisotropic. These elements can then be eliminated, leaving us with relations among $L^*_{\alpha \beta km}$ that are independent of any knowledge of the crystal from which the polycrystal is prepared, beside the fact that it is uniaxial. Some of these material-independent relations appear in the form of symmetry of the linear-response coefficients of the polycrystal, as space tensors: Since λ^* in eq.(11) is symmetric in α, β and the transformation back to the physical basis acts only on the field indices, the tensors $L^*_{(km)}$ must be symmetric—a nontrivial information; these account for $3n(n-1)/2$ of the $9n(n-1)/2$ compatibility conditions. All the other material-independent relations can be obtained in the following way: Since all the matrices $L^*(\alpha \beta)$ —only six of them are independent because of the $\alpha - \beta$ symmetry—are diagonal in the eigenbasis, any three of them must satisfy the compatibility conditions.

$$C [L^*(\alpha \beta), L^*(\gamma \delta), L^*(\epsilon \eta)] = 0. \quad (16)$$

These relations are symmetric with respect to any permutation of the three argument matrices, and are identities when any two of the arguments are equal. Even those equations that remain after this is taken into account, are not all independent, but they do contain all the material-independent relations.

We now turn to some examples. When the polycrystal is isotropized, it has an effective response matrix L^* —whose $n(n+1)/2$ independent elements are scalars—which must satisfy eq.(15) with L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} . There are no material-independent relations in this case.

In the most common case of two fields-such as the thermoelectric and magnetoelectric effects-there are, altogether, nine compatibility conditions (that involve L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp}) one for each pair of space indices, leaving only twelve independent thermoelectric coefficients for an arbitrary polycrystal of a uniaxial crystal, when L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} are given. These can be written, conveniently, as

$$\begin{vmatrix} e(\alpha\beta) & m(\alpha\beta) & a(\alpha\beta) \\ e^{\perp} & m^{\perp} & a^{\perp} \\ e^{\parallel} & m^{\parallel} & a^{\parallel} \end{vmatrix} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Here,

$$L^{\parallel} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{\parallel} & a^{\parallel} \\ a^{\parallel} & m^{\parallel} \end{pmatrix}, \quad L^{\perp} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{\perp} & a^{\perp} \\ a^{\perp} & m^{\perp} \end{pmatrix}, \quad L^*(\alpha\beta) = \begin{pmatrix} e^*(\alpha\beta) & a^*(\alpha\beta) \\ a^*(\alpha\beta) & m^*(\alpha\beta) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (18)$$

are, respectively, the two principal response matrices of the single crystal, and the α, β response matrix of the polycrystal. The elements of L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} enter these relations in two combinations that can be eliminated to leave seven crystal-independent relations. Three of these imply the symmetry $L^*(\beta\alpha) = L^*(\alpha\beta)$ (beyond the Onsager relations); the remaining four amounts to the six triplets $\{e(\alpha\beta), m(\alpha\beta), a(\alpha\beta)\}$ ($\alpha\beta = xx, yy, zz, xy, xz, yz$) being all in the same plane in the (e, m, a) space (the determinant of any three vanishes). The most general polycrystal, made of a uniaxial crystal, thus has only fourteen independent constants-when we have no information on L^{\parallel}, L^{\perp} -instead of the twenty-one that a general crystal has.

as a demonstration, we calculated, directly, the general multifield response matrix for a model isotropized polycrystal⁷. The basic element of the model is a spherical shell, of arbitrary proportions, in which the small domains of the single crystal are oriented with their \parallel -axis along the radius of the shell. Space is then filled with such shells of different proportions; then, these shells are filled from within, by other shells-not necessarily concentric with the one in which they are nested. We continue in this vein, in an infinite sequence of nestings, to fill the whole volume of space. This is a generalization of the model of Schulgasser² who calculated the effective coefficient for the special case of space-filling spheres, and for the single-field case. One then solves exactly for the effective response matrix, L^* , of such an isotropic medium and finds that it satisfies

$$L^*(L^{\parallel})^{-1}L^* + (d-2)L^* - (d-1)L^{\perp} = 0, \quad (19)$$

where d is the dimension of the problem. Multiplying by $L^{\perp}L^{*-1}$ on the left we get

$$L^{\perp}(L^{\parallel})^{-1}L^* - (d-1)L^{\perp}L^{*-1}L^{\perp} - (d-2)L^{\perp} = 0. \quad (20)$$

As all the matrices involved are symmetric, so is the right-hand-side of eq.(20) and so must the product on the left-hand-side be; this is, however, just the content of the compatibility conditions eq.(15) (remember that this condition is symmetric in the three arguments); as expected, L^* for this model satisfies the compatibility conditions.

The arguments we have presented do not extend-to our knowledge-to polycrystals of more general single crystals. This would have required the simultaneous diagonalization of three or more matrices which is not possible, in general (except for special cases where the three matrices are linearly dependent, for example, in which case our results still apply).

One interesting generalization pertains to the case where the polycrystal contains regions that are filled with either an ideal "insulator" -having $L=0$ -or an ideal "conductor"-for which the diagonal elements of L are infinite. In the former case all the

currents vanish in the regions occupied by the insulator (enclosures of vacuum will have this property in connection with the thermoelectric effect); this implies the appropriate zero-derivative boundary condition, in the crystals, at their boundaries with the insulator. In the case of an ideal "conductor" (such as enclosures of vacuum in the case of multispecies diffusion) all the potentials are constants on these boundaries. In either case the presence of the added material has a purely geometrical effect-entering, as it does, only through the location of the boundaries-and it certainly does not couple the eigenfields; all our results thus remain intact. (We assume that the added material does not percolate so as to render the effective properties trivial; e.g., if a conductor percolates in the direction along which the currents are measured, the polycrystal will have an infinite response.)

The question of polycrystals made of uniaxial crystals, that we have treated here, is not, altogether, divorced from that of two-phase mixtures discussed in ref. 6. One can prepare a material with uniaxial symmetry by forming very-thin-layer laminates of two isotropic components. The effective L^{\parallel} and L^{\perp} response matrices of the mixture are given, respectively, by the harmonic mean, and the mean of the response matrices of the two components. The composite made of small grains of such a laminate, is a special case of the sort of "polycrystals" we deal with in this paper. Not all the allowed L^{\parallel} , L^{\perp} can be obtained in this way because the means obey certain inequalities which L^{\parallel} , L^{\perp} need not obey. In the cases where this is possible, our results here can be shown to follow also from the results on two-phase mixtures.

All our results can be extended to the case of complex response matrices in a way that is described in ref. 6.

Clearly, results that have been derived elsewhere for uncoupled fields, can be applied to the eigenfields, and their meaning then expressed in terms of the "physical" fields. Take any result that is valid for the single-field case constituting an equality or an inequality involving the constants of the crystal and of the polycrystal. If this result holds for all the eigenfields, it can be written as a diagonal-matrix-relation. This relation has then to be written such as to have, on each side, an expression of the form $\dots \lambda^a (\lambda^d)^{-1} \lambda^c (\lambda^d)^{-1} \dots$, (both sides beginning and ending with the same power) where the λ 's are the diagonal response matrices in the eigenbasis, all of which transform in the same way. The same relation then holds in the physical basis, with the λ 's replaced by the L 's.

Other examples of such single-field results that call for a generalization to the multifield case are bounds on the effective constants^{1,2} and also improved simultaneous bounds on pairs of constants analogous to those found by Bergman^{8,9} for two-phase composites.

Acknowledgement: We thank K. Schulgasser for useful comments.

REFERENCES

1. K. Schulgasser, J. Phys. C 10, 407 (1977); and more recently: M. Avellaneda, A.V. Cherkaev, K.A. Lurie, and G.W. Milton J. Appl. Phys. 63, (10) 4989 (1988), and many references therein.
2. K. Schulgasser, J. Appl. Phys. 54, 1380 (1983).
3. H.B.C. Casimir, Rev. Mod. Phys. 17, 343 (1945).
4. H.B. Callen Thermodynamics, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, (1960).
5. See, for example, H. Goldstein classical Mechanics Addison Wesley, Reading (1950). A detailed proof, in a context similar to the present one, can be found in ref. 6.
6. M. Milgrom and S. Shtrikmam, preprint (1989).
7. M. Milgrom and S. Shtrikmam, Preprint (1989).
8. D.J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 1531 (1976).
9. D.J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 4304 (1976).

A LAYERED-SHELL MODEL OF ISOTROPIC COMPOSITES
WITH EXACT EXPRESSIONS FOR THE EFFECTIVE PROPERTIES

Mordehai Milgrom
Department of Physics
and
S. Shtrikman
Department of Electronics*

Weizmann Institute of Science
76100 Rehovot, Israel

Abstract:

A family of models, for multicomponent, isotropic mixtures, is suggested and discussed for which the exact values of the effective, linear-response constants can be calculated: The basic unit of the model is a hollow system of contacting concentric shells, each of which is made of one of the components. Space is packed with such units of different sizes, but the same proportions; the cavity within each such shell system is then packed with similar systems, and this continues in an infinite nesting sequence. We deal with the general case of a linear-response phenomenon involving n coupled driving fields; the effective response matrix is given in a closed form as a function of the volume fractions and the response matrices of the components. Some sub-families are treated in more detail. For example, a two-shell two-phase family spanned by q , volume fraction of the shells within the sphere they define. The special case $q=1$ is the well-known coated-sphere model. Varying q between zero and one, we get exact models that cover the whole range of allowed values of the effective constant of any isotropic composite. Another special case of interest is $1 \gg q$ (very thin shells). The value of the effective response matrix, L , is derived for this model, for a multicomponent mixtures; this turns out to have a simple form. The response matrix is symmetric under the interchange of any two components. This thin-shell model is an automatically isotropized laminate.

I. INTRODUCTION

The role of specific models in the study of the effective linear-response properties of multicomponent composites is two-fold: (i) They provide estimators of the effective properties of composites. (ii) More importantly, they serve as testing grounds for various general ideas that pertain to such composites; in particular, they help one assay the strengths of various bounds that one can derive, on the effective properties, from general arguments¹⁻¹⁰. Some of these models—such as the coated-sphere model—actually serve to delineate bounds of some significance¹. To cope with the ever-increasing sophistication of the bounds one is usually forced to employ solvable models of equal involvement; notably, hierarchical models of different degrees^{11,8,12}.

We add to the library of exactly solvable models, a family of simple models of composites that is, however, rather rich, and may serve as an additional test-bed, in the

*Also with the Department of physics, University of California, San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093.

light of which one can consider the effective properties of composites. The models involve hollow multilayered spherical shells that fill space and which are filled from within, by similar shells-not, necessarily concentrically-in an infinite sequence of nesting. As they stand, the models are non-hierarchical, but, clearly, they may be incorporated into sundry hierarchical models.

All the results are derived for the general case of linear-response to n coupled driving fields, such as in the thermoelectric and magnetoelectric effects, or coupled multispecies diffusion. To our knowledge, there are no exact model-results, in the literature, for the coupled, multifield case.

The model is described in §II, where we also state the results for the single-field case. In §III we give the general formalism for calculating the effective response matrix for the general, multifield and multicomponent case. Section IV specializes to two-component models. In §V we show how working in the eigenbasis of fields, that can be defined for two-phase mixtures, one greatly facilitates the handling of this case. Further miscellaneous points are made in §VI.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE MODEL-THE SINGLE-FIELD CASE

The basic element of the model is a hollow, d -dimensional sphere that is made of p concentric shells, S_k , bounded by radii r_{k-1} and r_k ; $k=1, \dots, p$ (see Fig. 1). The shell S_k is filled with component k having a response coefficient value ϵ_k . This coefficient can represent the dielectric constant, the magnetic permeability, the electric- or heat-conductivity, or the like. The volume fraction of component k is thus

$$v_k = \frac{r_k^d - r_{k-1}^d}{r_p^d - r_0^d}; \quad \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k = 1 \right). \quad (1)$$

This shell system is also characterized by the volume fraction of the sphere occupied by the components: $q = (r_p^d - r_0^d) / r_p^d$. Imagine now that the hollow within r_0 is filled with a trial equivalent medium of coefficient ϵ and the whole sphere is embedded in the same medium. Can a value of ϵ be chosen such that the embedded sphere will not make itself felt outside; namely, that an externally applied field \vec{E}_0 will induce a displacement $\vec{D} = \epsilon \vec{E}_0$, outside?

If this is possible, we can construct a composite of the p components that will have ϵ as its exact effective coefficient: As shown in Fig. 2, in the first stage one fills space with shell systems, like that described above, with different sizes but the same proportions; the hollows within these systems are then filled-in a second nesting stage-with similar systems; continuing in this vein, in an infinite but converging nesting procedure, the whole volume of space is filled with the components. After the ℓ 'th nesting stage, a fraction $1 - (1-q)^\ell$ of space is filled with the components. The resulting composite has isotropic linear-response properties, by construction, with $\epsilon(\epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_p, q)$.

This model takes a step beyond the multicoated-sphere model, in that the equivalent medium is both inside and outside the basic unit of layered shells. The resulting equation for the effective coefficient is then quadratic instead of linear. Further steps in this direction are not possible; for example, there is no equivalent medium in the case of a basic unit made of spaced-out concentric shells.

We defer the derivation of the expression for ϵ to §III where a formalism is described and the effective coefficients are derived, for the more general problem of coupled multifield phenomena. Here we only describe the procedure-as an introduction to the

more general problem-and give the results for the single-field case. We seek field configurations whereby the driving field outside the single shell system is homogeneous and hence derivable from a potential $\varphi(\vec{r}) = \phi(r)\cos\theta$ where r and θ are polar coordinates; the potential must have the same θ -dependence all over the system. Within each shell, $\varphi(\vec{r})$ satisfies the Laplace equation and thus $\phi(\vec{r})$ must then be of the form

$$\phi(r) = a_k r + \hat{b}_k r^{-(d-1)}; \quad r_{k-1} \leq r \leq r_k. \quad (2)$$

Here $k=0, \dots, p+1$ with $r_{-1}=0$, and r_{p+1} arbitrary but larger than r_p ; d is the dimension of the problem. We require a homogeneous field outside the outermost shell, i.e. $\hat{b}_{p+1} = 0$; we also require $\hat{b}_0 = 0$, lest the field diverge at $r = 0$; this leaves us with $2p+2$ unknowns. These are determined by the requirements that ϕ and $\frac{d\phi}{dr}$ be continuous across the $p+1$ boundaries r_0, \dots, r_p . A homogeneous set of linear equations is obtained whose coefficients depend on $\epsilon, \epsilon_1, \dots, \epsilon_p, v_1, \dots, v_p, q$ and a solution exists only when the determinant (of rank $2p+2$) of coefficients vanishes—a requirement that constitutes the (quadratic) equation for ϵ .

In §III we shall give a method, for calculating ϵ , that avoids such large determinants. Here we give the equation for ϵ for the two-component case:

$$v_1 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_1)}{\epsilon_1} + v_2 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_2)}{\epsilon_2} + \frac{qv_1 v_2}{\epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 d} (d'\epsilon_2 + \epsilon)(d'\epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2)(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon) - \frac{qv_2^2}{\epsilon_2} (\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(d'\epsilon_2 + \epsilon) = 0, \quad (3)$$

where component 2 is on the outside, and

$$d' \equiv d-1. \quad (4)$$

The field inside the cavity, while homogeneous, is not the same as that outside. the shielding factor $\sigma \equiv a_0/a_{p+1}$ is—as we were able to show—not larger than unity. Thus, in the complete model—medium, the field within a shell ℓ -times-nested, is reduced by a factor of at least σ^ℓ compared with the field outside the shells.

Given two components, the layered-shell models we construct from them by varying q from zero to unity, and allowing either component to fill the inner shell, cover the whole range of allowed value of the effective coefficient ϵ for any possible (isotropic) composite of the two materials.

To demonstrate this useful fact we first consider the limit of very thin shells: $q \rightarrow 0$. In this limit, eq. (3) approaches:

$$v_1 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_1)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_1)}{\epsilon_1} + v_2 \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_2)(\epsilon + d'\epsilon_2)}{\epsilon_2} = 0, \quad (5)$$

by which ϵ is symmetric under the interchange $v_1 \leftrightarrow v_2, \epsilon_1 \leftrightarrow \epsilon_2$ (amounting to an interchange of the two shells while they retain their volumes). Such symmetric composites have attracted much interest¹³. A celebrated symmetric estimator is given by the coherent potential approximation^{14,15}. It is also known that the bounds on the allowed values of ϵ are materialized for the two coated sphere models (our $q = 1$ case) with component 1 or 2 on the outside. Thus, starting with one component on the outside and

$q=1$, we lower q to zero; then, interchanging the two shells we leave ϵ intact; then we increase q to unity again (the volume fractions remaining the same all along). In the process we change ϵ continuously from one bound to the opposite; thus covering the whole allowed range.

Equation (5) provides a symmetric estimator of the effective coefficient of composites and is straightforwardly generalized to the case of p components:

$$\sum_{k=1}^p v_k \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_k)(\epsilon + d' \epsilon_k)}{\epsilon_k} = 0 \quad (6)$$

This follows as a special case of a result we derive in § III and is quite unavoidable once we know that eq. (6) holds for two components.

Equation (6) can also be written as

$$\epsilon^2 \epsilon_h^{-1} + (d-2)\epsilon - (d-1)\epsilon_m = 0, \quad (7)$$

where ϵ_m and ϵ_h are, respectively, the mean and harmonic mean of the ϵ_k 's:

$$\epsilon_m \equiv \sum_{k=1}^p v_k \epsilon_k, \quad \epsilon_h \equiv \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k \epsilon_k^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The fact that ϵ depends on the ϵ_k 's and v_k 's only through ϵ_m and ϵ_h is quite natural; after all, the local geometry, in any small neighborhood of a point, is that of a plane laminate (for the thin-shells limit). For planar laminates, the effective coefficient is ϵ_m , when the field is parallel to the plane, and ϵ_h when it is perpendicular. The thin-shell geometry combines the two with weights that depend on the dimensionality of the problem: For $d=1$ we have $\epsilon = \epsilon_h$; for a very large d one has $\epsilon \rightarrow \epsilon_m$; in two dimensions (parallel cylindrical shells) we have the compact expression $\epsilon = (\epsilon_m \epsilon_h)^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

In three dimensions, the physical (positive) solution is

$$\epsilon = \frac{\epsilon_h}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 + 8 \epsilon_m / \epsilon_h} - 1 \right). \quad (9)$$

This result is closely related to one obtained by Schulgasser¹⁶ for a model of isotropized polycrystalline powders (made of a single material). Beginning with a uniaxial material with a response tensor $\text{diag}(\epsilon_{\perp}, \epsilon_{\perp}, \epsilon_{\parallel})$ Schulgasser forms homogeneous spheres made of crystal grains, with their symmetry axis along the radius of the sphere. A space that is filled with such spheres acts as an isotropic medium with an effective

$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\parallel} (\sqrt{1 + 8 \epsilon_{\perp} / \epsilon_{\parallel}} - 1) / 2$. The connection with eq. (9)-pointed out by Schulgasser himself-comes about thus: If in our layered-shell model we choose among the many schemes of nesting, the one shown in Fig. 3 whereby the nesting is always concentric, we obtain a space that is filled with similar spheres; these are much like the spheres used by Schulgasser in his model with the role of ϵ_{\parallel} , ϵ_{\perp} played by our ϵ_h, ϵ_m .

Hence, the three-dimensional, thin-shell model with concentric nesting is a special case of Schulgasser's isotropized polycrystalline powder. On the other hand, our results for arbitrary nesting schemes can be used to enlarge the class of models for which Schulgasser's result for polycrystals applies: It is plain to see that if shells of arbitrary thicknesses, and not necessarily of the same proportions, are prepared from radially aligned grains of a uniaxial crystal, and these are nested in an arbitrary

fashion, the resulting medium will still have the effective constant value given by Schulgasser's expression. One way to see this is to observe that we can take ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 such that their mean equals ϵ_{\perp} and their harmonic mean equals ϵ_{\parallel} of the crystal.

For any polycrystalline construction as described above, there is an equivalent thin-shells composite for which is given by eq. (9); independent of the nesting scheme of such a composite. It is true that if $\epsilon_{\perp} < \epsilon_{\parallel}$ we cannot find such a physical composite that is equivalent to the polycrystalline powder-for $\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2 \geq 0$ we always have $\epsilon_m \geq \epsilon_h$ -but we can find, even in this case, unphysical ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , one of which is negative, and v_1, v_2 such that $\epsilon_h \geq \epsilon_m \geq 0$ and our derivation goes through, formally, in this case too. At any rate, we verified this by a direct calculation of the effective ϵ for a shell of arbitrary proportions.

we now turn briefly to the case where one of the components has a vanishing, or an infinite constant. For example, when ϵ stands for the electric conductivity, these correspond to an insulator and a superconductor, respectively. When $\epsilon_2 = 0$, the only non-negative solution of eq. (3) is $\epsilon = 0$; clearly no conduction is possible when all the spheres are coated by an insulator on the outside. When $\epsilon_1 = 0$ we get

$$\epsilon = \frac{v_2 q d'}{d - v_2 q} \epsilon_2; \quad (10)$$

the conductivity is finite for a finite value of q but goes to zero with q even though the volume fraction is finite. The reason for this behavior is that only the outer shell in the un-nested systems contribute to the conductivity-as the inner, insulating shell isolates all that is nested within this primary shell. The medium acts then as as if the volume fraction of the conductor is only $q v_2$. When one of the components is superconducting, if it is the outer component, ϵ_2 , the only non-negative solution is an infinite ϵ . When ϵ_1 is infinite we get

$$\frac{d - q v_2 d'}{q v_2} \epsilon_2. \quad (11)$$

So far we have discussed a one-parameter family of two-shell, two-phase models. More involved two-phase models can be obtained by arranging the two components in more than two alternating shells. Consider, for example, a three-shell configuration in which the first and third shells contain component 1 and the intermediate shell contains component 2. Fixing q and the volume fractions, the fraction, s , of the volume of component 1 that is in the inner shell ($0 \leq s \leq 1$) constitute a second parameter: $\epsilon = (\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, v_1, v_2, q, s)$. At the same time we want to consider a similar composite with component 2 divided between the first and third shell, and s now measuring the fraction of 2 in the third shell; for this $\epsilon = \hat{\epsilon}(\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2, v_1, v_2, q, s)$. For $s = 0$ and $s = 1$ we get the restricted family discussed before, and $\epsilon(s = 0) = \hat{\epsilon}(s = 1)$, $\epsilon(s = 1) = \hat{\epsilon}(s = 0)$. When $1 \gg q$ -the thin-shell limit- ϵ is independent of s ; when $q = 1$ we get the two-phase, doubly coated-sphere configuration. Here again, for q fixed at 1, the models with $0 \leq s \leq 1$ cover the whole allowed range of the effective ϵ .

When we consider two (uncoupled) linear-response constants, say ϵ and μ , of the same composite, the models of this sort, with $0 \leq s \leq 1$, fill a certain area in the ϵ - μ plane. The two-parameter model is thus helpful in examining simultaneous bounds on two effective constants^{2,3,10}. Schulgasser¹¹, for example, had employed hierarchical models to probe such simultaneous bounds.

III. FORMALISM: GENERALIZATION TO MULTIFIELD PHENOMENA

We now develop the formalism for calculating the effective constants of the layered-shell model and we do this for the general linear-response problem involving n coupled driving fields, derivable from potentials, which we shall treat as an n -tuple: $\varphi = (\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_n)$. The conjugate currents $\vec{J} = (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$ are linear in the potentials and given by

$$\vec{J}(\vec{r}) = -L(\vec{r}) \vec{\nabla} \varphi(\vec{r}) \quad (12)$$

Here L is the response matrix, generalizing ϵ .

In our multicomponent model, L is piecewise constant, taking the value L_k in the shell S_k . The potentials satisfy the n coupled equations

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{J} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (L \vec{\nabla} \varphi) = 0. \quad (13)$$

For a medium in which L is piecewise constant—such as ours—the potentials satisfy the Laplace equation within each component; across boundaries, φ and the normal component of \vec{J} are continuous. As described in §II, we want to calculate the response matrix, L , of the equivalent medium—one that is oblivious to the embedding of our shell system (with the effective medium filling the central cavity, as well). We then look for a solution of the field equations (13) with homogeneous fields, $\vec{\nabla} \varphi_k$, outside the shells. Without loss of generality, we choose all these fields in the same direction for all the fields—the polar z -axis. The φ -dependence cannot change across the spherical boundaries and so we must have, everywhere,

$$\varphi(\vec{r}) = \vartheta(r) \cos \theta. \quad (14)$$

The most general behavior possible for $\vartheta(r)$ within S_k (for φ to satisfy the Laplace equation) is

$$\vartheta(r) = a_k r + b_k r^{-d'}, \quad (15)$$

where a_k and b_k are n -tuplets of constants, and $d' = d - 1$. The continuity of ϑ across r_k requires:

$$a_k + b_k = a_{k+1} + b_{k+1} \zeta_{k+1}. \quad (16)$$

Here we have put $b_k \equiv \hat{b}_k r_k^{-d}$ and $\zeta_{k+1} \equiv r_{k+1}^d / r_k^d$.

The continuity of J_r across r_k reads:

$$L_k (a_k - d' b_k) = L_{k+1} (a_{k+1} - d' \zeta_{k+1} b_{k+1}). \quad (17)$$

In terms of the $2n$ -tuplets of coefficients $u_k \equiv (a_k, b_k)$ eqs. (16) (17) can be written as

$$A_k u_k = A_{k+1} Z_{k+1} u_{k+1}, \quad (18)$$

where, A_k is a $2n \times 2n$ matrix:

$$A_k \equiv \begin{pmatrix} I & I \\ L_k & -d' L_k \end{pmatrix}; \quad (19)$$

with I , the $n \times n$ unit matrix; and, Z_{k+1} is the diagonal matrix

$$Z_{k+1} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & \zeta_{k+1} I \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

We seek a solution for which $b_{p+1} = 0$, or $u_{p+1} = (a_{p+1}, 0)$. The field coefficients in the central hollow, u_0 , are then related to those outside the shell system, u_{p+1} , by

$$u_0 = Au_{p+1} \equiv A_0^{-1} A_1 Z_1 A_1^{-1} A_2 Z_2 \dots A_p^{-1} A_{p+1} u_{p+1} \quad (21)$$

(with the last factor of Z_{p+1} justifiably dropped for the above form of u_{p+1}). The matrices A_k are easily inverted to give

$$A_k^{-1} = d^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} d' & L_k^{-1} \\ 1 & -L_k^{-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Equation (21) can also be written as

$$u_0 = A_0^{-1} B_1 B_2 \dots B_p A_{p+1} u_{p+1}, \quad (23)$$

With

$$B_k \equiv A_k Z_k A_k^{-1} = d^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} d + \eta_k & -\eta_k L_k^{-1} \\ -d' & \eta_k L_k^{-1} + d' \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Here $\eta_k \equiv \zeta_k^{-1} = v_k q (r_p^d / r_{k-1}^d)$.

The transmission matrix, A , defined in eq. (21), is a function of the L_k 's, of q , of the volume fractions (through the η_k 's), and of L ; the latter being determined by requiring that the potentials are regular at the origin; i.e., that $b_0 = 0$, for any choice of a_{p+1} . Dividing A into quarters:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} A^{11} & A^{12} \\ A^{21} & A^{22} \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

we require, then, that $n \times n$ submatrix A^{21} vanish. For a system made of one set of shells, encapsulating the effective medium, and embedded in it, we have

$$A_0 = A_{p+1} = \begin{pmatrix} I & I \\ L & -d'L \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Writing then

$$B \equiv B_1 B_2 \dots B_p = \begin{pmatrix} B^{11} & B^{12} \\ B^{21} & B^{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (27)$$

we get $A^{21} \propto B^{11} - L^{-1} B^{21} + B^{12} L - L^{-1} B^{22} L = 0$, or finally,

$$L B^{12} L + L B^{11} - B^{22} L - B^{21} = 0, \quad (28)$$

This is the equation for the effective response matrix, of the d -dimensional layered-shell model. It is a coupled quadratic equation in the elements of L ; the B^{ij} 's are matrix-valued, rational functions of the L_k 's—the response matrices of the components.

One may ask at this point whether a legitimate solution—one in which L is real, symmetric, and positive-definite—always exists. Equation (28) is a set of n^2 equations but there are only the $n(n+1)/2$ independent elements of L as unknowns. We shall come back to this question in §V.

We note that the submatrix A^{11} of A plays the role of the shielding matrix for the

shell system giving the field strengths in the cavity in terms of those outside the system: $a_0 = A^{11} a_{p+1}$. The shielding matrix is given by

$$A^{11} = d^{-1} (L^{-1} B_{L+L}^{22} + L^{-1} B^{21} + d' B^{12} + d' B^{11}), \quad (29)$$

or, eliminating the first two, or the last two terms, by use of eq.(28) we get

$$A^{11} = B^{11} + B^{12} L = L^{-1} (B^{21} + B^{22} L). \quad (30)$$

After ℓ nesting steps the fields are reduced by $(A^{11})^\ell$.

We now consider the two limiting models with $1 \gg q$, and $q=1$. From the definition of η_k [below eq. (24)] we see that $\eta_k = v_k q + O(q^2)$. Retaining only the lowest order in q we find from eq. (24)

$$B_k \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} v_k \begin{pmatrix} I & -L_k^{-1} \\ -d' L_k & d' I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (31)$$

and to the same order

$$B = \prod_{k=1}^p B_k \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^p v_k \begin{pmatrix} I & -L_k^{-1} \\ -d' L_k & d' I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (32)$$

Here, I_{2n} is the $2n \times 2n$ unit matrix. Defining the mean, M , and harmonic-mean, H , of the L_k 's:

$$M \equiv \sum_{k=1}^p v_k L_k; \quad H \equiv \left(\sum_{k=1}^p v_k L_k^{-1} \right)^{-1}, \quad (33)$$

we have

$$B \approx I_{2n} + qd^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} I & -H^{-1} \\ -d' M & d' I \end{pmatrix}. \quad (34)$$

Identifying the quarter submatrices of B and using eq. (28), we get, to lowest order in q ,

$$LH^{-1}L + (d-2)L - (d-1)M = 0, \quad (35)$$

as the equation for the effective response matrix of the thin-shells composite—a generalization of eq. (7) to the multifield problem. Note that M and H —and hence L —are invariant under a permutation of any of the shells (each keeping its thickness). Note also that M and H are symmetric and positive-definite matrices—as are all the L_k 's. We shall show in § V that eq.(35) always has a unique, real, symmetric, and positive-definite solution.

The shielding matrix for this case can be obtained by substituting the B^{ij} 's from eq. (31) into eq. (30):

$$A^{11} = I - \frac{qd'}{d} (L^{-1} M - I) + O(q^2) = I - \frac{q}{d} (H^{-1} L - I) + O(q^2). \quad (36)$$

We shall show in § V that its eigenvalues are not larger than 1.

We now turn to the case $q=1$ which corresponds to $r_0=0$. One can get the equation for L , in this case, by taking the limit $r_0 \rightarrow 0$, in eq.(28). It is, however, easier to re-derive this equation by replacing A_0^{-1} with A_1^{-1} , as the first factor on the right-hand-side of eq.(21)-this corresponds to filling the central cavity with component 1, instead of the trial medium-and requiring, as before, that the lower-left quarter of the resulting transmission matrix vanish. This matrix is now given by $A_1^{-1}B_2 \dots B_p A_{p+1}$ into which L enters only through A_{p+1} . The resulting equation is thus linear in L -in contrast with the general, $q \neq 1$, case. If we write

$$\hat{B} = B_2 \dots B_p = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{B}^{11} & \hat{B}^{12} \\ \hat{B}^{21} & \hat{B}^{22} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

we get $\hat{B}^{11} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{21} + (\hat{B}^{12} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{22})L = 0$ or

$$L = (\hat{B}^{22} - L^{-1}\hat{B}^{12})^{-1} (L^{-1}\hat{B}^{11} - \hat{B}^{21}). \quad (38)$$

This is the explicit expression for the effective response matrix for a multifield linear-response in a multicoated-sphere composite-a special case of the multicomponent-shell model.

Sihvola and Lindel^{17,18} use similar transmission-matrix methods to solve for the effective constant of a multicoated-sphere configuration for the single-field case.

IV. EXAMPLES: TWO-COMPONENT MODELS

Substituting the expressions for B_1, B_2 from eq. (24) in eq. (27) and using eq. (28) we write the general equation for the effective response matrix, L , of a two-component, layered-shell model:

$$LK_1L + K_2L + LK_3 + kL + K_4 = 0, \quad (39)$$

where,

$$K_1 = (d + \eta_1) \eta_2 L_2^{-1} + \eta_1 (d + d' \eta_2) L_1^{-1}; \quad (40)$$

$$K_2 = \eta_1 \eta_2 d' L_1 L_2^{-1}; \quad (41)$$

$$K_3 = -\eta_1 \eta_2 d' L_1^{-1} L_2; \quad (42)$$

$$k = d(d-2)(\eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_1 \eta_2); \quad (43)$$

$$K_4 = -\eta_1 d' (d + \eta_2) L_1 - \eta_2 d' (d + d' \eta_1) L_2 = 0. \quad (44)$$

Here, η_1, η_2 are given in terms of q and the volume fractions by

$$\eta_1 = \frac{v_1 q}{1-q}, \quad \eta_2 = \frac{v_2 q}{1-v_2 q} \quad (45)$$

There is special interest in the effective response matrix of a two-component coated-sphere model, especially because they define bounds on the allowed values of the effective coefficients. In this ($p=2$) case (with component 2 outside), $\hat{B} = B_2$ and the quarter

submatrices of \hat{B} can be read off eq. (24). Noting that $\eta_2 = (r_2^d - r_1^d) / r_1^d = v_2 / v_1$, we find

$$L_{CS} = \left\{ v_2 L_2^{-1} + (v_1 + d') L_1^{-1} \right\}^{-1} (v_2 d' L_1^{-1} L_2 + v_1 d + v_2), \quad (46)$$

for the response matrix of a coated-sphere model with component 2 outside. When only one field is involved, equation (46) reduces to the well-known single-field result.

V. REPRESENTATION OF THE PROBLEM IN THE EIGENBASIS

It has been shown¹⁹ that the multifield, linear-response process of a two-component composite can be described in some eigenbasis of potentials and currents, $\psi = (\psi_1, \psi_2, \dots, \psi_n)$ and $\vec{J} = (\vec{J}_1, \vec{J}_2, \dots, \vec{J}_n)$, respectively, that are totally decoupled; these are, respectively, linear combinations of the "physical" fields φ and \vec{J} . The argument is based on the fact that any two real, symmetric, positive-definite matrices (of the same rank) can be diagonalized simultaneously by a real, congruent transformation: There exists a matrix W such that

$$\begin{aligned} W L_1 \tilde{W} &= \lambda^{(1)} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{(1)}, \lambda_2^{(1)}, \dots, \lambda_n^{(1)}); \\ W L_2 \tilde{W} &= \lambda^{(2)} \equiv \text{diag}(\lambda_1^{(2)}, \lambda_2^{(2)}, \dots, \lambda_n^{(2)}). \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

The eigenfields are then

$$\psi = \tilde{W}^{-1} \phi, \quad \vec{J} = W \vec{J}, \quad (48)$$

and one has

$$\vec{J} = -\lambda^{(1)} \vec{\nabla} \psi, \quad \text{and} \quad \vec{J} = -\lambda^{(2)} \vec{\nabla} \psi, \quad (49)$$

in components 1 and 2, respectively. Milgrom and Shtrikman¹⁹ use the existence of this basis to derive compatibility conditions, on the response matrix of any two-phase composite, that require no knowledge of the volume fractions or the microstructure of the composite. For an isotropic composite, such as the one we discuss in this paper, the relation is

$$L L_1^{-1} L_2 = L_2 L_1^{-1} L \quad (50)$$

Here, we can use the eigenbasis for the following purposes-pertinent to two-phase shell composites: (i) To show that there exists a physical solution to the equation for L . (ii) To show that the shielding matrix has eigenvalues that are not larger than unity. (iii) To demonstrate that all the multifield results we have derived for two-shell composite, can be obtained, straightforwardly, from the single-field result.

When working in the eigenbasis of the two-phase composite, L_1, L_2 are everywhere replaced by the $\lambda^{(1)}, \lambda^{(2)}$. As all the B^{ij} 's appearing in § III are rational functions of the L_k 's, they are also diagonal in the eigenbasis, and so are the matrix coefficients K_i in eq. (39). Multiplying eq. (39) by W on the left, and \tilde{W} on the right and defining $k_1 \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} K_1 W^{-1}$, $k_2 \equiv W K_2 W^{-1}$, $k_3 \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} K_3 \tilde{W}$, $k_4 \equiv W K_4 \tilde{W}$, and $\lambda \equiv W L \tilde{W}$, we get

$$\lambda k_1 \lambda + k_2 \lambda + \lambda k_3 + k_4 \lambda = 0, \quad (51)$$

with the k_i 's all diagonal.

Now, since L_1 and L_2 are positive definite, eqs.(40)-(44) tell us that k_1 is positive and k_4 is negative. There is then always a solution, λ , of the matrix equation (51) that is diagonal and positive; hence, the original equation (39) always has a solution L that is real, symmetric, and positive-definite as is required from a response matrix.

The many-component composite does not, in general, have an eigenbasis of decoupled fields. The many-component, thin-shell model is, nonetheless, amenable to an attack similar to the above: The matrices M and H which enter eq. (35) are linear combinations of symmetric, positive-definite matrices and thus share the same properties. They can, then, be diagonalized simultaneously by a congruent transformation into $m \equiv W M \tilde{W}$, $h \equiv W H \tilde{W}$ (the L_k 's themselves are not diagonalized by W , in the general, $p > 2$, case). It is easy to see, in the same way as above, that eq. (35) always has a legitimate solution:

$$L = W^{-1} \left\{ \frac{h}{2} \left(\sqrt{(d-2)^2 + 4(d-1) m h^{-1}} - 1 \right) \right\} \tilde{W}^{-1}. \quad (52)$$

The shielding matrix is also diagonal in the eigenbasis; it is, in fact, diagonalized by the similarity transformation:

$$a^{11} \equiv \tilde{W}^{-1} A^{11} \tilde{W}, \quad (53)$$

and so the elements of a^{11} are the eigenvalues of A^{11} . The elements m_k, h_k, λ_k of m, h, λ , respectively, are not, in general, the eigenvalues of M, H, L , as the former are not obtained from the latter by a similarity transformation. However, the elements of diagonal matrices like $m h^{-1}, h^{-1} \lambda$ etc. are the eigenvalues of the corresponding matrices in the physical basis; these do transform by similarity. Note that the response matrices connect potential to fluxes, and hence transform by congruence; the shielding matrix and the like connect potentials to potentials, and transform by similarity. Now because M and H are, respectively, the mean and harmonic mean of symmetric, positive-definite matrices, one can show that.

$$n_k \leq \lambda_k \leq m_k, \quad (54)$$

and so

$$a^{11} = I - \frac{q}{d} (h^{-1} \lambda - I) \leq I, \quad (55)$$

and so the eigenvalues of A^{11} that is given in eq. (36) are not larger than unity. We can also prove that this is true for the general case with $1 \leq q$ and two components only. We suspect that the statement is true, in general, but cannot offer a proof.

All the results we derived for the two-phase case can also be derived by writing a known, single-field result for the eigenfields and transforming back to the physical basis. In general, take any result that is valid for the single-field, two-phase case constituting an equality or an inequality involving the constants of the components and of the mixture; if this result holds for all the eigenfields, it can be written as a diagonal-matrix-relation. This relation has then to be written such as to have, on each side, an expression of the form... $\lambda^a (\lambda^b)^{-1} \lambda^c (\lambda^d)^{-1}$..., where the λ 's are the diagonal response matrices in the eigenbasis, all of which transform in the same way. The same relation then holds in the physical basis, with the λ 's replaced by the L 's. As an example, we rederive the expression for the coated sphere model, for the multi-field case. The well known expression for the effective constant ϵ is written, in three dimensions, as

$$\epsilon = \left\{ v_2 \epsilon_2^{-1} + (2+v_1) \epsilon_1^{-1} \right\}^{-1} (2v_2 \epsilon_1^{-1} \epsilon_2 + 3v_1 + v_2). \quad (56)$$

In the multifield case, this holds for each eigenfield separately and so it holds as a matrix expression with the ϵ 's replaced by the diagonal λ 's. Now, multiplying by W on the left and by \tilde{W} on the right, we get the same equation for the L 's, and this gives eq.(46) The form in which the right-hand-side of eq.(56) is put allows us to insert the appropriate W^{-1} factors, so that each λ is transformed into its corresponding L .

The same is true for inequalities; but they are understood as applying between quadratic forms, when the matrices in question are symmetric-expressing the fact that some matrix is positive definite. Alternatively, as the case may be, the matrix inequality is to be understood as applying to the eigenvalues. For example, if we show that the shielding factor $\sigma \leq 1$, in the single-field case, it follows that the shielding matrix is not larger than I -in the sense that its eigenvalues are not larger than unity-As A^{11} and I transform in the same way as we go from the eigenbasis to the physical basis.

It is known¹ that the single-field, coated-sphere, effective constants constitute bounds on the effective constants of a two-phase mixture; does the multifield result, eq. (46), play a similar role? Here the situation is not so simple. Which of the two coated spheres (with component 1 inside or outside) is the upper bound and which the lower one, depends on which of the two components has the larger constant. In the multifield case, it is possible that for some of the eigenfields, one component has larger constants and for the other eigenfields the other does; we can then not write a simple matrix inequality in the eigenbasis. If, however, we have two components for which $L_2 - L_1$ has a definite sign, as a quadratic form-say it is positive definite-then it follows that L_{CS} given in eq. (46) is an upper bound to the response matrix, L , of any composite made of components 1 and 2, in the sense that $L_{CS} - L$ is nonnegative; eq. (46) gives the lower bound, in the same sense, when 1 and 2 are interchanged.

VI. CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have derived the expression for the effective response matrix of a novel model for isotropic composites. The general problem of linear-response to n coupled driving fields, and p components, in d dimensions have been treated. All our results are valid for complex response matrices^{20,21}. This family of models arise as a natural generalization of the muchdiscussed, coated- and multicoated-sphere models. The effective response matrix for the multifield case has not been given before, even for the latter, and is derived in this paper as a special case. Further extension to spaced-out shells is not possible; but, one can, as always, incorporate the shell model in any hierarchical scheme to form more complex composite models.

For example, we can build a hierarchical composite based on the thin-shell model, by beginning with a pure material-say component 2-and add to it an small increment of 1 to form a thin shell composite; this is then used with another increment of 1 to form a thin-shell composite. Continuing in this manner in a well known procedure (a detailed-but by no means the first-account is given in ref. 22) we obtain in the limit of infinitesimal increments, a differential equation that gives the effective constant, ϵ , of the composite, for a finite volume fraction of 1:

$$\frac{dx}{dV} = - \frac{(x-1)(x+d')}{Vd'} \quad (57)$$

where, $x \equiv \epsilon / \epsilon_1$ and V is the total volume; the former is to be integrated between ϵ_2 / ϵ_1 and ϵ / ϵ_1 , and the latter between V_2 and $V_1 + V_2$. Integrating eq. (57) we find, rather interestingly the coated-sphere expression for ϵ . Thus, beginning with one component and adding the other continuously we get a composite with the maximal and minimal allowed values of ϵ -those realized by the two possible coated-sphere configurations, here realized by hierarchical thin-shell models. Clearly, by alternating the component we add incrementally, we can obtain an hierarchical, thin-shell model for any value between

the bounds, for given volume fractions: any isotropic composite is realizable by a thin-shell model composite.

composites made of planar laminates have received much warranted attention^{8,9,12}, and, in fact, play the role of a basic building-block of model composites. The thin-shell layered-shell models are akin to these and, presumably, can play similar roles. Like planar laminates, they have an effective response matrix that is invariant to an interchange of any of the layers. An advantage of the shell models is their built-in isotropy; it frees one from having to isotropize the laminate model when an isotropic model is sought.

All our results can be extended to ellipsoidal shells-delimited by confocal ellipsoids-to describe anisotropic composites²³. Some results that are useful for this end can be found in refs. 24, 21.

Another extension that invites further treatment is the derivation of the effective elastic properties of the shell models-for example, as exactly solvable models for fiber composites⁶.

Acknowledgement: We thank K. Schulgasser for useful comments, and Y. Dreyer for the execution of the figures.

REFERENCES

1. Z. Hashin and S. Shtrikman, J. Appl. Phys. 33, 3125 (1962).
2. D. J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 1531 (1976).
3. D. J. Bergman, Phys. Rev. B 14, 4304 (1976).
4. D. J. Bergman, Physics Reports (Section C of Physics Letters) 43, 377 (1978).
5. P. N. Sen, C. Scala and M. H. Cohen, Geophysics 46, 781 (1981).
6. Z. Hashin, J. Appl. Mechanics 50, 481 (1983).
7. J. G. Berryman, J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. 18, 585 (1985).
8. G. W. Milton, in Homogenization and Effective Moduli of Materials and Media, Eds. J. L. Ericksen, et.al., Springer, New York, (1986), p. 150.
9. G. W. Milton, Proceedings of the SIAM Conference on Multi-Phase Flow, Xerox Training Center, Leesburg, Virginia June 2-4, 1986, edited by G. Papanicolaou.
10. J. G. Berryman and G. W. Milton, J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys. 21, 87 (1988).
11. K. Schulgasser, Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer, 20, 1273 (1977).
12. G. W. Milton, Commun. Math. Phys. 99, 463 (1985).
13. M. J. Beran, in Composite Materials, Vol. 2, Ed. G. P. Sendeckyi, Academic Press, 1974, p. 209.
14. R. J. Elliott, J. A. Krumhansl, and P. L. Leath, Rev. Mod. Phys. 46, 465 (1974).
15. R. Landauer, in Electrical Transport and Optical Properties of Inhomogeneous Media, J. C. Garland D. B. Tamer Ed. Amer. Inst. Phys. New York (1978) p.1.
16. K. Schulgasser, J. Appl. Phys. 54, 1380 (1983).
17. A. Sihvola and I. V. Lindell, J. Electromagnetic Waves and Applications 2, 741(1988).
18. A. Sihvola and I. V. Lindell, J. Electromagnetic Waves and Applications 3, 37(1989).
19. M. Milgrom and S. Shtrikman, Preprint 1989.
20. G. W. Milton, J. Appl. Phys. 52 5286 (1981).
21. D. J. Bergman, Annals of Physics, 138, 78 (1982)
22. A. N. Norris, Mechanics of Materials 4, 1 (1985)
23. R. V. Kohn and G. W. Milton, in Homogenization and Effective Moduli of Materials and Media, Ed. J. L. Ericksen et'al. Springer, New York, 1986, p 97.
24. J. A. Osborn, Phys. Rev. 67, 351 (1945).

Figure captions

Figure 1. The schematics of a single shell-system.

Figure 2. The filling of space with basic shell systems to give the effective composite. The two components are represented by black and white, and the portions of space that are not yet filled, with an intermediate shade.

Figure 3. A specific sequence of space-filling by concentric nesting, that reproduces Schulgasser's model of isotropized polycrystals in which the crystal grains are arranged in solid spheres. The shades are of the same signification as in Fig. 2.

Figure 4. The extension of Schulgasser's model to a polycrystalline shell model. Crystalline grains of a uniaxial crystal are arranged in spherical shells so that the symmetry axis of each is along the radius of the shell in which it resides. Shells are then nested within shells in an infinite sequence.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

MANUFACTURE OF FIBER GLASS REINFORCED PLASTIC
POLES BY PRESS MOLDING METHOD

by

Williams P. Kao, Ph.D.*

1. Current market position of frp light poles in Taiwan.
2. Frp light poles properties.
3. Review of various pole manufacturing methods:
 - a. Filament winding method.
 - b. Centrifugal casting method.
 - c. Matched die press molding.
4. Press molding method:
 - a. Unidirectional smc.
 - b. Straight pole manufacturing.
 - c. Curved extender manufacturing.
 - d. Joint method.
5. Analysis and comparison among these manufacturing methods.
6. Conclusion.

* Tung Hsing FRP Corporation
P.O.Box 24-868
Taipei, Taiwan

ISBN 7-80003-062-8/TB-6

ISBN 0-08-037537-5